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Masterarbeit

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**Großräumige und kleinräumige Betrachtungen von pluvialen
Überflutungsschwerpunkten im Hinblick auf eine IKT-
Starkregenversuchsanlage für Versuche im Maßstab 1:1,
insbesondere auf Basis von Freeware -Computersimulationen.**

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Aufgabenstellung

Das IKT investiert in eine neue Versuchshalle mit einem weltweit einmaligen Großversuchsstand zur Untersuchung von Starkregen und Überflutung, mit der die komplexen technischen Zusammenhänge zur Niederschlagswasserbildung und -sammlung erstmals auf einer größeren Fläche (200 m²) im Maßstab 1:1 untersucht werden können.

In einem Teilbereich eines Hallenneubaus des IKT wird ein Versuchsstand für Überflutungszustände errichtet, in dem Entwässerungsgegenstände der Siedlungsentwässerung und abflusswirksame Flächen eingebaut und die komplexen technischen Zusammenhänge zur Niederschlagswasserbeseitigung simuliert werden können. So sollen unter anderem neue, innovative Konzepte zur schadlosen Ableitung von Niederschlagswasser im Straßenraum bei Starkregenereignissen entwickelt werden.

Vor diesem Hintergrund ist die Aufgabenstellung in der Masterarbeit eine großräumige (500x500 m) und kleinräumige Betrachtung (10x20 m) von pluvialen Überflutungsschwerpunkten in einem realen Gebiet der Siedlungsentwässerung. Im Hinblick auf die IKT-Starkregenversuchsanlage für Versuche im Maßstab 1:1 sollen Erkenntnisse gesammelt werden, insbesondere inwieweit auf Basis von Freeware -Computersimulationen praxisnahe Versuchsrandbedingungen festgelegt werden können. Für die hydrodynamische Abbildung von Abflüssen kann sowohl das Abflussverhalten an der Oberfläche ohne Betrachtung des Kanalnetzes als auch ein gekoppeltes Modell mit Interaktion zwischen Kanalnetz und Oberfläche mit Schnittstellen für Wasserein- und Wasseraustritte genutzt werden, soweit dies mit Open-Source-Software-Produkten möglich sein sollte.

Die neue IKT-Prüfanlage soll Starkregen und Überflutungen simulieren im Maßstab 1:1

Nachfolgend ist das Arbeitsprogramm beschrieben. In der Masterarbeit sind folgende Punkte zu bearbeiten:

ARBEITSPROGRAMM

1. Grundlagen und Definitionen von Rechenmodellen im Starkregenrisikomanagement.
2. Literaturrecherche zu unterschiedlichen Berechnungsmethoden zur Darstellung von pluvialen Oberflächenabflüssen und Überflutungssituationen (1D, 2D, 1D/2D).
3. Übersicht Freeware Softwareprodukten zur Anwendung für großräumige und auch kleinräumige Berechnungen. Darstellung der Einsatzgrenzen zur Einordnung und Abgrenzung ihrer Einsatzbereiche.

4. Wissenschaftliche Datenvorbereitung für die 1D- und 2D- numerisch-hydrodynamische Modellierung, einschließlich Datenerfassung, Datenbearbeitung und Validierung, wenn möglich mit Freeware-Produkten und anderen kostenfreien Mitteln.
5. Eigene, möglichst, gekoppelte 1D/2D – Berechnungen mit den Freeware Produkten für ein Einzugsgebiet und einer Kleinfläche aus diesem Gebiet, die innerhalb des Einzugsgebietes besonders charakteristisch ist.
6. Vergleich der Berechnungsergebnisse: Sind die Freeware Produkte geeignet? Welches Produkt liefert realitätsnahe Werte? Welche Modifikationen sind in den Berechnungen möglich (Regen, Oberflächen, Schnittstellen Kanalnetz etc.) um realitätsnahe Ergebnisse zu erzielen?
7. Empfehlungen an das IKT auf Basis der durchgeführten Berechnungen für die geplanten Starkregen-Versuchsanlagen. Die schriftliche Arbeit ist in dreifacher Ausführung ausgedruckt und gebunden am Prüfungsamt abzugeben. Jedem Exemplar soll ein Speichermedium beiliegen, welche die digitale Fassung der Arbeit sowie alle relevanten Literaturquellen und Daten beinhaltet. Die Arbeit ist in einem Kurzvortrag am Lehrstuhl für Siedlungswasserwirtschaft und Umwelttechnik vorzustellen.

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Prof. Dr.-Ing. habil. Marc Wichern

Abstract

Floods are the biggest natural disasters that cause many financial and human losses worldwide every year [1]. Numerous studies have been done on various aspects of this natural disaster. The purpose of this work was to examine the quality and capabilities of existing open-source numerical hydrodynamic models and their data preparation process, as well as their capabilities in microscale modeling since most numerical hydrodynamic models are preferably designed to model large areas [2].

First, comprehensive research was conducted on numerical hydrodynamic modeling methods and existing models. Next, two models were selected to analyze the desired watershed: EPA's Storm Water Management Model "SWMM" for one-dimensional modeling of the drainage system and the LISFLOOD-FP, initially developed by Bates & De Roo, two-dimensional modeling of the surface. Since only a single watershed was studied, special attention was paid to data collection and their accuracy. With the help of information available in several databases, numerous site surveys, as well as the use of geographic information systems for data processing, inputs were prepared for both models. The QGIS software was also used as a tool for pre-processing the inputs and post-processing the outputs.

While modeling with SWMM, the process of collecting and processing information was noticeably time-consuming; in addition to the need for multiple sources to provide the required information, applying a GIS product to evaluate and process the data was needed. Some data were also collected during a series of site surveys; in the course of the observations, the accuracy of the existing data was controlled as well. Building a model using LISFLOOD-FP did not require much time and detail; only the digital elevation model and performing a couple of QGIS processes were enough to obtain the necessary input data in order to build the model. Precipitation and infiltration data could be used in this model without the need for significant processing.

Once gathering and validating all the required data was completed, a model of the 3.98 hectares study area was built in one dimension by SWMM and in two dimensions by LISFLOOD-FP; afterward, the first simulations were performed by both models. The results were then calibrated whenever possible. After having the results of the calibrated models, with regard to flooding, the most critical spots of each result were selected for closer inspections. These critical points, each having an area around 500 square meters, were examined with the same approaches employed to generate the first eligible results. Moreover, inflows from the surrounding environment were added to these models as needed.

The assessment of micro-scale modeling was then followed by downsizing the entire study area in order to investigate the effect of the dimensions of the study area on the results, meaning that instead of selecting a location with very small dimensions and inevitably neglecting the influence of its surroundings, an entire watershed was downsized and modeled with the same methods. After having the results of all the three sets of models (an entire watershed, an isolated small area, and the downsized watershed), they were compared with each other and with an available pluvial flood¹ hazard map provided by the city of

¹ In the framework of this thesis, the pluvial flood events are simply referred to by the words "flood" or "flooding". In case other types of flooding are intended the type would be mentioned or a plural form of the "flood" would be used.

Gelsenkirchen as the reference.

The simulation results with freeware products show that both models are reasonably capable of detecting flood features such as critical points, flooding extent, and water depth. Although working with them is more complex than working with commercial products, the quality of the results with regard to the reference map was acceptable.

The results obtained for an isolated simulation of the critical points showed that disregarding the impact of surroundings leads to incorrect and unrealistic results, as expected.

Contrary to the results obtained for the critical points, the results obtained from the modeling of the downsized watershed provided acceptable accuracy; in particular, LISFLOOD-FP was able to predict the extent and depth of the flood with a minor difference. Also, for this watershed, both models could predict critical spots for more accurate analyses or for taking actions against flooding for this watershed.

Overall, it can be concluded that micro-scale modeling depends more on the quality of input data and provided details while building the model than on the selected product, and the open-source numerical hydrodynamic models are able to generate acceptable results.

Kurzfassung

Überflutungen sind die größten Naturkatastrophen, die jedes Jahr weltweit viele finanzielle und menschliche Verluste verursachen [1]. Es wurden zahlreiche Studien zu verschiedenen Aspekten dieser Naturkatastrophe veröffentlicht. Der Zweck dieser Arbeit war es, die Qualität und die Fähigkeiten vorhandener numerisch-hydrodynamischer Open-Source-Modelle und deren Datenvorbereitung zu untersuchen, sowie deren Fähigkeiten bei der kleinräumigen Modellierung, da die meisten numerisch-hydrodynamischen Modelle vor allem für die Modellierung großer Gebiete entwickelt wurden [2].

Zunächst wurde eine umfassende Recherche über numerisch-hydrodynamische Modellierungsmethoden und bestehende Modelle durchgeführt. Als nächstes wurden zwei Modelle ausgewählt, um das gewünschte Einzugsgebiet zu analysieren: Das „Storm Water Management Model, SWMM“ der EPA für die eindimensionale Modellierung des Entwässerungssystems und das ursprünglich von Bates & De Roo entwickelte LISFLOOD-FP für die zweidimensionale Modellierung der Oberfläche. Da nur ein einziges Einzugsgebiet untersucht wurde, wurde besonderes Augenmerk auf die Datenerfassung und deren Genauigkeit gelegt. Mit Hilfe von Informationen, die in verschiedenen Datenbanken verfügbar waren, zahlreichen Standortuntersuchungen sowie dem Einsatz von geografischen Informationssystemen zur Datenverarbeitung wurden die Eingaben für beide Modelle vorbereitet. Die QGIS-Software wurde auch als Werkzeug für die Vorverarbeitung der Eingabewerte und die Nachbearbeitung der Ausgabewerte verwendet.

Während der Modellerstellung mit SWMM war der Prozess des Erfassens und Verarbeitens von Daten deutlich zeitaufwendig; zusätzlich zu der Tatsache, dass mehrere Quellen die benötigten Daten zur Verfügung stellen mussten, war die Anwendung eines GIS-Produkts zur Auswertung und Verarbeitung der Daten erforderlich. Einige Daten wurden auch während einer Reihe von Vor-Ort-Untersuchung gesammelt; im Zuge dieser Observationen wurde auch die Genauigkeit der vorhandenen Daten kontrolliert. Die Erstellung eines Modells mit LISFLOOD-FP erforderte nicht viel Zeit und Details; lediglich das digitale Geländemodell und die Durchführung einiger QGIS-Prozesse reichten aus, um die erforderlichen Eingabedaten für die Erstellung des Modells zu erhalten. Niederschlags- und Infiltrationsdaten konnten in diesem Modell verwendet werden, ohne dass eine wesentliche Bearbeitung erforderlich war. Sobald die Erfassung und Validierung aller erforderlichen Daten vollständig abgeschlossen war, wurde ein eindimensionales Modell des 3,98 Hektar Untersuchungsgebiets mit SWMM und ein zweidimensionales Modell mit LISFLOOD-FP erstellt; anschließend wurden die ersten Simulationen mit beiden Modellen durchgeführt. Die Ergebnisse wurden dann, soweit möglich, kalibriert. Nachdem die Ergebnisse der kalibrierten Modelle vorlagen, wurden In Bezug auf Überflutung die Überflutungsschwerpunkten jedes Ergebnisses zur näheren Betrachtung ausgewählt.

Diese kritischen Stellen, die jeweils eine Fläche von etwa 500 Quadratmetern haben, wurden mit denselben Ansätzen untersucht, mit denen auch die ersten in Frage kommenden Ergebnisse erzeugt wurden. Darüber hinaus wurden diese Modelle bei Bedarf um Zuflüsse aus der Umgebung ergänzt.

Der Bewertung der kleinräumigen Modellierung wurde dann gefolgt, indem das gesamte

Untersuchungsgebiet verkleinert wurde, um die Auswirkung der Dimensionen des Untersuchungsgebiets auf die Ergebnisse zu untersuchen, d.h. anstatt einen Ort mit sehr kleinen Dimensionen auszuwählen und zwangsläufig den Einfluss der Umgebung zu vernachlässigen, wurde ein ganzes Einzugsgebiet verkleinert und mit den gleichen Methoden modelliert. Nachdem die Ergebnisse aller drei Modellsätze (gesamtes Einzugsgebiet, isoliertes kleines Gebiet und verkleinertes Einzugsgebiet) vorlagen, wurden sie miteinander und mit einer verfügbaren Starkregengefahrenkarte der Stadt Gelsenkirchen als Referenz verglichen. Die Simulationsergebnisse mit den Freeware-Produkten zeigen, dass beide Modelle einigermaßen in der Lage sind, Überflutungseigenschaften wie kritische Punkte, Überflutungsausmaß und Wassertiefe zu erkennen. Obwohl die Arbeit mit ihnen komplexer ist als mit kommerziellen Produkten, war die Qualität der Ergebnisse in Bezug auf die Referenzkarte akzeptabel.

Die Ergebnisse, die für die isolierte Simulation der kritischen Punkte erhalten wurden, zeigten, dass die Vernachlässigung des Einflusses der Umgebung, wie erwartet, zu falschen und unrealistischen Ergebnissen führt.

Im Gegensatz zu den Ergebnissen für die kritischen Punkte lieferten die Ergebnisse der Modellierung des verkleinerten Einzugsgebiets eine akzeptable Genauigkeit; insbesondere war LISFLOOD-FP in der Lage, das Ausmaß und die Tiefe des Überflutung mit einem geringen Abweichung vorherzusagen. Außerdem wären beide Modelle in der Lage, für dieses Einzugsgebiet Überflutungsschwerpunkten vorherzusagen, um genauere Analysen durchzuführen oder Maßnahmen gegen Überflutungen zu ergreifen.

Insgesamt lässt sich schlussfolgern, dass die kleinräumige Modellierung mehr von der Qualität der Eingabewerte und den zur Verfügung gestellten Details bei der Erstellung des Modells abhängt als von dem ausgewählten Produkt, und dass die numerisch-hydrodynamischen Open-Source-Modelle in der Lage sind, akzeptable Ergebnisse zu erzeugen.

Contents

Acknowledgments	I
Aufgabenstellung	II
Abstract	IV
Kurzfassung	VI
Contents	VIII
List of tables	XI
List of figures	XII
List of equations	XV
List of abbreviations	XVI
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Problem statement.....	1
1.2 Purpose	1
1.3 Approach	2
2 Basics and definitions of heavy rain risk management	3
2.1 Heavy rain.....	3
2.2 Types of floods	5
2.2.1 Pluvial (overland) floods	8
2.2.2 Flash floods	9
2.3 Risk management.....	9
2.3.1 Heavy rain risk management.....	9
2.3.1.1 Hydraulic Hazard Assessment (Hazard Maps)	11
2.3.1.2 Risk Assessment	11
2.3.1.3 Measures For Heavy Rain Risk Management	12
3 Numerical hydrodynamic modeling methods and tools	14
3.1 Numerical hydrodynamic modeling	14
3.2 Numerical hydrodynamic modeling methods.....	15
3.2.1 The 0D modeling approach	16
3.2.2 The 1D modeling approach	17
3.2.3 The 1D ⁺ modeling approach.....	20
3.2.4 The 2D ⁺ modeling approach	21
3.2.5 The 2D modeling approach	22
3.2.6 The 2D ⁺ modeling approach.....	24
3.2.7 The 3D modeling approach	24
3.2.8 Dual drainage concept.....	25
3.2.8.1 1D/1D Modeling Approach	26
3.2.8.2 1D/2D Modeling Approach	27
3.3 Data basis for numerical hydrodynamic modeling.....	28
3.3.1 Rainfall data.....	28
3.3.2 Surface property	29

3.3.3	Infiltration	29
3.3.4	Topographic data.....	29
3.3.5	Sewerage network.....	31
3.3.6	Drainage divide.....	31
3.4	Numerical schemes	31
3.4.1	Method of characteristics (MoC)	32
3.4.2	Finite difference method (FDM).....	32
3.4.3	Finite element method (FEM).....	32
3.4.4	Finite volume method (FVM)	33
3.5	Micro-scale modeling.....	33
3.6	Numerical hydrodynamic modeling tools.....	33
3.7	Summary of the literature review	35
4	Model and system selection.....	37
4.1	SWMM.....	37
4.2	LISFLOOD-FP	37
4.3	Used hardware system.....	38
5	Hazard assessment of a selected watershed in Gelsenkirchen.....	39
5.1	Investigation area	39
5.2	Data sources for modeling.....	40
5.3	HN-modeling using SWMM	41
5.3.1	Topographic data.....	41
5.3.2	Subcatchment.....	43
5.3.3	Infiltration	48
5.3.4	Sewerage system	50
5.3.5	Rainfall data.....	52
5.3.6	Surface water modeling.....	53
5.3.7	Model calibration	54
5.4	HN-modeling using LISFLOOD-FP	56
5.4.1	Topographic data.....	56
5.4.2	Roughness coefficient	56
5.4.3	Infiltration	57
5.4.4	Rainfall data.....	57
5.4.5	Surface water modeling.....	57
5.4.6	Model calibration	59
6	Results.....	64
6.1	SWMM.....	64
6.2	LISFLOOD-FP	69
6.3	Focused analysis.....	71
6.3.1	SWMM.....	71
6.3.2	LISFLOOD-FP	72
6.3.3	Downsizing	73

6.3.3.1	SWMM.....	73
6.3.3.2	LISFLOOD-FP.....	75
7	Discussion and conclusion.....	77
8	References	81
9	Appendix	90
9.1	Appendix A: SVEs based models.....	90
9.2	Appendix B: floodplain n-values	91
9.3	Appendix C: Thiessen polygon method.....	92
9.4	Appendix D: units of measurement	93
9.5	Appendix E: Parameters values	94
9.6	Appendix F: LISFLOOD-FP model inputs	97
9.7	Appendix G: SWMM5 results	98
9.8	Appendix H: comparing the downsized model with the original model	100

List of tables

- Table 1: stages of heavy rain warning outlined by DWD [14] 4
- Table 2: new categories of the site-specific heavy rain index from 1 to 12 as a function of the return period and under consideration of precise increase factors [9]..... 5
- Table 3: significant types of floods [20] 5
- Table 4: examples of design flooding criteria for sewerage systems for stagnant water resulted from flooding [18], [19]..... 8
- Table 5: classification of pluvial flood protection and heavy rain risk management adapted from “LUBW” [3] (figure 8) and “DWA” [33] (figure 9) [31]..... 10
- Table 6: common methods for flood modeling [1], [61], [64]..... 35
- Table 7: most well-known urban flood modelers [2]..... 36
- Table 8: data providers overview 41
- Table 9: depression storage depths and roughness coefficient for overland flow [83] 48
- Table 10: sensitivity of runoff volume and peak flow to surface runoff parameters [83] 48
- Table 11: storage curve for the artificial pond created in QGIS 50
- Table 12: routing time step effect on the results 53
- Table 13: header lines of the watershed DEM files..... 56
- Table 14: Solvers available for calculating floodplain flow [97]..... 58
- Table 15: computation time for the first set of the calibration simulations 60
- Table 16: subcatchments with the highest predicted runoff value 66
- Table 17: SWMM report of the flooded nodes (Figure 49)..... 67
- Table 18: terms of the SVEs [22], [123] 90
- Table 19: typical floodplain n-values[124] 91
- Table 20: units used in the current SWMM5 model [83] 93
- Table 21: units used in the current LISFLOOD-FP model [97] 93
- Table 22: subcatchments parameters and their values 94
- Table 23: junctions parameters and their values 95
- Table 24: conduits parameters and their values 96
- Table 25: results predicted by the SWMM5 for the subcatchments..... 98
- Table 26: results predicted by the SWMM5 for the junctions..... 99
- Table 27: comparing the SWMM5 results for original and downsized models 100

List of figures

Figure 1: schematic sketch for pluvial flood risk communication [9]	5
Figure 2: flow-types: (a) free-surface flow or open-channel flow, (b) pressurized flow or pipe flow, (c) combined free-surface and pressurized flow [24].....	6
Figure 3: typical storm sewer system (own illustration) [26].....	7
Figure 4: cases of flow exchange between the surface and sewer system through drainage inlets and maintenance holes: (a) free inflow and free flow in conduits, (b) submerged inflow and free flow in conduits, (c) submerged inflow and pressurized flow in the conduit, (d) overflow [23].....	7
Figure 5: a schematic overview of the process of heavy rain risk management (own illustration) [3] ..	10
Figure 6: workflow risk assessment (own illustration) [31].....	12
Figure 7: summary of different types of models [38].....	14
Figure 8: main components of NH-modeling (own illustration) [40], [41], [42]	15
Figure 9: the Preissmann slot [57].....	19
Figure 10: 1D models for sewerage system: (a) illustration of the 1D modeling approach showing the virtual reservoir (in broken outline) [61], (b) an example of overflow locating (red spots) in a 1D model [62].....	19
Figure 11: common mesh types: (a) unstructured grids of triangular cells, (b) mixed-meshes of triangular and quadrilateral cells, (c) quadtree, (d) Cartesian grids [40]	23
Figure 12: 2D models for the urbanized areas: (a) illustration of the 2D surface-flow flood modeling approach [61], (b) example of a 2D runoff simulation [62]	24
Figure 13: interaction of the major system and the minor system (“dual drainage concept”) [78].....	26
Figure 14: 1D/1D models for the urbanized areas: (a) illustration of a 1D/1D model simulating flows over the street network and through the underground drainage system [61], (b) example of flood map from a 1D/1D model [60].....	27
Figure 15: 1D/2D models for the urbanized areas: (a) illustration of a 1D/2D modeling approach [61], (b) example of flood map generated by a 1D/2D model [60].....	27
Figure 16: DSM and DTM difference : (a) digital elevation model, (b) digital surface model.....	30
Figure 17: the location of the study area (a), IKT-institute for underground infrastructure (b) [99].....	39
Figure 18: official flood map of the study watershed provided by the city of Gelsenkirchen [101]	40
Figure 19: study region displayed on Google Maps [102].....	40
Figure 20: general workflow of stream and watershed delineation with GIS (own illustration) [104]....	41
Figure 21: digital land models of the selected watershed (a) DSM, (b) DEM	42
Figure 22: final surface model (height-corrected DEM)	43
Figure 23: SWMM surface representation concept: (a) idealized representation of a subcatchment, (b) idealized subcatchment partitioning for overland flow [83].....	44
Figure 24: watershed division preparation process: (a) watershed divided according to the DEM, (b) flow direction map calculated for a one-meter DEM, (c) a sample of flow direction map calculated for a corrected five-centimeter DSM, (d) watershed divided according to the Thiessen polygon method	45

Figure 25: the result of the manual watershed division	45
Figure 26: (a) oriented minimum bounding box generated for each subcatchment, (b) one-meter interval contour lines	46
Figure 27: watershed land use map	47
Figure 28: georeferenced soil map of the NRW in the area of IKT-watershed	49
Figure 29: examples of important data gained through site surveying: (a) uncovering maintenance hole hidden under bushes, (b) maintenance hole shown on the map not connected to the drainage system, (c) water at the junction on a dry day, (d) the diameter and direction of the pipe and the water existence indicating that the junction is connected to the artificial pond in the watershed.....	51
Figure 30: watershed drainage system model	52
Figure 31: one-hour Euler Type II model precipitation for a 100-year heavy rain event (own illustration)	53
Figure 32: the final watershed map created in SWMM5 showing the elements used for the simulations	54
Figure 33: simulation run layout of the SWMM5	54
Figure 34: Manning's n values: (a) roughness coefficient automatic generated by QGIS, (b) roughness coefficient based on SWMM model of the watershed	57
Figure 35: simulation run layout of the LISFLOOD-FP	58
Figure 36: the process of data validation and model calibration	59
Figure 37: predicted flood extent and depth after the rain event: (a) reference flood map [101], (b) simulation result of using acceleration solver, and the DEM-base auto-generated roughness coefficient values	60
Figure 38: predicted flood extent and depth after the rain event: (a) flood map on the surface model which was used for the simulation, (b) existing water in the artificial pond.....	60
Figure 39: predicted flood extent and depth after the rain event: (a) reference flood map [101], (b) simulation result of using Roe solver, and the DEM-base auto-generated roughness coefficient values	61
Figure 40: predicted flood extent and depth after the rain event: (a) reference flood map [98], (b) simulation result of using acceleration solver, and the roughness coefficient values used in the SWMM model.....	61
Figure 41: predicted flood extent and depth after the rain event: (a) reference flood map [98], (b) simulation result of using Roe solver, and the roughness coefficient values used in the SWMM model	61
Figure 42: predicted flood extent and depth after the rain event: (a) reference flood map [98], (b) simulation result of using acceleration solver, and the DEM-base auto-generated roughness coefficient values on the height corrected digital elevation model	62
Figure 43: significant differences between the reference map and the map generated by the LISFLOOD-FP: (a) the area for which the DEM data was incorrect, (b) the front view of the structure in the pond	63
Figure 44: calculation results of the one-hour precipitation.....	64
Figure 45: calculation results after the simulation ends	65
Figure 46: subcatchment-62 hydrograph with respect to the rain intensity.....	65

Figure 47: subcatchment-16 and subcatchment-45 hydrograph with respect to the rain intensity.....	66
Figure 48: water elevation profile from junction-5 to the outfall.....	67
Figure 49: calculation results 24 minutes after the precipitation starts	68
Figure 50: maximum water velocities for a 100-year rain event.....	69
Figure 51: aspects of the predicted maximum water depth: (a) maximum water depth predicted by the model for each pixel throughout the simulation, (b) the time of maximum inundation depth in each pixel	69
Figure 52: flood hazard map of IKT-watershed for a 100-year rain event with a duration of one hour generated by LISFLOOD-FP	70
Figure 53: the selected part of the watershed for a focused analysis.....	71
Figure 54: simulation results for subcatchment-45	71
Figure 55: different conditions of the predicted most critical area: (a) close up of the area selected for separate analysis, (b) HN-modeling result while observing the selected area alone, (c) HN-modeling result while observing the selected area as a part of the watershed	72
Figure 56: (a) raster histogram of water depths predicted by and isolated simulation of the area, (b) raster histogram of water depths predicted by and simulation of the area as part of the watershed....	73
Figure 57: the total runoff amount predicted by the original model compared to the total runoff amount predicted by the downsized model	74
Figure 58: additional flooded nodes	75
Figure 59: the difference between the size of the original watershed and the downsized watershed ..	75
Figure 60: comparison of the downsized model with the original model: (a) flood hazard map of the downsized watershed for a 100-year rain event with a duration of one hour generated by LISFLOOD-FP, (b) flood hazard map of the original watershed for a 100-year rain event with a duration of one hour generated by LISFLOOD-FP	76
Figure 61: downsizing the model without increasing the dem resolution: (a) DEM of the downsized watershed with a resolution of one meter, (b) predicted hazard map for the downsized watershed with the DEM resolution of one meter.....	76
Figure 62: Thiessen polygon construction procedures [127]	92

List of equations

- Equation 1: Navier-Stokes momentum equations [1], [46]..... 16
- Equation 2: continuity equation [1], [46] 16
- Equation 3: momentum equation (1D) [52] 17
- Equation 4: continuity equation (1D) [52] 18
- Equation 5: frictional slope [43] 18
- Equation 6: basic weir equation for flow over a weir [43] 21
- Equation 7: simplified momentum equation [68] 21
- Equation 8: continuity equation using discharge between cells [66]..... 22
- Equation 9: the flow between the floodplain cells [43] 22
- Equation 10: momentum equations (2D) [22]..... 23
- Equation 11: continuity equation (2D) [22] 23
- Equation 12: frictional slopes on the x and y directions [43] 24
- Equation 13: subcatchment area calculation based on DEM data [110] 46
- Equation 14: subcatchment width calculation [110] 46
- Equation 15: Horton infiltration capacity over time [83]..... 49
- Equation 16: floodplain n-values (modified channel method) [73] 91

List of abbreviations

0D	Zero-dimensional
1D	One-dimensional
1D/1D.....	Coupled model sewer(1D)/ surface(1D)
1D/2D.....	Coupled model sewer(1D)/ surface(2D)
1D/3D.....	Coupled model sewer(1D)/ surface(3D)
2D	Two-dimensional
3D	Three-dimensional
DEM.....	Digital Elevation Model
DSM.....	Digital Surface Model
DTM.....	Digital Terrain Model
DWD	Der Deutsche Wetterdienst
DWMwl	Diffusive Wave Model with Inertia
DWMwol	Diffusive Wave Model without Inertia
FDM.....	Finite difference method
FEM.....	Finite element method
FVM.....	Finite volume method
GIS.....	Geographical Information System
GWM Gravity Wave.....	Model
h.....	Hour
ha.....	Hectare
HGL	Hydraulic Grade Line
KWM.....	Kinematic Wave Model
LFP	LISFLOOD-FP
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LPS	Liters Per Second
m.....	Meter
Max.....	Maximum
min.....	Minute
Min.....	Minimum
mm.....	Millimeter
MoC	Method of characteristics
NH.....	Numerical Hydrodynamic
Norm.....	Normal
NRCS.....	Natural Resources Conservation Service
NRW	North Rhine-Westphalia

RANS.....Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes
RSI.....Rainstorm Severity Index
SISystème Internationale (The International System of Units)
SVEs.....Saint-Venant Equations
SWEs.....Shallow Water Equations

1 Introduction

1.1 Problem statement

In recent years, the number of flood events has been increased. This growing number of floods, especially in urban environments that result from changes in global climate, has so far caused many human and financial losses around the world. In urban areas, flooding is characterized by high intensity alongside with short response time that can lead to massive losses. Consequently, it has become a growing concern of hydrologists, and further researches are much needed. The complex urban infrastructures and the sewerage systems make the understanding of the flow dynamics throughout the urbanized areas challenging. The hazard and risk analysis represent an essential planning basis for effective damage reduction. Experts have been employing several means and methodologies to study urban flood hazards, from which numerical hydrodynamic modeling has shown to deliver promising and effective results to deal with the issue. Commercial models are usually used for this purpose. Although these models can offer useful results, their widespread is hindered because of being non-open for users. It is especially a major issue for engineers and researchers without access to commercial products. Heretofore, researchers have made few attempts to bring alternative options for commercial modules, such as creating their own model [3], [4]

Modeling heavy rain events and their resultant flood hazard maps without determining the vulnerability of structures at risk and generating flood risk maps consequently and the ability to evaluate the effectiveness of planned flood precautionary measures are incomplete. Micro-scale models can be applied to assess the cost-effectiveness of specific prevention measures on a single structure, for example [5].

1.2 Purpose

In this thesis, the model building process and result quality of the most known non-commercial numerical hydrodynamic models, namely SWMM5 and LISFLOOD-FP, will be investigated. This study's second objective is to evaluate the capability of these models to conduct flood hazard analysis at a micro-scale.

For this purpose, a single watershed in Gelsenkirchen, which consists of both urbanized and non-urbanized areas, will be modeled in order to assess the quality of freeware products at meso-scale modeling and micro-scale modeling. Among others, the questions will be addressed:

1. Are the results created by these products rational?
2. Are the input parameters of these products adjustable to achieve realistic results?
3. Are these user-friendly?
4. Are these products time-consuming in terms of pre-processing, computational, and post-processing time?
5. Are these products suitable for micro-scale modeling?
6. Are the freeware products suitable for the new IKT- project, building an experimental facility to perform heavy rain tests at a scale of 1:1?

1.3 Approach

After the introduction, the second section briefly discusses the basic concepts of heavy rain risk management and related terms. The third section contains detailed information on the numerical hydrodynamic modeling methods and tools. This section deals with different aspects of numerical hydrodynamic modeling, such as definitions, applied equations, methods, data basis, numerical schemes, and tools. This section ends with a summary of the most important information presented in tabular form. In the fourth section, the models used in this thesis will be introduced, and the reason for selecting them will be briefly explained. In the main part of the work, the fifth section, information gathering, data processing, and model execution, will be discussed. The sixth section is a report of the gained results from the built models. In addition to explaining the results, this report includes multiple maps and several diagrams. Since detailed comparative data were not available, the official map was taken as a reference and the logic of the results was validated. Finally, in section number seven, the questions raised at the beginning of the work are answered in detail according to the simulation results.

2 Basics and definitions of heavy rain risk management

2.1 Heavy rain

Heavy² rain and pluvial flood are two inseparable terms, given that pluvial flooding is “surface water flooding resulting from intense rainfall” [6].

To prevent or mitigate pluvial flooding and its potential damages in areas at high risk of heavy rain, understanding the concept of heavy rain is necessary. Commonly three different methods are applied to describe heavy rain [7]:

1. Relative thresholds: a rain event whose precipitation depth is above a specific percentile of all the recorded precipitation depths of the same duration over a reference period counts as a heavy rain event [7]
2. Absolute thresholds: a rain event whose intensity exceeds a fixed threshold counts as a heavy rain event, where intensity is defined as the rainfall depth per unit of time [8]
3. Return value: a rain event of a determined return period counts as a heavy rain event [7]

Furthermore, it is essential to know three main parameters that are frequently used for characterizing rain events [9]:

1. Rain duration: time interval between the beginning and end of precipitation, including interruptions in precipitation [10], which is expressed in particular duration steps [9]
2. Return period: the average length of time between rain events of the same magnitude is the return period [11]
3. Rainfall depth: liquid precipitation depth on a horizontal surface during an observation period in the absence of drainage, evaporation, and percolation where 1 mm equals precipitation of 1 l/m² [12]

Although there is no single definition of heavy rain, a general view of it is explained in the “Arbeitshilfe kommunales Starkregenisikomanagement” [10] guideline. According to the guideline, a heavy rain event is a rare rainfall event, including a large amount of precipitation and high intensity, causing a flood risk that is hard to calculate. The resulting precipitation typically has a short duration and is locally restricted. A similar explanation is also presented by DIN 4049 [13], adding that heavy rains occur on average a maximum of twice a year.

On the other hand, the “Deutscher Wetterdienst”³ (DWD) [14] and “Kommunales Starkregenisikomanagement in Baden-Württemberg” [3] guideline define heavy rain events more specifically; in addition to a general definition of heavy rain, DWD uses three intensity levels (Table 1) to warn about a heavy rain event [14].

“Kommunales Starkregenisikomanagement in Baden-Württemberg” [3] guideline uses the same approach to describe heavy rain with a simple criterion; once the precipitation exceeds 5 mm in 5 minutes or 20 mm in an hour, the precipitated region is facing a heavy rain event.

It is also worth mentioning that for analyzing the heavy rain frequency in the “Emscher-Lippe”

² The terminology for heavy rain risk management is not unique; “storm,” “heavy,” and “extreme” are commonly used in scientific works as an adjective to describe rainfall (precipitation) events. In various cases, they have the same notion and could replace each other. In a few sources, there was a slight difference between those three, yet they would still be overlapping. The German term “Starkregen” covers all contents. Respecting the comfort of the readers, I will be using the phrase “heavy rain” throughout this work.

³ The German weather service

area, the intensity of 20 mm precipitation per day has been selected. As claimed by the author of this study, this threshold is a typical value to distinguish a heavy rain event as it has also been used in ExUS-Study⁴ and other scientific works [15].

Table 1: stages of heavy rain warning outlined by DWD [14]

Warning	Threshold Value	Stage
Heavy rain	15 to 25 l/m ² in 1 hour 20 to 35 l/m ² in 6 hours	2
Severe rain	25-40 l/m ² in 1 hour 35-60 l/m ² in 6 hours	3
Extremely severe rain	> 40 l/m ² in 1 hour > 60 l/m ² in 6 hours	4

Heavy rain is a relative term; as the climate varies from place to place, the definition and threshold of heavy rain vary with it; therefore, it is challenging to achieve a single standard to characterize heavy rain. Compared to all methods, the return period method is the most used in the field of engineering [7]. DWA-M 119 guideline [16] also uses return values to classify heavy rain events into four classes:

1. Heavy rain: rain events with a return period of a year or more for a given duration and intensity
2. Design rain: rain events for which the sewerage system⁵ is designed, i.e., its return period meets the requirements of the German standard DWA-A 118 for hydraulic design
3. Rare heavy rainfall: rain events with a return period above the crucial return period for overflow but within the crucial return period for inundation
4. Extraordinary heavy rain: rain events with a return period above the crucial return period for inundation

It has become even more evident in previous years that most of the current sewerage systems cannot convey and store instantaneous surface runoff during heavy rain events. Considering that as a result of climate change, an increase in the number of severe events, particularly heavy rainfalls, is possible, the awareness of responsible political decision-makers and the public is of great importance. As citizens are directly touched by urban flooding, either as residents or owners of flooded properties, communication of flood risks is the fundamental element of urban flood risk management. Private house owners are responsible for reducing or limiting the potential harm of flooding, which must be communicated [18]. The starting point for communicating flood risks is having an image of the heavy rain, which is understandable for all target groups. The argumentation with statistical return periods does not seem suitable for communication with the general public [16]. In order to achieve an easy to explain heavy rain description, Schmitt has developed a unique, non-dimensional rainstorm severity index (RSI). This approach adds a new category, including five more levels to the existing categorization of his. This category covers rain events with a return period of more than a hundred and, in contrast to the first seven indices, is site-independent and is carried out using

⁴ Extremwertstatistische Untersuchung von Starkniederschläegen in NRW

⁵ There are three main types of modern sewerage systems: sanitary sewers (for wastewater from industrial and domestic sewers), storm sewers (also called surface sewers), and a combined system where a single network collects both storm runoff water and wastewater [17]. In the framework of the current study, the "sewerage system" mostly refers to storm sewers; if necessary, the type will be defined.

increase- coefficients obtained from the analysis of heavy rainfall depths (Table 2) [9].

Table 2: new categories of the site-specific heavy rain index from 1 to 12 as a function of the return period and under consideration of precise increase factors [9]

Return Period [a]	1	2	3.3	5	10	20	25	33.3	50	100	> 100				
Category	Design Heavy rain				Intense Heavy rain				Extraordinary Heavy rain		Extremely Heavy rain				
RSI [-]	1	1	2	2	3	4	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Increase-coefficient [-]										1.00	1.20	1.40	1.60	2.20	≥ 2.80
											-	-	-	-	
											1.39	1.59	2.19	2.79	

DWD uses the same classification for pluvial flood risk communication with the public, using a more visually enlightening yet very similar structure (Figure 1). The assignment of rainfall depths to severity index values is carried out using site-specific heavy rain statistics [18].

Figure 1: schematic sketch for pluvial flood risk communication [9]

This method proves to be a plausible and reliable approach that could be applied to both urban water management and classical hydrology; it is strongly recommended as a tool for communicating to those involved (residents, municipal decision-makers, and planners) [9].

2.2 Types of floods

Based on the German edition of the European Standard, DIN EN 752 [19], flooding is when wastewater or surface water flows unintentionally on the surface or enters into buildings. Urban floods generally happen as a combination of meteorological and hydrological extremes, such as extreme rain events and flows. To begin with heavy rain risk assessment, one must have a general understanding of types of flooding and their causes. Two useful methods to characterize floods are either based on a combination of sources, causes, impacts, or the speed of onset of flooding (Table 3) [20].

Table 3: significant types of floods [20]

Characterizing by causes	Characterizing by onset time
River (or fluvial) floods	Flash floods
Pluvial (or overland) floods	Urban floods ⁶
Coastal floods	Semi-permanent floods
Groundwater floods	Slow rise floods
Failure of artificial water systems	-

Within the scope of the present work, pluvial floods (Section 2.2.1) and flash floods (Section

⁶ Flash floods, coastal floods, or river floods can provoke flooding in urban areas, but urban flooding as an individual type happens due to a lack of drainage in an urban area [21].

2.2.2) are of great importance, since by definition, both happen mostly due to heavy precipitation.

Other useful pieces of information to understand pluvial flooding, especially in terms of numerical hydrodynamic modeling (Section 3.1), are flow-types, flow-stages, and flow-exchange cases between the surface and sewerage system, which could be recognized during a flood event. Three main flow-types and two flow-stages can arise when floods happen; likewise, the flow-exchanges can be classified into four categories [22], [23].

Flow-types can be categorized as follows:

1. Free-surface flow: the flow in an open-channel⁷ or a closed conduit having a free surface is classified as “free-surface flow” or “open-channel flow,” where the water flow is primarily driven by gravity while the surface stays at atmospheric pressure (Figure 2, (a)) [22], [24]
2. Pressurized flow: when the conduit is flowing full, and there is no free surface; the liquid inside becomes pressurized; therefore, the flow is called “pressurized flow” or “pipe flow” (Figure 2, (b)) [22], [24]
3. Combined free-surface and pressurized flow: a hybrid form of flow happens in which both the free-surface and pressurized flow may occur (Figure 2, (c)) [22]

Figure 2: flow-types: (a) free-surface flow or open-channel flow, (b) pressurized flow or pipe flow, (c) combined free-surface and pressurized flow [24]

Flow-stages can be categorized as follows:

1. Runoff concentration or conveyance: this stage starts with the time at which runoff is generated up until it enters the sewerage system [23]
2. Sewer flooding or exceedance flow: this stage refers to the point from which floodwater starts flowing from surcharged sewer [23]

In practice, most of the time, both stages happen simultaneously and are tightly related, but during simulations, they are often handled separately [23].

After the end of the precipitation sewerage system continues to drain water and might again have sufficient capacity for collecting surface runoff. The sewerage system’s drainage capacity and its components drainage capacity (Figure 3), infiltration, evaporation, and the topography in the area of interest determine how long the flooding on the surface would last [25].

⁷ “The structures with closed tops are referred to as closed conduits and those with the top open are called open-channels” [24].

Figure 3: typical storm sewer system (own illustration) [26]

Even when the sewerage system has sufficient capacity according to the requirements of the standards, the entire surface runoff may not enter into the sewerage system; the exchange of water between the surface system and the sewerage system depends on the intake capacity of the maintenance holes and the drainage inlets along with the drainage capacity of the conduits (Figure 4) [23].

Flow-exchanges can be categorized as follows:

1. Free inflow and free flow in conduits: drainage inlet behaves as a weir, and both drainage inlet and conduits have enough capacity to accommodate more water (Figure 4, (a)) [23]
2. Submerged inflow and free flow in conduits: the capacity of drainage inlet for free-surface flow has been exceeded, and it begins to work as an orifice; although the capacity of conduits has not been exceeded yet, only a fraction of the water can flow into the conduits, (Figure 4, (b)) [23]
3. Submerged inflow and pressurized flow in the conduit: conduits have gotten full, but the pressure is not yet sufficient to provoke an overflow (the piezometric head is yet below surface water level) (Figure 4, (c)) [23]
4. Overflow: the piezometric head in the sewerage system is higher than the piezometric head of surface water, therefore causing overflow (Figure 4, (d)) [23]

Figure 4: cases of flow exchange between the surface and sewer system through drainage inlets and maintenance holes: (a) free inflow and free flow in conduits, (b) submerged inflow and free flow in conduits, (c) submerged inflow and pressurized flow in the conduit, (d) overflow [23]

2.2.1 Pluvial (overland) floods

Pluvial flood is defined as flooding due to rainfall or snowmelt that usually converts into runoff-flows on the ground. This phenomenon typically happens throughout urban areas before it enters natural or human-made drainage systems or watercourses. Pluvial flooding occurs when rainfall intensity overwhelms the drainage system as well as the capacity of the ground to absorb water [20].

One of the often observed characters of pluvial floods is its “rapid-onset,” which means it can sometimes be described as a flash flood event as well as a pluvial flood event [23].

Although this phenomenon can emerge in both urban and rural regions, it is mainly an issue of urban areas [19]; the current study’s focus is also on urban pluvial flooding.

A serious health hazard can occur when combined systems (stormwater and wastewater) are overwhelmed; when the sewers overflow onto the streets, the resulting flood is a combination of surface-water and untreated sewage. Sufficient hydraulic capacity is necessary to limit sewer flooding to nationally or locally determined frequencies. Drainage systems are designed with specific hydraulic performance to evacuate a certain amount of rainfall-runoff and prevent flooding [6].

For the hydraulic performance of urban drainage systems, the main criterion is their degree of flood protection in order to take care of “health and safety of the population” and “environmental protection” therefore, DIN EN 752 [19] outlines flooding return periods for the designing of the sewerage systems based on the land-use and impacts of the flooding on the selected area.

Table 4 gives an overview of the required flooding return periods for the designing of the sewerage systems.

Table 4: examples of design flooding criteria for sewerage systems for stagnant water resulted from flooding [18], [19]

Impact	Exemplary Locations	Flooding Frequency	
		Return Period [a]	Exceeding Probability Per Year
Very low	Roads or open spaces away from buildings	1	100 %
Low	Agricultural land (depending on land-use)	2	50 %
Low to medium	Open spaces used for public amenity	3	30 %
Medium	Roads or open spaces adjacent to buildings	5	20 %
Medium to high	Flooding in occupied buildings excluding basements	10	10 %
High	Deep flooding in occupied basements or road underpasses	30	3 %
Very high	Critical infrastructure	50	2 %

• The frequency should be increased (probabilities reduced), where the floodwater flows rapidly.

• A lower value may be considered when rehabilitation of existing systems and when achieving the exact design criteria for a new system would lead to high costs.

The flood frequencies presented in the table above should be seen as recommendations, and their primary use is for new planning or upcoming rehabilitation [19].

2.2.2 Flash floods

According to NOAA⁸, a flash flood is defined as a sudden burst of water over an area whose peak usually appears within six hours from the start of a heavy rain event or a dam burst or breakthrough of another barrier. The combination of a flood's destructive power and incredible speed makes flash floods the most dangerous type of floods. Urban areas are at high risk of flash floods. The surface structure in these areas (impervious streets, roofs, and car parking) results in lower absorption of rainfall water by the ground, which causes an increased runoff and, consequently, increases the flash flood potential [27].

2.3 Risk management

The risk of heavy rain is generally a combination of two parameters: hazard potential or occurrence probability and vulnerability or damage potential. A practical and comprehensive heavy rain risk management must include both features [10].

A hazard is a source of a possible adverse effect; in calculating the consequences of a hazard, the assumption is that the affected system is fully exposed, though, in reality, all structures have a certain degree of protection, which could vary from low to high [28], which could be represented by the vulnerability. The vulnerability of an element shows its sensitivity to the impacts of a hazardous phenomenon. Hazard and vulnerability make it possible to have a clear explanation of risk; UNDRR⁹ [29] describes the risk as "The sum of expected losses and damage of any kind due to a particular natural phenomenon, as a function of natural hazard and vulnerability of the element at risk." Lowering the vulnerability of elements at risk and the whole in danger area is the main focus of risk management [30].

2.3.1 Heavy rain risk management

Heavy rain risk management¹⁰ deals with the possible consequences of flooding caused by heavy precipitation in urban areas [10]. Unlike most flood types, a pluvial flood does not necessarily happen near water bodies; therefore, its risk must be managed differently. The flood's statistical return period is not used in pluvial flood risk management, but the simulation would instead be handled by an adapted approach regarding heavy rain events [31].

The severity of a heavy rain event influences the resulting flood and determines the necessary actions to take. In urban heavy rain risk management, the focus is on rare, extraordinary, and extreme surface runoff events caused by heavy rain (Table 5). As the rain intensity increases, the influence of the sewer system on the flooding event decreases, consequently the sewerage system can have a specific effect on the flooding in case of rare surface runoff events, as opposed to extraordinary and extreme surface runoff events, where this effect could be overlooked in order to simplify the calculations; thus, water flows on the surface and forms surface runoff. In heavy rain risk management, rain events with a return period of 30 years or more than 30 years are used to calculate surface runoff [3].

This system helps identify endangered areas, evaluate risks, and develop and implement

⁸ The US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration

⁹ UN. Office of the Disaster Relief Co-Ordinator

¹⁰ In most of the English works, this is referred to as flood risk management or sometimes pluvial flood risk management. Here I used the translated version of the German term "Starkregenrisikomanagement," as this field deals a lot with legal aspects that can vary from country to country.

adequate measures and policies [32].

Table 5¹¹: classification of pluvial flood protection and heavy rain risk management adapted from “LUBW” [3] (figure 8) and “DWA” [33] (figure 9) [31]

Rain Events (Section 2.1)	Return Period [a]	Jurisdiction Level	Protection Aim	Objectives within Jurisdiction Level
Design Rain	1 - 5	Municipal flood protection	Avoidance of overflow	1. Public drainage systems including backflow prevention for objects like buildings
Rare Heavy Rainfall	10 - 30	Overlapping field of authorities	Flood protection	1. Public drainage systems including backflow prevention for objects like buildings 2. Traffic and open areas
Extraordinary Heavy Rain	> 50	Heavy rain risk management	Damage control	1. Public drainage systems including backflow prevention for objects like buildings 2. Traffic and open areas 3. Technical and constructive object-protection for public and private properties

The effort is usually to prevent floodwater from moving towards “high-value” areas and accelerating its conveyance from the urban regions elsewhere; obviously, this will not solve the problem [34].

It is impossible to provide total protection against the negative impacts of flooding arising from heavy rain events; however, by taking proper protective actions, the chance of a hazard’s occurrence and the respective possible damage could be reduced; in order to achieve this, both preventive actions and structural adjustments on the hydraulic performance in an effort to reduce possible damages should be taken, for example, through targeted property protection measures against surface water flooding or usage alterations.. The process of heavy rain risk management in urban areas (Figure 5) takes place in three phases [3]:

1. Hydraulic hazard assessment (hazard maps) (Section 2.3.1.1)
2. Risk assessment (Section 2.3.1.2)
3. Measures for heavy rain risk management (Section 2.3.1.3)

Figure 5: a schematic overview of the process of heavy rain risk management (own illustration) [3]

¹¹ The translation from German to English is not similar to the cited references.

Since the beginning of 2019, the new guideline published by the state of North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW) [10] promotes heavy rain risk management; it also encourages the cities and municipalities to provide flood hazard maps (Section 2.3.1.1) to assess risks of pluvial flooding (Section 2.3.1.2) and to invent measures (Section 2.3.1.3) for reducing the consequences of heavy rain events [35]. Thus far, several cities in this state, including the city of Gelsenkirchen (Section 5.1), have provided public flood hazard maps.

2.3.1.1 Hydraulic Hazard Assessment (Hazard Maps)

An urban heavy rain risk management plan starts with assessing current and potential flood hazards [36].

The hazard assessment includes all efforts and methods that try to find areas at risk of severe flooding caused by heavy rain events. Products of hazard assessments are flood hazard maps. Flood hazard maps are created using numerical¹² hydrodynamic models (NH-models) in order to simulate the rainfall-runoff and its following flow processes. Flood hazard maps illustrate the expected runoff and flooding conditions under various¹³ scenarios (Section 3) [3]. For each scenario, a comprehensive hazard map should provide information about flood magnitudes: extent, depth, and duration; if possible, flow velocity and propagation as well [10].

For planning development activities in an area, understanding the hazard situation is essential. In such situations, flood hazard maps could be used to help make decisions. Moreover, in some regions, the responsible authorities must present flood hazard maps as part of the urban heavy rain risk management [10]. Therefore, in addition to providing information, they should also be easy to read by both professional and non-professional groups [20].

2.3.1.2 Risk Assessment

Flood hazard and flood risk must be distinguished; information such as magnitude or possibility of an event is represented by hazard maps, whereas risk maps represent further details on the consequences. For the evaluation of consequences, the created hazard maps must be analyzed to find out the damage potential (Section 2.3) [10]; in this phase, depth and velocity of water, flood propagation, rate of recurrence, dynamics of the flow are recommended criteria to be analyzed [33].

Critical objects and infrastructure facilities must be localized, for which a vulnerability (Section 2.3) analysis must be carried out. Vulnerability does not only refer to monetary damages; non-monetary damages like ecosystem impairment or threat to human health can be just as valuable; the focus of vulnerability analysis should not just be on areas with a considerable depth of inundation; buildings can have a high level of vulnerability to the small amounts of water [10].

The combination of hazard, probability of occurrence, and vulnerability makes it possible to determine and evaluate the risk; the final phase of risk assessment is the identification and prioritization of the identified, endangered areas (Figure 6) [10] [31].

¹² Most of the English literature refers to it as "hydrodynamic models." In German literature, it is referred to as "numerical hydrodynamic models." Since this work has been carried out in Germany and the phrase "numerical hydrodynamic" is more precise, this phrase is selected for the current study.

¹³ Selected scenarios in the state of North Rhine-Westphalia are rare heavy rain events (optional), extraordinary heavy rain events, and extremely heavy rain events [10].

Figure 6: workflow risk assessment (own illustration) [31]

2.3.1.3 Measures For Heavy Rain Risk Management

The measures to prevent or reduce flooding can be divided into different sorts. The type of flood (Section 2.2) determines the measure that is best suited for the phenomena; though regulations are the primary decision-maker for the selection and implementation of measures; in Germany, the legal situation of pluvial flooding is undecided; however, it can be performed analogously to other types of floods. Preparedness, response, and regeneration are the three steps toward mitigating the risk¹⁴ [31].

The purpose of the preparedness is to reduce the vulnerability of the urbanized environment against flooding. Preparedness includes both precautionary and preventive actions. Actions such as flood control by plodders (to cap flood peaks), restoration of flood plains, flood-adapted land-use (e.g., not to urbanize flood-prone areas), enhancing community engagement together with increasing cooperation of the property owners (e.g., preparedness for response, property level mitigation measures, and flood insurance) and flood risk awareness. These actions demand basic knowledge and awareness of flooding and its consequences; risk communication is the main pillar of flood risk awareness (Section 2.1) [31], [37].

Flood marks setup, public hazard maps, educating residents, alongside precautionary communication, are the key elements of flood risk awareness [31].

The purpose of the response is to alleviate flood duration and extent after it begins. Aside from flash floods, other types of floods can be forecasted hours or sometimes days beforehand; the time between forecasting a flood and its peak can be used for executing emergency measures to reduce the damages; measures like the evacuation of endangered spots or management of retention areas. Providing support service for those affected by flood and documenting the flood characteristics and consequences to get ready for the regeneration phase also belong to the response phase [31], [37].

The purpose of the regeneration is to reconstruct and rehabilitate. In case flood loss cannot be prevented, distributing the financial burden improves the recovery process; for example, in Germany, flood insurance is available for the commercial sector as well as for the private property owners. A comprehensive evaluation and analysis of the flood event is a part of this phase; this is for being better prepared for the first phase and improve the measures taken [31], [37].

¹⁴ There are other types of classifications, besides what has been briefly mentioned here. Different types of classification, and more details on measures, and more examples of it can be found in: "Dezentrale Maßnahmen zur Hochwasserminderung," "Risikomanagement in der kommunalen Überflutungsvorsorge für Entwässerungssysteme bei Starkregen," "Starkregen und urbane Sturzfluten."

One of the factors that should be considered in the whole process is the duration of flooding. In the course of flooding, areas in danger of deep, persistent inundation should receive rescue actions at first [10].

3 Numerical hydrodynamic modeling methods and tools

3.1 Numerical hydrodynamic modeling

The purpose of models is to represent aspects of reality. The term “models” mostly stands for mathematical models that run on computers, although different types of models (Figure 8) can be distinguished. Two main groups of models are physical models (models you can touch) and abstract models (models you cannot touch) [38].

Scale models and analog models are the subgroups of physical models. A scale model is the physical representation of an object constructed at a usually reduced scale. An analog model is a representation of a phenomenon based on analogies between different physical systems. Subgroups of abstract models are conceptual models, for instance, word models and graphical representations, and mathematical models that rely on mathematical formulas or equations. Mathematical models can be divided into empirical models and physics-based models; empirical models are data-oriented [38].

The general laws of physics govern physics-based models, which leads to either analytical models or numerical models. In analytical models, the mathematical equations are simplified in order to get solved. Another technique for solving complicated mathematical equations is translating them in a way that makes them solvable by a computer; this technique leads to numerical models [38].

Figure 7: summary of different types of models [38]

Numerical models, as opposed to experimental techniques, are optional. In reality, these two tools cannot replace each other, but instead, they complete each other. Experimental evidence is needed to confirm the results of numerical modeling. Numerical modeling is a popular choice, not only because of economic motivations but also due to the amount of provided information by such models [39].

In heavy rain risk management, in order to predict and mitigate flooding consequences, numerical models are used to simulate floods at lower costs than physical scale models; they also do not involve substantial physical systems and data extraction instrumentation [2].

Numerical models that are based on fundamental equations of hydrodynamics are called “numerical hydrodynamic models” (NH-models); the goal of NH-models is to simulate flood propagation and inundation processes as accurately as possible (or required) in the model, under consideration of the main physical properties. Theoretically, through a complete solution of the mentioned equations, it is possible to describe flow processes within the modeling area accurately, however in practical application, that is impossible; consequently, numerical approximation approaches are applied instead of analytical ones, which lead to a sufficiently accurate approximate solution. Numerical approaches help calculate flow processes, mainly flow velocities and water level, as a function of discrete natural topographical and hydrological data as well as flow resistances and flow losses; this calculation leads to visualization and evaluation of the flows within the domain (Figure 8) [40].

Figure 8: main components of NH-modeling (own illustration) [40], [41], [42]

3.2 Numerical hydrodynamic modeling methods

A simple way to classify NH-models is based on the dimensionality of the represented processes [1]. NH-Modeling methods can be categorized as zero-dimensional “0D” (Section 3.2.1), one dimensional “1D” (Section 3.2.2 to 3.2.3), two-dimensional “2D” (Section 3.2.4 to 3.2.6), three-dimensional “3D” (Section 3.2.7), and combinations of them (Section 3.2.8) [43]. Except for 0D models that are not based on physical laws, other NH-models are adopted from three-dimensional Navier-Stokes momentum equations¹⁵ under the assumption of a constant density for an incompressible¹⁶ fluid (Equation 1) [45].

¹⁵ Also known as the dynamic equations [44].
¹⁶ The mass density of the liquid does not change [24].

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \right) = \rho B_x - \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} \right)$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} \right) = \rho B_y - \frac{\partial P}{\partial y} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial z^2} \right)$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} + w \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \right) = \rho B_z - \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial z^2} \right)$$

Where:

ρ fluid density
 (u, v, w) velocity components
 (x, y, z) coordinates
 t time
 p pressure
 μ viscosity
 B_x, B_y, B_z Body force components (e.g., gravity)

Equation 1: Navier-Stokes momentum equations [1], [46]

The Navier-Stokes equations, combined with the equation of continuity (Equation 2), provides a system of equations that can completely (in three-dimensions) describe the various motion characteristics of incompressible fluid flow [45].

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} = 0$$

Where:

t time
 (u, v, w) velocity components
 (x, y, z) coordinates

Equation 2: continuity equation¹⁷ [1], [46]

The momentum equations refer to the conservation of momentum and the continuity equations to the conservation of mass [44]. Overall, these equations are analytically unsolvable; hence, there are different numerical approaches (Section 3.4) to model flow properties based on the Navier-Stokes equations. The outcome of using the Reynolds-averaged approach to achieve an approximation of the Navier-Stokes equations is a set of partial differential equations named Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations¹⁸ (RANS). Typically, engineers employ the RANS equations for computing motion features of flows [47], [48].

3.2.1 The 0D modeling approach

The 0D flood modeling method uses the least complicated rules among the various flood modeling methods [43]. 0D models are used primarily when a rapid assessment of inundation depth and extent is needed, where a lesser level of details is satisfactory in the description of spatial distributions, or there is no better option available. This method relies on digital terrain models (DTM) plus simplified hydraulic assumptions and applies non-physics-based methods [49]. This method could be fitting in cases with distinct flow pathways across the floodplain or for large study areas and regions with inadequate data. However, this approach for sites with complex topography or significant flow momentum conservation is not accurate enough since

¹⁷ A more complete version of the equation can be written as " $\partial p / \partial t + (\partial(\rho u)) / \partial x + (\partial(\rho v)) / \partial y + (\partial(\rho w)) / \partial z = 0$ " however considering the assumption of incompressible fluid in flood modeling, the derivative of p with respect to time is zero consequently the result can be written as equation 2 [1].

¹⁸ Detailed information about this topic can be found in the reference number [47] and the the reference number [48].

dynamic effects such as velocity or variations in flow are neither taken into account in computing nor estimated [50]. Geographical information system (GIS) software products are used for this method [43].

Considering that the 0D modeling approach is too simple for the generation of a detailed flood hazard map [44], this approach will not be further discussed in the present thesis.

3.2.2 The 1D modeling approach

1D models are used to describe numerous hydraulic situations. This category of NH-models is mostly employed when a highly “detailed resolution” is not required, or there is a “dominant flow direction” [39], [2]. This approach is also a suitable choice for rapid analyzes such as “real-time application,” “emergency operation,” and “early warning” [51].

In urban areas, 1D simulations are used for both sewerage system flow modeling and surface flow modeling. In 1D modeling, the system is represented as a set of links and nodes that are connected [51].

For simulating the sewerage system as a 1D system, links usually are the representation of conduits; however, weirs, orifices, valves, and pumps also count as links, while the nodes of the model represent maintenance holes and street inlets. For the surface network, links represent overland pathways, and nodes represent ponds or channel junctions [23]. The 1D representations of the Saint-Venant equations (SVEs) are regularly used for the 1D modeling of the flow (Equation 3, Equation 4) [52]. One-dimensional Saint-Venant equations (also referred to as the one-dimensional form of the shallow water equations¹⁹ (SWEs)) are simplified versions of the general Navier-Stokes equations (Section 3.2) [53].

The underlying assumptions of the SVEs are [2]:

1. The pressure has a hydrostatic²⁰ distribution
2. The slope of the channel bottom is insignificant
3. The flow is one dimensional, assuming consistent velocity throughout the cross-section
4. Turbulence and friction are assumed to follow the laws of steady-state flow
5. The density of water stays constant

$\frac{1}{A} \frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{A} \frac{\partial(Q^2/A)}{\partial x} + g \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} - g(S_0 - S_f) = 0$	
<i>Where:</i>	
<i>A</i>	<i>flow cross-section area</i>
<i>Q</i>	<i>flow discharge</i>
<i>x</i>	<i>distance</i>
<i>t</i>	<i>time</i>
<i>g</i>	<i>gravitational acceleration</i>
<i>h</i>	<i>hydraulic head of water</i>
<i>S₀</i>	<i>bed slope in the longitudinal direction</i>
<i>S_f</i>	<i>friction slope (Equation 5)</i>

Equation 3: momentum equation (1D) [52]

¹⁹ Shallow water equations are the English name of the Saint-Venant equations in view of the fact that they govern free-surface flows in shallow waters [53].

²⁰ The streamline curvature is minor and vertical accelerations are inconsiderable [2].

$$\frac{\partial A}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial Q}{\partial x} = 0$$

Where:

A	<i>flow cross-section area</i>
Q	<i>flow discharge</i>
x	<i>distance</i>
t	<i>time</i>

Equation 4: continuity equation²¹ (1D) [52]

Friction slope, S_f is defined as:

$$S_f = \frac{4\tau_o}{\rho g D_H}$$

Where:

S_f	<i>friction slope</i>
τ_o	<i>average boundary shear stress</i>
ρ	<i>fluid density</i>
g	<i>gravitational acceleration</i>
D_H	<i>hydraulic diameter</i>

Equation 5: frictional slope [43]

The Saint-Venant equations have been developed to characterize one-dimensional unsteady²² open-channel flows (Section 2.2); these equations are applicable for urban sewerage systems as long as no surcharge happens [23]. In this case, the surface runoff would be modeled using a simple rainfall-runoff transfer function; the surface network and sewerage system interact over the inflow from the surface into the drainage network (Section 3.2.8) [54]. For the simulation of urban flooding, one-dimensional²³ models are vastly used to model the sewerage system; the reason behind this is the direction of the flow in a pipe, which is expected to be along the longitudinal axis (1D assumption) [22].

A free-surface condition in the piping system is provided as long as the water level stays below the pipe crown; otherwise, the pipe flow will become pressurized (Section 2.2). When the water level reaches the pipe's crown, it is feasible to have both types of flows simultaneously in a single pipe and create a "free-surface-pressurized flow" situation [22].

The use of 1D Saint-Venant equations for a pressurized flow is only possible under the application of definite approaches; the Preissmann slot concept is often adopted in such approaches [52]. The purpose is the transition of the pressurized flow in the pipe into a conceptual free-surface flow by attaching a "hypothetical, continuous, narrow slot" (Figure 9) in the soffit of the entire length of pipe; important is that it should not cause a noticeable error in the water volume [55]. The significant disadvantage of this theory is that when the pressure drops down, it enables the water level to drop lower than the pipe's crown without considering the existence of a venting point at the location. However, when the system does not return to a free-surface flow condition after being pressurized (that is the case in the present thesis (Section 2.3.1) and also in the study of Vasconcelos due to heavy precipitation), this

²¹ Some models do include the lateral inflow term (q) and use $(\partial A/\partial t) + (\partial Q/\partial x) = q$ for calculating [43].

²² Meaning that the flow velocity at a given location varies with time; the flow conditions may change in relation to both space and time; the flow conditions in real-life situations such as flood waves are ordinarily unsteady [24].

²³ The depth and velocity of one-dimensional flow in watercourse change only in the longitudinal direction, from which it can be concluded that the velocity is constant and the water surface is horizontal across any section perpendicular to the longitudinal access [23].

disadvantage can be neglected [56].

Figure 9: the Preissmann slot [57]

With the 1D approach for the sewerage system, the overflow is not able to spread through the surface network, and it will be stored as stagnant water in a “virtual reservoir” (Figure 10, (a)) above the maintenance holes. The stored water is allowed to go back to the sewerage system when a free-surface flow in the system starts to go on again [51] [58]. However, solving the issue with a virtual reservoir’s help is used in the first generation of 1D modelers. The second generation of 1D models resolves the surcharged water issue by linking the 1D sewerage system to a 1D model of the surface system so that the surcharged water can propagate on the surface (Section 3.2.8.1) [59].

The overflow water in the virtual reservoir results in an unrealistic behavior of the flood propagation, and it may also result in an exaggeration of the calculated depth of flood, yet the possible spot of the overflow can be located by this method [60].

By using the 1D approach for the sewerage system, the only outcome of the modeling is the floodwater-volume at each node (Figure 10, (b)), other features of flooding stay unclear, such as spatial extent, duration, flood depths, and flow velocities [61].

Figure 10: 1D models for sewerage system: (a) illustration of the 1D modeling approach showing the virtual reservoir (in broken outline) [61], (b) an example of overflow locating (red spots) in a 1D model [62]

It has been proven that the 1D approach performance for modeling sewerage systems is very successful [2].

This method is also used to model the surface flow. For modeling surface networks, 1D models are used to represent streets and watercourses [2]. A 1D model of a surface network makes sense as long as the surface water does not overtop the curbs; otherwise, the flow is not considered one-dimensional anymore, and the simulation results could vary significantly from the observed data; hence this approach may be insufficient for modeling a massive flood event [25]. In this system, the links' characteristics are determined by linear geometry and nodes by storage capacity. With the help of the digital elevation model of the floodplain, the surface network can be extracted either automatically or manually [51].

Ever since the advances in the field have made it possible to carry out 2D simulations of the surface flow, 1D models of the surface are often compared with two-dimensional models. The main advantage of 1D models over 2D models is its notably shorter computing time, making it more suitable for real-time applications; on the other hand, compared to 2D models, the setup of 1D models is more complicated than other methods and also time-intensive. Another disadvantage of 1D models is the weak visual representation of the surface flow; thus, it is not suitable for communication with non-technical [23].

3.2.3 The 1D⁺ modeling approach

Although 1D models are computationally efficient, their flaws could not be ignored; for instance, lateral spreading of the flood cannot be simulated, absence of constant topography treatment, and subjectivity to the cross-section location. The 1D⁺ approaches have been developed to overcome such restrictions without having to deal with complications of 2D and 3D methods [63].

1D⁺ approach handles the main channel as one-dimensional and employs a storage cell concept to present the floodplain in two dimensions; over each cell, water can be stored, assuming that the water has the same level all over the cell (horizontal water-level). A large area, up to several square kilometers, can be covered and modeled by these storage cells [64], [65].

The 1D⁺ approach, in contrast to 1D, is not based on the assumption that the flow is parallel to the main channel; yet, momentum is not conserved for the simulation, i.e., the water can transfer instantaneously from one end of the storage cell to the other end. The result of that is having no information on the velocity of the flood progress and significant errors in the calculation of inner cell flows [43], [64], [65].

This method ordinarily uses 1D Saint-Venant equations (Equation 4, Equation 3) to model in-channel flow and a flood storage cell for 2D modeling of the surface flows [66].

The difference in water levels between the channel and flood storage cell determines water exchange between them. Appropriate weir flow equations should be applied to compute this exchange of water. Equation 6 must be modified depending on the flow conditions for an accurate calculation of the exchanged water next [43]; using conservation of volume, the water level above each storage cell is computed [64].

<p><i>Where:</i></p> <p>Q <i>flow discharge</i></p> <p>C_d <i>coefficient of discharge</i></p> <p>b <i>crest width</i></p> <p>h <i>water head above the weir crest</i></p>	$Q = C_d b h^{3/2}$
---	---------------------

Equation 6: basic weir equation for flow over a weir [43]

Although modified weir equations are used for the computation of exchange flows (between the channel and the cells, or between the cells), they are not always correct; the assumption of horizontal water-level leads to false water-level estimations near the storage cell boundaries, commonly provoking significant errors in the calculation of exchange flows. Nevertheless, these will not be an issue if the filling and draining processes are short compared to the flood duration. Another limitation of the 1D⁺ method is the user-defined size and position of storage cells and links between them; thus, the user needs pre-knowledge of flow pathways in the floodplain [65].

3.2.4 The 2D⁻ modeling approach

The 2D⁻ models, in particular, rely on high-resolution topographic data sets [64] and are capable of generating two-dimensional flow dynamics without solving the complete set of 2D governing equations [67].

Two groups of 2D⁻ can be distinguished [52]:

1. 2D⁻ models which rely on square-grid topographic data and a simplified 1D representation of the flow between the grid cells
2. 2D⁻ models which are based on a simplified form of the 2D shallow water equations (Appendix A), where some terms are neglected

The former method is similar to the 1D⁺ method cause both do not conserve momentum for the 2D simulation, but, in 2D⁻ method, the grid dimensions are considerably smaller than those of a 1D⁺ method [52].

In the 2D⁻ approach, each of the topographic data cells is considered a storage cell. The rate and direction of flow are a function of the topography of the floodplain and the water surface gradient [43]. Such models often²⁴ use the kinematic wave approximation (Equation 4, Equation 7) to simulate flow in the channel. The kinematic wave model simplifies the 1D SVEs (Equation 3) by neglecting convective acceleration, local acceleration, and pressure terms in the momentum equation (Equation 7, Appendix A) [68].

<p><i>Where:</i></p> <p>S_0 <i>channel bed slope</i></p> <p>S_f <i>friction slope</i></p>	$S_0 = S_f$
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Equation 7: simplified momentum equation [68]

²⁴ The equations in section 3.2.4 are taken from a popular 2D⁻ model's code (LISFLOOD-FP); they may vary slightly in other models.

Water depths are calculated by solving a continuity equation (Equation 8) for the fluxes over each cell's four faces during the time step [66].

$$\frac{\partial h^{i,j}}{\partial t} = \frac{Q_x^{i-1,j} - Q_x^{i,j} + Q_y^{i,j-1} - Q_y^{i,j}}{\Delta x \Delta y}$$

Where:

$h^{i,j}$ water-free surface height at the node (i,j)
 t time
 Δx & Δy cell dimensions
 Q_x & Q_y volumetric flow rates between floodplain cells

Equation 8: continuity equation using discharge between cells [66]

A momentum equation can then calculate the flow between cells in the x and y Cartesian directions (Q_y can be calculated analogously) [43]:

$$Q_x^{i,j} = \frac{h_{flow}^{5/3}}{n} \left(\frac{h^{i-1,j} - h^{i,j}}{\Delta x} \right)^{1/2} \Delta y$$

Where:

Q_x volumetric flow rates between floodplain cells
 h_{flow} depth of water available for flow between two neighboring cells²⁵
 n Manning's friction²⁶ coefficient (Appendix B Appendix B)
 $h^{i,j}$ water-free surface height at the node (i,j)
 Δx & Δy cell dimensions

Equation 9: the flow between the floodplain cells [43]

Despite neglecting some terms of the full 2D model, the final results of 2D simulations have proven to be promising; this, along with the low computational cost, makes them a proper choice when only maximum water depths and flood inundation extent are essential. However, 2D models that neglect convective acceleration might predict the hydrodynamic spreading inaccurately; therefore, an application for high momentum flood spreading conditions is not suggested. Generally, these models are not suitable when momentum conservation is essential for the accuracy of the simulation (e.g., dealing with a small obstruction, extremely unsteady flow conditions, supercritical flows, hydrodynamic shocks) [71].

3.2.5 The 2D modeling approach

Two-dimensional flood modelers have been developed to achieve details of the water-flow propagation on a surface by considering the movements of flow in two orthogonal directions [51], which allows a precise determination of flow conditions velocities, flow directions, and flood depths [62].

DEMs make it possible for 2D models to discretize the whole watershed into a continuous hydraulic cell mesh. Unstructured grids of triangular cells (Figure 11, (a)), mixed-meshes of triangular and quadrilateral cells (Figure 11, (b)), quadtree (Figure 11, (c)), and Cartesian grids (Figure 11, (d)) are the possible designs for a mesh. DEM, land-use, and soil type of a watershed are the foundation of the discretization [23], [40],[72].

²⁵ h_{flow} is defined as the elevation difference between the highest water level and ground level of neighboring cells [69].

²⁶ Also known as the Manning's roughness coefficient [70].

Figure 11: common mesh types: (a) unstructured grids of triangular cells, (b) mixed-meshes of triangular and quadrilateral cells, (c) quadtree, (d) Cartesian grids [40]

A point with spatial coordinates (X, Y, Z) represents every grid cell mathematically; within each cell, rainfall inputs and model parameters are consistent; in other words, the size of these cells influences the accuracy of the simulation results as well as the computation time [23].

For a precise simulation of urban areas, a fine grid resolution of the digital elevation model (Section 3.3.4) is needed (typically less than 5 m) to simulate the flows on the surface and around the buildings [25].

2D approaches almost exclusively rely on the two-dimensional SWEs²⁷; these equations can be obtained by integrating the general Navier-Stokes equations (Section 3.2) over the vertical direction [65].

The SWEs are most suitable for flows with a surface extent much larger than their depth and where lateral changes in the velocity field are large [66]. The assumptions of 2D SWEs are similar to those specified in section 3.2.2, excluding the one-dimensional flow assumption (number 3) [24]; based on these assumptions, 2D SWEs can be described as:

$$\frac{\partial hU}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(hU^2 + 0.5gh^2) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(hUV) - gh(S_{0x} - S_{fx}) = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial hV}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(hV^2 + 0.5gh^2) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(hUV) - gh(S_{0y} - S_{fy}) = 0$$

Where:

h flow depth
t time
U, V velocity components respectively on the *x* and *y* directions
x, y space coordinates
g gravitational acceleration
S_{0x}, S_{0y} bed slopes respectively on the *x* and *y* directions
S_{fx}, S_{fy} friction slopes respectively on the *x* and *y* directions

Equation 10: momentum equations (2D) [22]

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial hU}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial hV}{\partial y} = 0$$

Where:

h flow depth
t time
U, V velocity components respectively on the *x* and *y* directions
x, y space coordinates

Equation 11: continuity equation (2D) [22]

²⁷ Also known as 2D SVEs [53].

The friction slopes are defined as:

$$S_{fx} = \frac{n^2 U \sqrt{U^2 + V^2}}{h^{4/3}}$$

$$S_{fy} = \frac{n^2 V \sqrt{U^2 + V^2}}{h^{4/3}}$$

Where:

S_{fx}, S_{fy} friction slopes respectively on the x and y directions
 n Manning's friction coefficient (Appendix B)
 U, V velocity components respectively on the x and y directions
 h flow depth [73]

Equation 12: frictional slopes on the x and y directions [43]

The 2D simulation results are inundation extent (Figure 12 (b)) and the flow dynamics in particular velocities and depths. In this method, the sewerage system is not taken into account (Figure 12 (a)); subsequently, in areas where the sewerage system has an impact on the flooding situation, the risk of the flood can be underestimated (neglected discharge from the sewerage system) or overestimated (lack of drainage) [62].

Figure 12: 2D models for the urbanized areas: (a) illustration of the 2D surface-flow flood modeling approach [61], (b) example of a 2D runoff simulation [62]

As already stated, this approach focuses only on the surface flows; consequently, it is more appropriate for areas with no tangible water drainage, or for when the influence of the water drainage is negligible on the flood propagation, or for heavy rain event modeling [3], [51].

3.2.6 The 2D+ modeling approach

The 2D+ models are similar to 2D models, but with a solution for vertical velocities by only applying continuity, meaning that this approach can predict the velocity in all three directions, which makes them a preferred option for modeling when the focus of the simulation is on water quality and sediment transport, where there is a need for a precise estimation of the concentration of transported sediment [44], [64]. On the other hand, the high computational cost is the reason why this approach is rarely used for practical urban flood modeling and is used mainly for coastal modeling applications [52].

3.2.7 The 3D modeling approach

The 3D models are mostly performed exclusively for simulating specific processes such as erosion processes, sediment transport, water quality analysis, experimental laboratory investigations, and validating studies about 3D models. Like 2D+ models, being

computationally expensive is the main reason for the limited application of 3D models. However, they are getting more popular as technology develops [43], [67]. In addition to computational costs, inadequate calibrated data hinders the parameterization and application of 3D models [66]; 3D simulations are rarely the case in modeling urban flood events due to the disadvantages mentioned above [22]. A 3D representation of flow motion requires completely solving the RANS equations (Section 3.2); additionally, further approximations are necessary to manage both horizontal and vertical changes in the domain extent [66].

From another perspective, 3D illustrations of flood inundation can enhance the residents' and decision-makers' contribution to the management of flood risks (Section 2.3.1.2). Since 3D modeling of the flood events is not yet in a stage to be used as a primary tool for producing flood hazard maps, there have been attempts to visualize 2D flood hazard maps obtained from SWEs in three dimensions. Integrating 2D hydraulic simulations with computer graphic science can help improve the visual aspects of 2D models and represent flooding events in 3D environments. Hazard maps provided by this method still belong to the 2D classes of NH-models; nevertheless, for risk communication purposes, they could reveal more information than classic 2D hazard maps representing the water levels and could be a valuable support for flood propagation maps [74].

3.2.8 Dual drainage concept

For creating urban flood hazard maps, the simulation domain is assumed to be a combination of two networks, the "major system" to represent the flow on the street network and the "minor system" for the sewerage network. The major system consists of all the above-ground flow pathways such as street and swales, and the minor system consists of the sewerage system network, including the maintenance holes and the drainage inlet connections; the flow exchange between the sewerage system and the streets happens through maintenance holes or drainage inlets ("network nodes"). For simulating pluvial floods, the major systems are usually modeled by 1D, and 2D techniques, while the minor systems are exclusively modeled in 1D [25], [22].

In the matter of mapping floods under heavy rain events, it is essential to take the flow-exchange between the minor and major systems into consideration. In this situation, rainfall-runoff has already exceeded the capacity of the sewerage system (Section 2.3.1), which leads to water overflowing from the maintenance holes and causes a possible exceedance-flow on the surface to happen. In such cases, the interaction between the two networks should not be neglected (Figure 1). The need for an approach capable of reflecting the interaction between these two components has resulted in the introduction of the dual drainage approach²⁸. The dual drainage approach aims to assess flooding on the major system begun as a result of a heavy rain event [76], [77], [78].

The water can move from the major system to the minor system in a bidirectional manner through model the linkage nodes, which are usually maintenance holes street inlets. With the help of mass and energy conservation equations (Section 3.2), the linkage between the systems can be computed [59].

²⁸ also known as coupled urban flood models [75].

Figure 13: interaction of the major system and the minor system (“dual drainage concept”) [78]

Different types of dual drainage approaches are 1D/1D models (Section 3.2.8.1) and 1D/2D models (Section 3.2.8.2), meaning that the minor system would be modeled in one dimension, and the major system can be modeled in one, two, or three dimensions [22].

These approaches are often divided into two categories, the “tight coupling” method and the “loose coupling” method [51]. The coupling of minor and major systems in a tight coupling method is based on similar time steps; In this mode, the interaction between the major and minor system models is integrated, and they are operated as one unit. This process allows real-time interactions between the two systems; plus, governing equations are synchronously solved for nodes, network ends, pipes, and surface flows [51]. A loose coupling model can only perform on specific time steps cause major and minor systems are modeled separately. In this mode, the minor system can be viewed as a pre-process to generate input data to model the major system; therefore, the models can be run individually using two different software packages. This mode is often used for studying large systems with lower accuracy [51].

3.2.8.1 1D/1D Modeling Approach

A 1D/1D simulation of the urban system represents both major and minor systems in a one-dimensional manner (Section 3.2.2). In this approach, the major system is handled as a user-defined network of ponds and open channels linked to the minor system and has a computation time of up to a few hours. The 1D/1D modeling allows locating overflow spots, measuring flow-depth, and calculating one-dimensional velocity with acceptable correctness by accurately defining the surface flow paths (if it can be categorized as channeled-flow). When the water tops the given pathways, a 1D/1D model cannot provide decent flood information. This simulation method is recommended for sewerage system preparation and control, emergency actions, and early warning [51], [60]. The typical results of 1D/1D models are ordinary plots or simple animations; flood inundation maps are either unavailable or unrealistic outputs gained by a linear extrapolation between major system nodes; subsequently, results of 1D/1D models

are not as impressive as their opposing 1D/2D models and are often neglected. Through automatic GIS post-processing, outcomes of 1D/1D simulations can be converted into flood inundation maps. In order to achieve reliable flood pathways in the generated flood inundation maps from the results of 1D/1D models, accurate computation of storage level and the quality of digital elevation models are of great importance [22].

Figure 14: 1D/1D models for the urbanized areas: (a) illustration of a 1D/1D model simulating flows over the street network and through the underground drainage system [61], (b) example of flood map from a 1D/1D model [60]

Developing and Verifying 1D/1D models seem to be both highly data and time-demanding. Additionally, as soon as surface flow overtops the street curbs, it can no longer be considered channeled flow; hence, these modeling approaches cannot present a full city [60].

3.2.8.2 1D/2D Modeling Approach

A 1D/2D simulation of the urban system represents the minor system still as a 1D model while the major system flows are computed using a 2D model (Figure 15, (a)). The 2D surface model allows the simulated flow to spread across the domain by reproducing the surface topography and assigning time-varying precipitation to each surface element, converted to effective precipitation after loss calculation for the element. In this approach, the runoff is calculated and generated via the sewerage system together with the surface model [60].

The 1D sewerage system model connected to the surface model behaves as a transport and storage unit. Through the system nodes (maintenance holes, drainage inlets), the bidirectional flow exchange between the minor system and the major system becomes possible. As a result, this kind of model can predict water levels, flow velocities in two-directional components, and overflow volume (Figure 15, (b)). Due to the spatially well-defined approach to generate runoff, this method comes closest to real conditions [62].

Figure 15: 1D/2D models for the urbanized areas: (a) illustration of a 1D/2D modeling approach [61], (b) example of flood map generated by a 1D/2D model [60]

The resulting accuracy depends mostly on the resolution and accuracy of the 2D model and its linking to the 1D model. Grid size for such models is recommended to be between 1 to 5 meters. The required simulation time for such models could be up to days, limiting the 1D/2D real-time simulations [60].

Comparing different flood modeling approaches has shown that the 1D/2D runoff generation method significantly influences the flooding calculation results. Therefore, it is important to adjust the choose the runoff generation approach based on the problem and the available dataset [62].

3.3 Data basis for numerical hydrodynamic modeling

The input data that a model uses for parameterization, calibration, and validation, profoundly influence model quality [79].

Simulation of urban pluvial flooding is more complicated than typical hydrological models in river basins, and so, careful consideration and data collection of both major and minor systems are essential [80].

Pluvial flood modeling consists of two processes [25]:

1. hydrological or statistical model (rainfall-runoff generation), which simulates the surface runoff caused by a heavy rain event and aims to determine flood waves hydrological parameters [25], [81]
2. hydrodynamic or hydraulic model (overland flow modeling), which simulates the flows in the major and minor systems and aims to determine parameters such as inundation level, flood extent, flood depth, and if possible, flood velocity [25], [81]

In the hydrological process, the surface runoff and its hydrographs will be computed for each sub-watershed; the hydrographs are then used as input for the hydrodynamic process. The hydrological process could be performed apart from the hydraulic process; however, studies have shown that separate models might not be valid for heavy rain runoff, considering that the sewerage system's capacity plays a role in runoff interactions [25].

3.3.1 Rainfall data

The duration and intensity of the precipitation is the most crucial input of every model, and its associated uncertainty dominates the general uncertainty of the process. Pluvial floods often happen as a result of rainfalls of a small scale and high intensity; these features make monitoring the magnitude and spatial distribution of such events difficult; besides, the characteristics of urban watersheds (high imperviousness and small dimensions) make them extremely sensitive to the distribution of the precipitation. For the quality of rainfall data, a one-kilometer spatial resolution with a one-minute temporal resolution is recommended; however, a more excellent resolution can be groundbreaking for a detailed sewerage system modeling. Rain gauge and radar are the two most used sensors for precipitation estimation in urban areas [23].

Rainfall-runoff modeling requires estimating the "effective rainfall" since the "total rainfall" does not turn into the runoff for reasons like rainwater soaking into the ground, being caught in tree

leaves, and retaining in a depression. The amount of rainwater loss immediately after the storm starts is called “initial loss,” and the amount of rainwater loss that happens as it flows on the surface is called “continuing loss.” These losses can be calculated as a function of topography, wetness, soil type, and watershed land use. The leading processes involving initial losses are interception, depression storage, and surface wetting, whereas evaporation and infiltration play the central role in continuing losses [23].

3.3.2 Surface property

In the context of NH-modeling, surface roughness, vegetation, and sometimes land-use information is required, particularly for flow resistance quantification. Surface properties are determined through observation and then categorization of the observed data into classes based on the use of the terrain or soil-mechanical characteristics. In the absence of measurement data of adequate quantity or quality, a routine parameter selection can be made using large-scale land-use data and literature values [40].

3.3.3 Infiltration

Infiltration is the process of precipitation penetrating the unsaturated soil surface and filling the pores of the underlying soil layers. In pervious infiltration, losses are often the main part of precipitation losses. Solving the infiltration equation²⁹ involves the relationship between soil permeability and pore water tension as a function of soil moisture content be available. Various algebraic infiltration models have been developed to capture the infiltration capacity dependence on soil characteristics and the previous infiltrated water volume during the course of a heavy rain event. Regardless of the infiltration method, the method parameters are strongly dependent on the soil type and condition of the investigation area [83]

3.3.4 Topographic data

One of the essential inputs of NH-Models is the spatial dataset of the floodplain area. In this context, three terms³⁰ are frequently used in specialized publications, which are [84]:

1. Digital Elevation Model (DEM): is a “bare” earth surface model; it is assumed that DEMs are without any human-made features, vegetation, or any “nonground” items (Figure 16, (a)).
2. Digital Terrain Model (DTM): is a broader term for a DEM. DTMs contain one or more kinds of terrain data, for example, terrain drainage patterns and soil characteristics. Once a DTM deals with just information of the terrain’s height, it also counts as a DEM; in other words, DEMs are a specific kind of DTMs.
3. Digital Surface Model (DSM): is an elevation model that captures the highest point of everything covering human-made features, vegetation as well as bare sections of the ground (Figure 16, (b)).

Figure 16 clearly illustrates the difference between DEM and DSM. Both pictures show the

²⁹ Theoretically, infiltration is governed by the Richards equation [82], which is a highly nonlinear partial differential equation that makes it unfavorable for multipurpose models [83].

³⁰ The differences between these three models are not always explicit, and the definitions are not universal; here, the most commonly used descriptions in the literature are explained [84].

investigation area of this study. Picture (a) is a 3D visualization of the digital elevation model data available on https://www.bezreg-koeln.nrw.de/brk_internet/index.html as a compressed *.xyz text file format [85], where picture (b) demonstrates the digital surface model of the area, likewise in 3D. The required data for DSM visualization are also downloaded from the same source as a compressed *.las format [86]; both pictures are generated via QGIS³¹ [87]. The DSM-photo shows every detail on the surface, even the cars parked on the street, whereas the DEM-photo displays the same area's bare surface.

Figure 16: DSM and DTM difference ³²: (a) digital elevation model, (b) digital surface model

For estimating the flood volume on the surface, DEMs are necessary. The results of the simulation illustrate the water level in relation to the DEM; accordingly, the quality of the DEM affects the quality of the results, so for a reliable result, the following data are a must [25]:

1. Elevation of the base of the roads as well as the curbs
2. Elevation and overall topography of the watersheds
3. Elevation high points and low points

For an accurate representation of the flood-prone area, the resolution of the DEM plays a significant part; for studying the urban area, a horizontal resolution of 1m×1m up to 5m×5m and a vertical resolution of under 0.20 m is advised; this resolution can cover the size of the buildings, streets, and sidewalks. A 5m×5m DEM is more suitable for fast analysis, whereas a 1m×1m DEM is suitable for a detailed assessment. DEMs must be adjusted to get useable for flood simulation. The process of correcting DEMs by raising pixels to involve buildings is known

³¹ More about data, data processing, and software work can be found in section 5.

³² The coloring and classifications here are to magnify the difference between DEM and DSM; they may vary in the main part of the project.

as “height correction of DEM” [25].

DEMs are generally in the form of raster data, points, or line features. Plausibility checks and, if necessary, post-processing of the topographic data such as error detection, interpolation of data gaps, terrain edge definition, and data density optimization, are indispensable and time-consuming parts of the model creation. Regularly several datasets must be combined to cover all relevant geometries [40].

3.3.5 Sewerage network

In the case of a sewerage system or surface/sewerage system modeling, sewer-specific data are essential. The fundamental elements for creating the drainage network model are details about maintenance holes and drainage inlets such as invert elevation, depth, nominal diameters, dimensions, and coordinates of their location. Furthermore, detail of conduits, including shape, slope, inlet plus outlet offset, length, and existing flows, are needed. If any special structures are in the system, their information should be available as well. Finally, each sewerage system’s terminal point with details is required as they play a key role in modeling a drainage system [88].

3.3.6 Drainage divide

The main criterion to define a drainage divide is the flow accuracy within the simulated area, meaning that the model could efficiently consider all flow-related parameters within the defined drainage divide. Topographic elevation data are often used to determine the lateral boundaries. This process's complexity is to delimit the downstream area before having the modeling results based on a few data available at the beginning of the investigation. Due to this, in case of having access to valid previous investigation results, the drainage divide can be imported directly. An additional drainage divide should be defined in the model once empirical data of observed flow conditions, control structures, or control points are available. In the absence of adequate data, the modeling area is usually extended so far downstream or upstream that possible errors in selecting the drainage divide no longer affect the actual investigation area [89].

3.4 Numerical schemes

The equations that describe fluid dynamics include non-linear terms (Section 3.2), making an analytical solution of these mathematical models impossible (except for some exceptional cases), thus requiring some simplifications. A discretization method that approximates the differential equations by an algebraic equation system must be employed to solve them by computers. This chapter presents a brief overview of the numerical schemes used in flood modeling software products to solve the flow motion equations [22], [48]. Numerical schemes help discretize and solve mathematical models at small domains in space or time and simulate unsolved fluid flow elements with parameterized approximations. Although numerous methods to discretize and simplify the equations have been devised, all simulations have the same underlying mechanism [90]. Numerical grids (Section 3.2.5) discretize the floodplain at which the variables are to be calculated; after having a discrete representation of the geometric

domain and dividing it into a finite number of subdomains, the numerical scheme to be used in the discretization process must be chosen [48]. There is a vast number of numerical schemes; however, the most used approaches to solve the SVEs fall into one of four discretization approaches, namely: method of characteristics, finite difference methods, finite element methods, and finite volume methods [2], [52].

3.4.1 Method of characteristics (MoC)

The method of characteristics is an analytical method (Section 3.1) that graphically integrates the partial differential equations. This method converts specified partial differential equations into a set of characteristic equations, the answers of which form “characteristic curves,” which play an essential role in simplifying the original equation. The scheme cannot provide reliable outcomes once a shock or a bore occurs in free-surface flow due to the characteristic curves' convergent behavior. Accordingly, this method is more applicable to pressurized flow rather than free-surface flow (Section 2.2). Moreover, the method of characteristics, together with the finite difference method (Section 3.4.2), can perform fully functional for boundary condition designations [22], [2].

3.4.2 Finite difference method (FDM)

In the method of finite difference, the governing equations are approximated by finite difference quotients, so that difference quotients replace the derivatives. The finite difference method transforms a continuous world into a discrete environment in order to compute partial derivatives. The resulting numerical solutions are the values of fixed discrete points in the domain, called grid points. Although the implementation of this method is on a structured grid, the result grid points are not necessarily of any specific structure, and more importantly, unstructured grids are proven to be more appropriate for modeling environmental flow. The two classes of finite difference methods are the explicit method and the implicit method. The explicit method progresses the solution to the end of the time step at one grid point, whereas the implicit method employs the dependent variables' values to approximate the derivatives at the beginning and the end of each time step. The explicit scheme is suitable for applications in rapid transients problems and generally is not a proper method for solving flood routing problems, where the implicit scheme is a more compatible choice [22], [2], [52].

3.4.3 Finite element method (FEM)

The finite element methods turn the problem into a system of algebraic equations by splitting the problem into smaller and simpler sections called finite elements that are in two-dimensions and are commonly unstructured. This scheme's unique feature is the association of weighting functions to the equations before the integration over the entire domain. In each element, the unknown variables are approximated by trial functions, which are linear combinations of piecewise linear functions; the next step is substituting a global function by the governing partial differential equations based on the approximations. Finally, the equation system is solvable by using the initial values stated in the main problem. The finite element method allows for handling non-homogeneous grids; on another note, mesh generations can be time-

consuming. The scheme has not been used as much as other methods in commercial software packages, possibly for the reason that it leads to long run-times [22], [2], [52].

3.4.4 Finite volume method (FVM)

The finite volume scheme divides the space into two-dimensional areas without requiring a specified geometric shape; the 2D regions are called finite volumes. Flux equations over the control volume boundaries are formed by integrating the SVEs throughout each control volume. Across each boundary, flux values are used for two neighboring control volumes that are separated by the very same boundary, leading to an ideal mass and momentum conservativeness of the approach, theoretically. In other words, the flux leaving a finite volume and the flux entering its adjacent finite volume simultaneously over a common boundary must have the same value. The finite volume scheme and the finite difference scheme work in the same way in one-dimension. The conservativeness, conceptual simplicity, and geometric flexibility of this method explain the increasing popularity of the finite volume method, to the point that they are the most used method in shallow water flow simulations [52].

3.5 Micro-scale modeling

Flood risk assessments are primarily undertaken at a macro-scale or meso-scale; however, a micro-scale modeling is needed for a detailed assessment of crucial elements. Micro-scale modeling aims to conduct hazard and risk assessments at the scale of individual facilities or buildings, which is feasible thanks to recent advances in flood simulation, making modeling with up to 10 cm data resolution possible. In such analyses, flood hazard assessment relies on detailed spatial models to solve the 2D SVEs. In general, there are three methods to present the impact of buildings on the surface runoff movements in flood modeling; the first method shows the effect of buildings using porosity parameters, which allows low-resolution data to be used and reduces modeling time, but is not recommended for micro-scale modeling. In the second method, called building block, a building is represented by increasing the height of the DEM cells to the height of the roof of the building. In the third method, called building hole, the area in which a building is located is not considered in modeling, and instead, a hole with closed boundary conditions is created in the model. One of the purposes of micro-scale modeling is the evaluation of the flood protection measures and their efficacy. This approach can provide an acceptable illustration of small topographic variations and small-scale structural elements. This simulation approach allows the user to accurately represent the surface components, buildings details, and changes in terrain elevation and define a specific roughness coefficient for each surface element. This method's advantage is that the roughness coefficient calibrations become critical [5], [91].

3.6 Numerical hydrodynamic modeling tools

The increasing growth of urbanization has led to an increase in the number of flash floods happening in urban areas, which has cost many lives and caused significant damage to properties [92]. Among different methods that are used to study urban floods, NH-modeling has proven to be a reliable approach [4]. With the aim of preventing or mitigating the number

of floods in urban areas, flood models have been developed to compute, simulate, and hopefully accurately forecast flooding in urban areas [93].

Most complete pluvial flood modeling tools that are popular throughout the field model the sewerage system in 1D, the overland flow in 2D and make it possible for both systems to interact with each other [94]. The current urban flood models can be categorized into two main classes: research-based applications and commercial software³³ products [22]. To date, all coupled 1D/2D models are commercial and not available for engineers and researchers (Table 7); this fact hinders their extensive application, which leads to a severe issue for engineers and researchers for whom a purchase is not an option [4].

Research-based models could be kind of heterogeneous, i.e., governing equations, numerical schemes, and links between sewer flow and surface flow may vary across applications; besides, a number of them have been developed for research uses and require validation [22]. So far, the attempts to propose a proper replacement for commercial models have had two outcomes [4]; one of those two is to model the sewerage system by an open-source 1D model and use the results for the 2D simulation of the overland flow [95]. The other approach is to develop the own 1D (2D) model and integrate it with an existing 2D (1D) model; the first approach is more straightforward than the second one [94].

Commercial products are characterized through similar governing equations and broadly examined numerical schemes. Consequently, in this class, the models are often more robust and rigorously tested. Relying on this standardization, the developers could concentrate more on the graphical aspects to make the product more appealing and user-friendly to the customers [22]. Examples of these tools can be found in section 3.7.

³³ In this work for commercial products, the most complete packages are considered.

3.7 Summary of the literature review

This section summarizes the various flood simulation methods and their applications, as well as the programs that have been developed for this purpose and their capabilities. There are two critical aspects in choosing the suitable flood inundation model; these two factors are the considered dimensionality of the flow and the mathematical complexity used in the numerical simulation [44]. The next two tables provide useful information to find an appropriate model based on the two aspects.

Table 6 delivers an overview of the most commonly used flood modeling methods, summarizing general information such as input data required, capabilities of each model, output data, proper applications, and time required for a simulation. More details and information about these models are available in sections 3.2.1 to 3.2.8.2 (Table 6).

Table 6: common methods for flood modeling³⁴ [1], [61], [64]

Criterion	1D model	2D model	1D/1D model	1D/2D model
Main data requirement	Sewerage network or surface channel	DEM or DTM	Sewerage network and surface channels	Sewerage network and DEM or DTM
Drainage network representation	Sewerage model: yes Channel model: no	Simplified capacity representation	Yes	Yes
Surface flood representation	Sewerage model: no Channel model: yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Computational time scale	Minutes to hours	Up to several hours	Minutes to hours	Hours to days
Adequate case study scale	Macro/mezzo	Micro	Mezzo/micro	Micro
Flood map and analysis accuracy	Low	Moderate to high	Moderate	High
Overflow spots of sewerage system	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Flood depth	Sewerage model: no Channel model: yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Surface flow velocity	Sewerage model: no Channel model: yes	2D	1D for surface channels	2D
Flooded streets	Sewerage model: no Channel model: yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Flooded buildings	No	Yes	No	Yes
Flooded extent	No	Yes	No	Yes
Flood forecast	Hotspots	Limited by computing time	Yes	Limited by computing time
Flood hazard/ risk map	Potential overflowing spots	Flood extent Flood damages	Flood extent Flood damages	Flood extent Flood damages
Real-time application	Yes	On-going research	Yes	On-going research

Table 7 provides an overview of the commonly known models with information on the type, numerical schemes used, equations, and public availability [2]. According to the subject of the

³⁴ 3D models and 1D/3D models are excluded due to lack of related and comprehensive research, 0D models are also not included since they are not NH-modelers.

present research, the freely available models are shown in gray.

Table 7: most well-known urban flood modelers³⁵ [2]

UFM	Model ³⁶	Numerical Scheme	Equations ³⁷	Freeware
++SYSTEMS	1D/2D	Unknown	SWE	No
ANUGA	2D	Explicit	SWE	Yes
CCHE	2D	Both	SWE	No
CEASG	1D/2D	Explicit	Cellular	No
DELFT3D	Multi-layered 2D	Explicit	SWE	No
DIVAST	2D	Both	SWE	No
DRAINS	1D/1D	Unknown	SWE	No
FLO-2D	2D	Explicit	SWE	No
Flood Modeller	2D	Both	SWE, KWM	No
FLOWROUTE-i	2D	Explicit	SWE	No
GWM	2D	Explicit	GWM, SWE	No
HEC-RAS	1D	Implicit	SWE	Yes
IBER	2D	Explicit	SWE	No
INFOWORKS ICM	1D/2D	Explicit	SWE	No
JFLOW+	1D/2D	Explicit	DWMwol, SWE	No
LISFLOOD-FP	2D	Explicit	KWM, GWM, SWE	Yes
MIKE URBAN+	1D/2D	Implicit	SWE	No
MOUSE	1D	Implicit	SWE	No
PDWAVE	2D	Explicit	DWMwol	No
REM U	1D	Explicit	SWE	No
RFSM	2D	Explicit	SWE	No
RFSM EDA	2D	Explicit	GWM	No
RUBAR 20	2D	Explicit	SWE	No
SIPSON	1D/1D	Implicit	SWE	No
SIPSON/GWM	1D/2D	Implicit/Explicit	GWM, SWE	No
SIPSON/PDWAVE	1D/2D	Implicit/Explicit	DWMwol	No
SIPSON/UIM	1D/2D	Implicit/Explicit	SWE, DWMwol	No
SOBEK	1D/2D	Implicit	SWE	No
SWMM5	1D	Semi Implicit	SWE, KWM	Yes
TRENT	2D	Explicit	SWE	No
TUFLOW	1D/2D	Both	SWE	No
UIM	2D	Implicit/Explicit	DWMwol	No
XP-STORM	1D/2D	Explicit	SWE	No

³⁵ This table has been updated by the author.

³⁶ For commercial software, only the most complete package was considered.

³⁷ Only the overland flow model equations are mentioned.

4 Model and system selection

As seen in Section 4, there are not many options for modeling with freeware products. Table 6 presents four freeware models that simulate floods. Of these four options, ANUGA has not been updated in recent years and is not compatible with new hardware systems (Section 4.3); moreover, there is not enough research about it to assess its performance. HEC-RAS is mostly used to calculate the floods that arose from channels, and while reviewing the literature, the use of this model to simulate urban floods was not seen. SWMM5 and LISFLOOD-FP are both robust models that have been tested many times by different researchers [52], [71]; furthermore, both have been updated recently. SWMM5 and LISFLOOD-FP have been used throughout this work; the lack of choices does not mean these two models are selected out of compulsion; on the contrary, both models have proven their worth repeatedly in their areas of use. However, there is a lack of a freely available 1D/2D model for researchers and engineers in this field. More information about each of these models is given below.

4.1 SWMM

The Storm Water Management Model, commonly referred to as SWMM, is developed by the USA's environmental protection agency and is capable of simulating a single event or long-term precipitation event. SWMM is a dynamic rainfall-runoff model and was first introduced in 1971; it is broadly considered an efficient 1D sewerage system model. It employs 1D Saint-Venant equations (Equation 3, Equation 4) to simulate runoff quantity and quality, primarily in urban areas. SWMM discretizes the study area into smaller hydrological units called subcatchments and predicts the rainfall-runoff process of each of them without the ability of surface routing. A single outlet must be assigned to each subcatchment surface to collect the generated runoff, which could be a maintenance hole or a subcatchment. Another essential parameter of an SWMM subcatchment is depression storage; when the water depth in the reservoir exceeds the depression storage value, surface runoff is generated. The transport component of SWMM uses the runoff output as input to model the flow inside the sewerage system elements [4], [88], [96].

Section 5.3 provides more details on required input data and how SWMM processes this data. Since SWMM's first release, there have been several versions of it; in this work, the latest version known as SWMM5 is employed³⁸.

4.2 LISFLOOD-FP

Originally Bates & De Roo developed the LISFLOOD-FP raster-based model [68]. LISFLOOD-FP can demonstrate the flooding development and produce a worthy estimate of the maximum flood extent. LISFLOOD-FP employs an intelligent volume-filling process based on hydraulic principles, mass conservation physical notions, and hydraulic connectivity to handle surface flooding. Additionally, the model can combine a 1D channel with a 2D floodplain, where the channel and the floodplain can be placed in the same grid cell. The model can as well account for spatially uniform precipitation, spatially uniform infiltration, and evaporation; lastly, it can

³⁸ Available at: <https://www.epa.gov/water-research/storm-water-management-model-swmm>

contain weirs in the model. LISFLOOD-FP does not allow a flexible cell size and uses a uniform mesh throughout the domain. The primary input data of LISFLOOD-FP is the floodplain DEM file; the model uses DEM cells as a mesh to represent the floodplain [4], [97]. Sections 3.2.4 and 3.2.5 provide details on the equations used by LISFLOOD-FP.

Section 5.4 provides more details on required input data and how LISFLOOD-FP processes this data. Since its first release, there have been several versions; in this work, version 5.9.6 known is employed³⁹.

4.3 Used hardware system

The simulations of both minor and major systems, as well as data manipulations, were performed with a Dell Precision 7720 notebook provided by the IKT- Institut with the following technical details:

1. Processor: Intel Core Xeon E3-1535M v5 with 4 cores, each 3.00 GHz
2. Installed RAM: 64 GB
3. Graphics card: NVIDIA Quadro M1200
4. Operating system: Microsoft Windows 10 Pro

³⁹ Available at: <http://www.bristol.ac.uk/geography/research/hydrology/models/lisflood/downloads/>

5 Hazard assessment of a selected watershed in Gelsenkirchen

5.1 Investigation area

The focus of the present thesis is the geographical location of the “IKT-institute for underground infrastructure,” which is located southeast of Gelsenkirchen, NRW, in a region called Ueckendorf (Figure 17, (a)). The area in which the institute is located has not experienced any significant floods in recent years [98]. The facility area is approximately 13,431 m² with a maximum difference in elevation of 15.88 m; the IKT-institute is limited from north and east by Exterbruch and Ostpreußen street, respectively; to the south and west, the surrounding of the study region is mostly composed of trees and dense bushes (Figure 17, (b)). The district is primarily notable for the main building, which takes 2,687 m² of the whole area, and does not have a large green area.

Figure 17: the location of the study area (a), IKT-institute for underground infrastructure (b) [99]

The city of Gelsenkirchen provides the residents with a free accessible flood hazard map. The map illustrates the computation results of a 2D rainfall-runoff simulation for a 100-year rain event scenario (Section 2.1), based on KOSTRA- Atlas 2010 [100]. The flow paths on the terrain surface have been determined by topographic analysis for the entire urban area. The DEM used for these computations depicts the surface as a regular grid with one-meter width. The map provides the following information [100]:

1. The watershed area and low points: the whole area is divided into locally delimited watershed areas for each depression, and the low point of each depression is marked
2. The flow paths: the routes taken by a water drop within the watershed area to reach the low point are shown
3. The water levels: the map indicates the maximum water level recorded for each cell during the entire simulation period; in the map, the water-depths are color-coded (Figure 18)

The sewerage system and small local structures such as curbs are not considered in the generation of inundation maps mentioned above; consequently, in particular circumstances, the water level could be overestimated or underestimated [100].

Figure 18 demonstrates an expanded view of the public hazard map with a focus on the investigation area:

Figure 18: official flood map of the study watershed provided by the city of Gelsenkirchen [101]

Figure 18 shows the watershed area in which the IKT-institute is located. Following section 3.3.6, the same watershed is chosen for the current investigation⁴⁰, i.e., the study area is expanded to the whole watershed, not only the property of the Institute (Figure 19). Nevertheless, a more detailed analysis of the critical points within the initially chosen area has been done (Section 6.3).

Figure 19: study region displayed on Google Maps [102]

The selected watershed of 3.98 hectares lies between latitudes 51°30'29.9772"N and 51°30'35.6904"N and longitudes 7°07'52.255"E and 7°08'11.526"E and has an average 54.57 altitude of meters above mean sea level.

Based on the most recent statistics, the watershed receives more than 813 mm of annual rainfall, and its temperature range varies from -9.1°C to 40.0°C [103].

5.2 Data sources for modeling

The watershed includes buildings, drainage inlets, maintenance holes, conduits, green areas,

⁴⁰ An automated watershed delineation using QGIS has also been performed using both DEMs and DSM of the area; the results correspond to the aforementioned figure (Section 5.3.2).

and an artificial pond. For the investigation area’s physical representation as a computational model, each of these components needed several parameters to be provided. No one had assembled a detailed micro-scale model of the entire watershed before; hence there was no single database containing all the information required. It was essential to collect data from multiple sources and compile them into a coherent body of information. Table 8 gives an overview of sources from which the data were collected.

Table 8: data⁴¹ providers overview

Data	Provider
Sewerage system	site-specific surveying, AutoCAD maps
Losses	engineering fluid mechanics ⁴² , civil engineering equations ⁴³
Depression storage depth	parameter guidance from the SWMM User’s Manual
Manning’s coefficient	parameter guidance from the SWMM User’s Manual
Horton infiltration parameter	parameter guidance from the SWMM User’s Manual
Precipitation	KOSTRA-DWD 2010R software
Soil characteristics	federal institute for geosciences and natural resources
LiDAR	Cologne’s regional administration’s official website
DEM	Cologne’s regional administration’s official website
Land use	Cologne’s regional administration’s official website

Some of these data have only been used for one of the models, while most are generally necessary for all types of modeling, independent of the software product; however, each product requires its own individual input format.

5.3 HN-modeling using SWMM

5.3.1 Topographic data

Before working with specialized flood simulators, topographic data must be prepared for further usage. Figure 20 shows the general steps toward data preparation and correction.

Figure 20: general workflow of stream and watershed delineation with GIS⁴⁴ (own illustration) [104]

Watershed DEM and DSM⁴⁵ data were the fundamental source of information for representing the surface. Here, the data were collected from Cologne’s regional administration’s official

⁴¹ The evaporation and groundwater parameters can be ignored for the selected watershed in case of a heavy rain event simulation due to the high humidity and tightness of the pipes respectively [98].

⁴² Technische Strömungslehre

⁴³ bauformeln.de

⁴⁴ Not all these steps were necessary for this project since QGIS only has been used for data preparation and not the complete analysis.

⁴⁵ All the processes in section 5.3.1 have been done via QGIS.

website. The digital elevation model and the 3D measurement data of the tile 1_32_370_5708_2, in which the understudy watershed is located, were downloaded, extracted, and organized for further processing in QGIS. Both datasets are in the UTM32 geographic coordinate system. For a proper representation of the watershed surface, both DEM and DSM data were required. The State of North Rhine-Westphalia provides elevation models with a grid width of 1 meter, i.e., it has a point density of at least 1 point/m². The available DEM data of the watershed is of good quality; however, without a height correction, they are not suitable for modeling a small watershed (Section 3.5). The baseline data for the generation of these DEMs are “Light Detection and Ranging” data (LiDAR). LiDAR data are obtained from the laser scanning and describe the terrain and the surface by irregularly distributed georeferenced elevation points. These data are also available by the same provider with a point density of 4 to 10 points per square meter on average. The DEM data have a vertical accuracy of +/- 20 centimeters and no horizontal inaccuracy, while the LiDAR data have a horizontal accuracy of +/- 30 centimeters; however, their vertical accuracy is by 5 centimeters less than the DEM data [105], [106].

Prior to work with DEM, a reprojection to the country’s local projection was necessary considering DEM analysis requires a metric projection; hence, the latitude-longitude geographic coordinate system with degree units does not function [104].

The LiDAR data needed more preprocessing than DEM data. LiDAR transformation into DSM has been done with the LAsTool plugin’s help. Two raster data have been generated from the LiDAR files, one with a grid width of 5 cm (for a detailed micro-scale modeling) and one with a one-meter grid width (for a complete watershed modeling and combining with the DEM data). Once the preparation was completed, the watershed was extracted out of the whole tile by its extent (Figure 21, (a)). The *.xyz DEM data only needed an interpolation to be converted in raster data and ready for an extraction (Figure 21, (b)).

Figure 21: digital land models of the selected watershed (a) DSM, (b) DEM

Once both maps were all set, voids and sinks of them were eliminated. The void interpolation objective is to cover the missing data using the values of surrounding cells; however, this step did not result in any changes due to the provided data's high quality. The sink removal algorithm aims to eliminate artificial depressions caused by DEM creation by filling them up or cutting through them; these depressions hinder water movement toward the outlet [104]. This process resulted in a few changes, especially in the DSM. Then, the buildings and sidewalks' elevation were imported from DSM in DEM to achieve a more realistic representation of the watershed surface. The quality of the resulted map (height-corrected DEM) was then improved by doing the void and sink removal once again. For validation of the final map, an official

AutoCAD map of the IKT containing the critical points' elevation was georeferenced to overlay the corrected DEM; then, elevations of these points were compared to elevations of the same spots in the final map. The maximum elevation difference was less than one centimeter, which is way smaller than the vertical accuracy of the two maps (+/- 20 centimeters each). Based on site-surveys, few more changes have been added to the corrected DEM; The last checkpoint source was Google Map. This source was applied for overall horizontal positioning control; no differences were observed. The resulting "height-corrected map" was then used for further analysis (Figure 22).

Figure 22: final surface model (height-corrected DEM)

The height-corrected map was used as a base map to calculate flow directions and to derive streams. The flow directions were calculated similarly to slope calculation. For each cell, slopes to the surrounding cells were calculated, then the flow direction was assigned to the steepest slope. The stream network was constructed to determine the precipitation water movement's behavior on the watershed surface based on the calculated flow directions. As surface water flows towards the outlet, it accumulates; hence a threshold is needed above which the accumulated flow is considered a part of the stream. Given that there is no general rule to define this threshold, the existing flood hazard map (Figure 18) was used as a reference to define the threshold value as well as the outlets (Section 5.3.2) [104].

5.3.2 Subcatchment

Subcatchments are the smallest computational units used by the SWMM to represent the drainage region. In SWMM, a subcatchment is conceptualized as a rectangle having a uniform slope directing surface runoff into a single discharge point, which could be a system node or

another subcatchment (Figure 23, (a)). Subcatchments themselves are divided into impervious and pervious subareas. Surface runoff infiltration only happens into the pervious subarea upper soil zone. The impervious areas of the subcatchments are again divided into two parts, with or without depression storage (Figure 23, (b)) [83].

Figure 23: SWMM surface representation concept: (a) idealized representation of a subcatchment, (b) idealized subcatchment partitioning for overland flow [83]

Each subcatchment has its particular hydrological characteristics and its individual rainfall-runoff processes. The SWMM simulation is conducted based on geographical and hydrological information of these subcatchments, thereby directly affecting the simulation results. In order to specify subcatchments, three methods are commonly used. The first approach is based on the watershed partition method, the second approach is based on the sewerage system, and lastly, the most common division method is the direct manual watershed division [107], [108]. Since the understudy watershed is relatively small, which makes the model more sensitive to data accuracy (Section 3.5), a manual watershed division was chosen to account for discretization complications in a small urbanized environment. The method used here combines several site-surveys and the aforementioned approaches while trying to maintain uniform properties throughout each delineated subcatchment to represent surface spatial variability properly [83].

In the first method, an automatic watershed delineation was performed for the corrected DEMs; the generated subcatchments drain into a computational node [109]. This approach helped to divide the watershed's non-urbanized area (Figure 24, (a)). The flow directions were calculated for the corrected DEM map (Figure 24, (b)); however, this process is always challenging due to the extensive range of flat terrain in urban areas [107]. For getting the most use of this method, all the steps were repeated for the DSM data as well. Before the implementation of the process on the DSM, the DSM data was corrected based on on-site observations, especially at the locations of drainage nodes to lead the flows toward the minor system. Since the DSM data has a resolution of 5 cm, the generated flow directions have a fine resolution as well, which helped with the delineation of small subcatchments and getting into the details (Figure 24, (c)).

The second method is based on the storm sewer system, and the watershed topography is not considered in the delineation processes. Since in SWMM, the minor system nodes represent the subcatchment outlets, a drainage area is allocated to each node, generally by using the Thiessen polygon method (Appendix C) and junctions' spatial distribution (Figure 24, (d)) [107].

Figure 24: watershed division preparation process: (a) watershed divided according to the DEM, (b) flow direction map calculated for a one-meter DEM, (c) a sample of flow direction map calculated for a corrected five-centimeter DSM, (d) watershed divided according to the Thiessen polygon method

Once each method's initial subcatchment-division was defined, further refinements were required; therefore, the results were compared, combined, validated, and adjusted by considering slopes and several site-surveys both on dry⁴⁶ and wet⁴⁷ days. This adjustment aimed to reflect obstruction locations, which may have directed surface flows away from their natural paths. In this manner, the delineation led to 63 discrete SWMM subcatchments within the drainage area (Figure 25). The subcatchments range from undeveloped forested areas to industrial areas.

Figure 25: the result of the manual watershed division

Once the watershed division was done, the required parameters for each subcatchment were calculated and assigned to the corresponding subcatchment. The required parameters for the subcatchments in an SWMM model can be divided into two categories, each containing different subcategories [110]:

⁴⁶ To check for possible obstructions that could divert the flow from its natural path, they were also added to the DEM data.
⁴⁷ To observe the surface runoffs' natural patterns.

1. Physical Parameters: area, width, and slope
2. Hydrological Parameters: imperviousness, impervious manning, pervious manning, impervious and pervious depression storage, maximum infiltration rate, minimum infiltration rate, and decay coefficient

The subcatchment areas have been calculated automatically via QGIS for the polygon layer representing the subcatchments distribution. The area can also be estimated manually based on the DEM resolution and the number of pixels inside each subcatchment (Equation 13) [110].

	$S_i = \text{cell size}^2 \cdot n_i$
<i>Where:</i>	
S_i	<i>the area of subcatchment i</i>
<i>cell size</i>	<i>the resolution of DEM pixels</i>
n_i	<i>the number of DEM pixels located in subcatchment i</i>

Equation 13: subcatchment area calculation based on DEM data [110]

Few of the automatically calculated substatement areas have been double-checked by this method. The results showed no significant deviation from initial calculated areas; however, the automatic method provides more precise outcomes counting the pixels cut by the subcatchment boundaries.

SWMM5 necessitates the subcatchment width parameter as an essential input to obtain a sense of geometry. A good estimation of the subcatchment width can be obtained by dividing the subcatchments area by its maximum overland flow length (Equation 14) [83].

	$W_i = S_i / l_{max}$
<i>Where:</i>	
W_i	<i>the width of subcatchment i</i>
l_{max}	<i>the maximum runoff length in the subcatchment i</i>
S_i	<i>the area of subcatchment i</i>

Equation 14: subcatchment width calculation [110]

In the framework of this study, the maximum flow path length estimations were computed using QGIS, for which the maximum straight-line within each subcatchment were calculated using the “Oriented minimum bounding box” and “Polygons to lines” tools (Figure 26, (a)). For the method's reliability testing, the longest flow route of various subcatchments was estimated manually, with the help of flow directions and one-meter interval contour lines, both generated by QGIS (Figure 26, (b)). A comparison between manual and automatic calculations showed no notable deviation.

Figure 26: (a) oriented minimum bounding box generated for each subcatchment, (b) one-meter interval contour lines

For each subcatchment, the slopes were estimated by analyzing the DEM data using the QGIS raster slope analysis tool. The generated slope map required additional processes to achieve the average slope for each subcatchment; the zonal statistics tool combined with several vector analysis tools were then employed to obtain the final slope values [111].

The land surface type of the watershed is a mix, meaning that it can be categorized into two primary sorts [83]:

1. Pervious surface: allows infiltration of the rainfall into the underlying soil
2. Impervious surface: no infiltration occurs

The impervious area percentage can manually be calculated by overlaying watershed boundaries on the official land use map provided by the state of NRW [112]; however, this map does not provide sufficient information for small watershed analysis and detailed subcatchment parameterization. Nevertheless, the overall distribution of the watershed land use was calculated based on this map and used as a benchmark to evaluate the manual impervious area percentage calculation for each subcatchment (Figure 27). The watershed impervious area amount is 45.57% by assuming 76.00% imperviousness for the industrial region and 1.90% for surfaces with vegetation [83]. For each subcatchment, a manual impervious ratio has been calculated with the aid of Google Earth. The average impervious surface percentage calculated by this approach is 45.52%, which agrees with the first outcome.

Figure 27: watershed land use map

As explained above, each subcatchment is a combination of pervious and impervious areas; SWMM also offers the “subarea routing” option to control the internal overland flow of each subcatchment. User can decide between three options [83]:

1. Impervious: runoff from pervious area flows to impervious area
2. Pervious: runoff from impervious flows to pervious area
3. Outlet: runoff from both areas flows directly to the outlet

This option has been set based on the position of the pervious and impervious surfaces within each subcatchment.

The rest of the required surface parameters, such as pervious and impervious depression storage depths and pervious and impervious Manning’s coefficient, were set according to recommended values from the SWMM User’s Guide. Table 9 shows the selected depression storage depths for pervious and impervious surfaces as well as the selected surface Manning’s “n” values based on the values suggested in the user manual.

Table 9: depression storage depths and roughness coefficient for overland flow [83]

Surface	Depression storage	n
Smooth asphalt	1.30	0.011
Smooth impervious surface	1.30	0.013
Light turf	5.08	0.200
Dense shrubbery and forest litter	7.62	0.400

Results of a sensitivity analysis have revealed the effect of subcatchment critical parameters on the outcomes. Area and imperviousness percentage play the most significant role in the final hydrograph; an increase in these parameters causes an increase in runoff peak and runoff volume. Changes in width, slope, and roughness affect the hydrograph’s shape. Increasing width and slope result in an increase in runoff peak and a decrease in runoff volume, whereas roughness has an inverse effect as for width and slope. Depression storage changes the hydrograph moderately. Runoff peak and runoff volume drop as the value of depression storage rises. In general, as the storm depth increases, the effect of losses (roughness and depression storage) becomes relatively less significant (Table 10) [83].

Table 10: sensitivity of runoff volume and peak flow to surface runoff parameters [83]

Parameter	Typical effect on the hydrograph	Effect of increase on runoff volume	Effect of increase on runoff peak	Comments
Area	Significant	Increase	Increase	Less effect for a highly porous catchment
Imperviousness	Significant	Increase	Increase	Less effect when pervious areas have low infiltration capacity
Width	Affects shape	Decrease	Increase	An increase causes a generally faster response for storms of varying intensity
Slope	Affects shape	Decrease	Increase	Same as for the width, but less sensitive
Roughness	Affects shape	Increase	Decrease	Inverse effect as for the width
Depression storage	Moderate	Decrease	Decrease	The significant effect only for low-depth storms

5.3.3 Infiltration

The classical Horton method was selected to take the infiltration losses into account. SWMM offers different infiltration methods, from which Horton is the most suitable for a heavy rain event. This approach relies on empirical observations indicating that infiltration decreases exponentially from an initial maximum rate to a certain minimum rate during a rain event. Nevertheless, regardless of the infiltration method, the method parameters are highly dependent on land use and soil characteristics. Required input parameters to determine are the maximum and minimum infiltration rates and a decay coefficient. These values depend on

the soil type, initial moisture content, and vegetation of the study area (Equation 15) [83].

$f_p = f_\infty + (f_0 - f_{p\infty})e^{-k_d t}$	
<i>Where:</i>	
f_p	<i>infiltration capacity into the soil</i>
f_∞	<i>minimum or equilibrium value of f_p (at $t = \infty$)</i>
f_0	<i>maximum or initial value of f_p (at $t = 0$)</i>
t	<i>time from beginning of storm</i>
k_d	<i>decay coefficient</i>

Equation 15: Horton infiltration capacity over time [83]

Horton’s equation simulates soil infiltration capacity as a function of time, based on empirical observations, and is suitable to rain events for which the precipitation intensity surpasses the infiltration capacity. SWMM also offers a modified Horton infiltration for non-heavy rain events. Even though the Horton infiltration equation is possibly the most prominent infiltration model available, selecting parameter values is challenging [88].

In order to define the infiltration parameter of the model, the soil type of the watershed was required. The soil type has been specified based on a soil map provided by the federal institute for geosciences and natural resources [113]. The soil map was georeferenced and overlaid on the watershed to assign corresponding soil types. Considering the watershed size and the fact that SWMM only uses the infiltration method for pervious areas (which are not distributed all over the watershed (Figure 27)), a single soil type was decided for the whole watershed (Figure 28).

As shown in the soil map, the dominant soil type of the watershed surface layer is loess. The loess soil consists of strongly sandy, clayey, partly humic silt and is characterized as “slightly permeable” based on the percolation test, according to DIN 18130-1. In the hydrologic soil classification offered by the natural resource conservation (NRCS), loess is assigned to group B, i.e., it has moderate infiltration rates when thoroughly wetted [88], [114].

Figure 28: georeferenced soil map of the NRW in the area of IKT-watershed

A maximum infiltration rate of 203.2 mm/h, a minimum infiltration rate of 10.9 mm/h, and a decay coefficient of 3.0 h⁻¹ were set for the simulations based on the values suggested by the

SWMM manual, which are adjustable at any time analogous to the other values.

5.3.4 Sewerage system

Data for the watershed conduits and nodes were taken from several sources. The watershed drainage system contains 31 maintenance holes and 24 drainage inlets, and a small artificial pond.

The watershed SWMM model contains one storage element, representing the artificial pond with a depth of 0.2 m covering around 301 m² on a dry day. The storage curve for the pond was calculated utilizing QGIS. At 10 cm intervals, contour lines were generated. Table 11 demonstrates the calculated storage curve.

Table 11: storage curve for the artificial pond created in QGIS

Elevation [m]	Depth [m]	Area [m ²]
53.00	0.00	301.635
53.20	0.20	301.635
53.25	0.25	328.743
53.30	0.30	414.893
53.35	0.35	450.021
53.40	0.40	484.697
53.45	0.45	525.852

From all the nodes and links in the system, 38 nodes and 61 conduits were specified in an existing rainwater conveyance network map of the IKT; however, determining dimensions of the minor system was a challenge since not all the necessary modeling data could be extracted from the provided drainage system map. Unfortunately, significant data such as pipe diameter was missing from this map, and the map did not deliver any information about the terminal point of the system. The information had also not been updated since its creation, so important changes were missing; therefore, field data collection was necessary. Geographical locations, invert elevations, and depths of the nodes were double-checked and validated by onsite data investigation. Each of the drainage inlet covers and maintenance hole covers was removed for depth and dimension measurements within the IKT institute property. All the drainage inlets have the same depth, length, and width of 70 cm, 50 cm, and 30 cm, respectively. The maintenance hole depths vary from 0.79 m to 3.90 m, while they all have the same diameter of 60 cm. The pipes' diameter and direction toward the next drainage node were also determined during the onsite data collection. The node ground elevations are taken from the site plan, which corresponds to DEM data's elevation values. During data collection, besides depth and invert values of junctions, more useful information was obtained:

1. A total of 17 new junctions were found that were not displayed on the map (Figure 29, (a)).
2. A total of 5 junctions shown on the map were either nonexistent or not connected to the drainage network (Figure 29, (b)).
3. There was water in three maintenance holes; the initial water depth in these collectors was measured (Figure 29, (c)).
4. Two downspouts connected the rooftops to the ground surface, and one was directly connected to the drainage system.

5. The diameter of the pipes was measured.
6. With the help of direction, diameter, and flow in the pipes connected to each maintenance hole, together with the available map, the drainage network's underground structure was accurately estimated (Figure 29, (d)).
7. The conduits inlet and outlet offsets from the inlet and outlet junctions were measured.

Figure 29: examples of important data gained through site surveying: (a) uncovering maintenance hole hidden under bushes, (b) maintenance hole shown on the map not connected to the drainage system, (c) water at the junction on a dry day, (d) the diameter and direction of the pipe and the water existence indicating that the junction is connected to the artificial pond in the watershed

Both maintenance holes and drainage inlets are represented by “junction” in SWMM. SWMM assumes all surface runoff will go to the junctions and be routed downstream, meaning that it does not model the inflow and outflow restrictions caused by node cover, and assumes the same surface area for all the junctions, which could be defined under simulation options as “minimum nodal surface area.” Minimum nodal surface area is used at nodes when computing changes in water depth [83]. A minimum nodal surface area of 0.21 m² has been defined, achieved by weighted averaging of maintenance holes surface area and drainage inlets surface area.

All the drainage network water flows into the only outfall in the drainage system located in the northwest corner of the watershed and finally exits the system. The details of this outfall are unknown; however, its location and capacity were available, which are enough to run a heavy rain simulation [98].

Further details of the conduits, which carry water toward the watershed outfall, have been

collected from the sewerage system map. Using Pythagoras' theorem, the elevation of pipe fittings and the exact lengths of conduits were calculated.

Junction nodes also represent pipe fittings in an SWMM model. For representing pipe fittings correctly, the depths of junctions were defined as equal to the maximum pipe diameter connected to them. In order to prevent flooding in pipe fitting junctions, a surcharge depth higher than the maximum expected hydraulic depth in the whole system was defined for each pipe fitting. The watershed pipe data was mostly extracted from the drainage system map. It provided the size, inlet node, and outlet node for most of the conduits. This information was augmented and controlled with the field survey results.

The watershed rainwater conveyance system's building material is brick, and there is no leakage in the whole system [98]. Conduits Manning's n values have been chosen according to the values suggested by the SWMM user manual. Entry and exit loss coefficients were set to 0.5 and 1, respectively [115], [116].

After gathering all the required information, all relevant values have been assigned to the SWMM model, and eventually, the drainage network was precisely defined to represent the real stream accurately (Figure 28).

Figure 30: watershed drainage system model

Appendix E summarizes the properties of the entire drainage system and the values used to build the model.

5.3.5 Rainfall data

Within the scope of this master thesis, a 100-year rain event was taken into consideration; the design rain was modeled according to the Euler-type II precipitation model with a duration of one hour and a time step of five minutes. The 100-year rain event has a total precipitation depth of 55.00 mm and was chosen since it corresponds to the selected rain event used by the city of Gelsenkirchen to create the official flood hazard map so that the results are comparable with it as a reference map (Figure 18, Figure 31). These precipitation models were obtained using the KOSTRA-DWD 2010R software from the "Institut für technisch-wissenschaftliche Hydrologie GmbH."

Figure 31: one-hour Euler Type II model precipitation for a 100-year heavy rain event (own illustration)

The precipitation data were added to the model in the form of user-defined time series to supply the required inputs for the only rain gage of the system.

5.3.6 Surface water modeling

At the beginning of modeling with SWMM, SI metric unit system was selected for flow units; SWMM determines units of all other quantities based on the chosen flow unit (Appendix D). Before analyzing the model performance, the general options of the analysis needed to be determined. SWMM lets the user choose between three different flow routing approaches, namely the steady flow routing method, the kinematic wave routing method, and the dynamic wave method. The dynamic wave routing method was selected within the current research framework since it solves the complete one-dimensional Saint-Venant equations and, consequently, generates the most theoretically accurate results. SWMM dynamic wave routing method calculates continuity and momentum equations for conduits and a volume continuity equation at junctions (Equation 3, Equation 4). With this form of routing, the pressurized flow in a full conduit can be represented (Section 2.2, Section 3.2.2) [83]. The runoff computation time step was set to one second, which is the smallest interval possible in SWMM. The routing time step for the flow through the conveyance system was set to 0.1 of a second; this step was repeated with larger and smaller time steps; the shorter time step resulted in a higher flow routing continuity⁴⁸ error, and the other ones did not change the results it just caused an increase in simulation time from 8 seconds to 8175 seconds (Table 12).

Table 12: routing time step effect on the results⁴⁹

Routing time step [s]	Flow routing continuity error	Runoff quantity continuity error	Number of critical elements	Total elapsed time
1	-0.014	0.000	5	00:00:02
0.1	0.000	0.000	0	00:00:08
0.01	0.000	0.000	0	00:01:09
0.001	0.000	0.000	0	00:13:29
0.0001	0.000	0.000	0	02:16:15

⁴⁸ Continuity errors in SWMM5 stand for the percent difference between initial storage plus total inflow and final storage plus total outflow for the entire drainage system. The validity of the outcomes requires to be doubted if the continuity errors exceed around +/-10 percent [88].

⁴⁹ The outcomes that did not show any change overall five test simulations are not included.

Figure 32 shows the last version of the model built to simulate the watershed, the simulations performed to analyze this watershed have been performed on this model. As shown in the picture, areas of subcatchments vary from 0.0023 hectares to 0.852 hectares, conduits lengths are between the range of 1.22 meters to 45.48 meters, and invert elevations of the nodes lie between 48.51 meters and 53.73 meters.

Figure 32: the final watershed map created in SWMM5 showing the elements used for the simulations

The final values of the subcatchment-, conduit-, and junction- parameters are shown in the Appendix G. Lastly, after providing the modeler all the required input data, the simulation was executed with a simple click on the run button (Figure 33).

Figure 33: simulation run layout of the SWMM5

5.3.7 Model calibration

The reasonableness of an SWMM model usually takes place by calibrating the model against any available monitored data. There is no data available about the sewerage system

performance for the selected watershed, which makes an accurate calibration of the model impossible. Since this research's main focus was to study the performance of freeware products, this lack of calibration does not negatively affect the outcomes; still, Huber's previous research has given away that uncalibrated models can deliver valuable results provided that hypotheses made during the model development are realistic [117].

For large events⁵⁰, where runoff is generated on both impervious and pervious areas, only a few parameters such as surface area and percentage of impervious area are dominant, while the hydrology does not significantly affect the results. Generally, as the storm depth increases, losses (e.g., infiltration, depression storage) become less decisive, and the land surface starts behaving more and more like an impervious surface. In contrast to runoff quality predictions, reasonable estimates of hydrographs can be made before calibration for runoff quantity prediction [83].

Despite the lack of experimental data, several simulations were run with varying values for Manning's roughness coefficient and infiltration parameter to assess the model sensitivity. These simulations' performance did not show any noteworthy difference in the results⁵¹; besides, the results were compared to the previous 2D simulation results (Section 5.4.6), and the surface and sewerage system data were compared and completed with numerous site observations (Section 5.3.1 to 5.3.5).

⁵⁰ The theories about which rain event counts as a large event are not unanimous; however, an event with a return period greater than two years counts as a large event in most related works. With this being the case, rain events employed in the current study fall into the "large" category.

⁵¹ The result agreed with the results from the user manual (Table 10, Section 5.3.7)

5.4 HN-modeling using LISFLOOD-FP

5.4.1 Topographic data

The primary component of the LISFLOOD-FP model is the terrain data set. The LISFLOOD-FP's mesh is a cartesian grid, with its squares all have the same dimensions (Section 3.2.5), meaning that the mesh can be generated quickly only by inserting the watersheds DEM data. In order to generate a mesh for LISFLOOD-FP to simulate the watershed surface runoff, two datasets were translated into ASCII file format:

1. The digital elevation model without further adjustment, to compare the performance of the LISFLOOD-FP with the official flood map of the watershed (Figure 18)
2. The height-corrected DEM built upon numerous site investigations to evaluate the importance of the details in the micro-scale modeling (Section 5.3.1, Figure 22)

The LISFLOOD-FP user manual suggests grid resolutions of approximately 25 m to 100 m for rural floodplain applications and smaller resolutions in urban areas. The preferred vertical accuracy recommended is 0.25 m or less [97]. The DEM used in this work fits both of these criteria. The DEM file with the *.ascii file extension has six header lines with values of each grid point specified as a 2D array coming afterward. Table 13 contains the header lines used in the current study and what they are signifying.

Table 13: header lines of the watershed DEM files⁵²

DEM		Comment [97]
ncols	376	Number of columns
nrows	167	Number of rows
xllcorner	370309.000000000000	X cartesian co-ordinate of the lower left corner of the grid in meters
yllcorner	5708011.000000000000	Y cartesian co-ordinate of the lower left corner of the grid in meters
cellsize	1.000000000000	Cell size in meters
NODATA_value	-999999999	Null value

5.4.2 Roughness coefficient

LISFLOOD-FP provides the user with two different methods to specify the Manning's coefficient of the floodplain; one is to assign a uniform value for the entire floodplain, and the other one is to assign values of Manning's coefficient to each raster grid cell across the floodplain and thereby apply a spatially variable Manning's coefficient [97]. Since the watershed is a semi-urban area that consists of industrial areas and woods (Figure 26), the second approach was used. In order to generate a suitable file containing roughness coefficients for each cell of the DEM, the help of QGIS was needed. Although QGIS is able to generate an automatic roughness coefficient for raster layers by calculating the largest inter-cell difference of a central cell and pixels surrounding it (Figure 34), another layer was generated with values used in the SWMM5 model (Table 9) [118].

The second layer was built by recreating the SWMM5 subcatchment model (Figure 25) as a vector layer in QGIS, assigning the Manning's n values used in the SWMM model as an attribute to each feature of this layer, and finally converting the vector layer to a raster layer

⁵² Both DEM file and height corrected DEM file have the same header lines.

(Figure 34).

Figure 34: Manning's n values: (a) roughness coefficient automatic generated by QGIS, (b) roughness coefficient based on SWMM model of the watershed

Both of these layers were converted to *.ascii format by the same process as described in section 5.4.1 and were used to analyze the influence of the roughness coefficient on the watershed model (Section 5.4.6).

5.4.3 Infiltration

Not all the simulation methods provided by the LISFLOOD-FP support an infiltration calculation, and when they do, a uniform infiltration rate is assumed across the floodplain; therefore, if applicable, the infiltration rate of the impervious area was preferred over the infiltration rate of the woods. The reason for this decision is the fact that in such heavy rain events, the pervious area starts behaving impervious, and on the other hand, the main interest of the present thesis is urban areas where the surface is mostly impervious. The values were decided based on the method described in section 5.3.3 (Appendix F) [83], [97].

5.4.4 Rainfall data

The LISFLOOD-FP model applies spatially uniform precipitation over the domain; this work deals with a small area and an extremely heavy rain event; hence this quality may cause no lack of accuracy here; however, this may not be a proper method to recreate and model in other cases. The same rainfall data as for section 5.3.5 were adjusted and prepared to be read by the LISFLOOD-FP modeler (Appendix F).

5.4.5 Surface water modeling

LISFLOOD-FP is a simple model downloaded as a *.zip file; it does not require further installation after being unzipped. The unzipped folder contains 14 files, which are not all needed for each simulation. The main files are model executables; however, the model must be run from the Windows command line, not by double-clicking the executable [97].

Once all the information necessary to run the simulation was prepared, they were addressed in the *.par file, which is a code containing this information's names and locations (Appendix F). Besides data of watershed and precipitation, the duration of the simulation, the maximum possible time step, and the floodplain flow solver (Table 14) must be defined in this file. Solvers are numerical schemes that simulate the flood wave propagation across the floodplain by simplifying the shallow water equations (Equation 10, Equation 11) [97]; in the present thesis, two of the solvers offered in LISFLOOD-FP were used:

1. The “acceleration” model: simplifies the shallow water equations by neglecting the convective acceleration term (Appendix A). The solver uses various time steps throughout the simulation; these time steps are related to water depth and the cell size [97].
2. The “Roe” model: solves the full shallow water equations. Despite being the most comprehensive solver in the package, the Roe solver has been reviewed only on a limited number of scenarios and possibly is not as robust as the acceleration solvers [97].

Except for the difference in the equations solved by each model, another difference between the acceleration solver and the Roe solver is the consideration of the infiltration losses, which is ignored in the Roe solver while the acceleration solver assumes a spatially uniform infiltration rate throughout the floodplain [97].

Table 14: Solvers available for calculating floodplain flow [97]

Solver	Dimensions	Shallow water terms included	Shallow water terms assumed negligible	Timestep
Routing	1D on a 2D grid	User-specified velocity and bed slope direction only	All	Adaptive
Flow-limited	1D on a 2D grid	Friction and water slopes	Local and convective acceleration	Fixed
Adaptive	1D on a 2D grid	Friction and water slopes	Local and convective acceleration	Adaptive
Acceleration	1D on a 2D grid, friction terms in 2D	Friction and water slopes, local acceleration	Convective acceleration	Adaptive
Roe	2D	All terms	None	Adaptive

No extra boundary condition was necessary to be defined in the code since the default option (zero-flux) fits this case the best.

Lastly, after providing the modeler with all the required input data, the simulation was executed with the help of the Windows command prompt and a simple command line (Figure 35).


```

Eingabeaufforderung
Microsoft Windows [Version 10.0.17134.1304]
(c) 2018 Microsoft Corporation. Alle Rechte vorbehalten.

C:\Users\mobill>cd C:\Users\mobill\3D Objects\Thesis\Software\Lisflood-FP\versuche\100a\HKDEM\velocity
C:\Users\mobill\3D Objects\Thesis\Software\Lisflood-FP\versuche\100a\HKDEM\velocity>liflood -v ikt_acceleration.par
*****
LISFLOOD-FP version 5.8.9
*****

Loading parameters...
Using acceleration formulation for floodplain flow
Reading parameters done.

Start Date: 22/1/2021
Start Time: 3:17:57

Loading DEM: height_corrected_FP.dem.asci
376x167
BL corner (378309.000000,5788011.000000)
MCDATA_value -1000000000.000000
Done.

Loading floodplain Manning's n data: manning_auto.n.asci Done.

Porosity off
Weirs off

Loading time varying rainfall: ikt.rain
Done.

Floodplain infiltration set at: 0.0000010000 ms-1

Starting time steps: acceleration mode

Finished.

Finish Date: 22/1/2021
Finish Time: 6:24:45

Total computation time: 186.80 mins

```

Figure 35: simulation run layout of the LISFLOOD-FP

5.4.6 Model calibration

Calibration of the 2D HN-models is often carried out by adjusting roughness coefficient values till the simulation results match the observed results. Since parameters such as Manning’s roughness coefficient are immeasurable, they have to be inferred by calibration. One way to achieve more realistic roughness coefficient values is by using detailed, high-resolution DEM (5.4.3), which allows having a spatially distributed roughness coefficient and consequently less need to calibrate an HN-model [119], [120].

The parameters that played a key role in the 2D LISFLOOD-FP model and needed to be calibrated are the floodplain’s roughness coefficient and the surface model. The prior one was calibrated based on the area’s official flood map (Figure 18), both simulating a 100-year rain event, while the latter one was calibrated based on field investigations; moreover, a decision should have been made between the solvers. Figure 36 gives an overview of the steps taken towards achieving the input data that fits the best.

Figure 36: the process of data validation and model calibration⁵³

After running the first four simulations to decide on a solver and calibrate the Manning’s n values, the first thing noticed was simulation times. For this specific watershed, the Roe solver needs more calculation time, which can be explained considering that it solves the complete 2D SWE equations while the other solver neglects the convective acceleration term of the 2D SWE equations.

⁵³ n₁ is roughness coefficient generated automatically by QGIS, and n₂ is roughness coefficient based on watershed SWMM model.

Table 15 gives details on the computation time needed for each generated map.

Table 15: computation time for the first set of the calibration simulations

Solver	n	Values generated automatically by QGIS	Values adapted from the SWMM model
Acceleration		24.13 minutes	27.43 minutes
Roe		81.48 minutes	79.20 minutes

It is noteworthy to mention that a long computation time and a more complicated set of equations do not necessarily mean better results; as already explained in section 5.4.5, the Roe solver is still in developing stages and may result in some unexpected results.

After having the first set of simulations, all the results have been added as a raster layer in QGIS. In order to have a more sensible comparison between the results and the official flood map, the same water depth categorization, colors, and background is used. Nevertheless, a slight difference can be recognized between the official map and the simulation results due to the maps' different GIS projections.

Figure 37: predicted flood extent and depth after the rain event: (a) reference flood map [101], (b) simulation result of using acceleration solver, and the DEM-base auto-generated roughness coefficient values

Figure 37 displays the flood map, simulated with the acceleration solver, and the DEM-base auto-generated roughness coefficient values on the right and the left one is the reference map. As shown in the pictures, the predicted and reference maximum flooding depths and extents are very similar. The two spots specified on each picture with blue lines are the most apparent differences between the two map; the one on the left, though, is because of the different projection of the to maps causing the none flooded area to look crooked on reference map, by overlaying the water depth layer on the DEM file this can clearly be seen (Figure 38, (a)). The other difference is exactly where the artificial pond of the watershed is located. The water depth in the simulated map is larger than the water depth in the reference map; the existing water in the pond can explain this, which was considered in the simulated map (Figure 38, (b)).

Figure 38: predicted flood extent and depth after the rain event: (a) flood map on the surface model which was used for the simulation, (b) existing water in the artificial pond

Figure 39: predicted flood extent and depth after the rain event: (a) reference flood map [101], (b) simulation result of using Roe solver, and the DEM-base auto-generated roughness coefficient values

Figure 39 displays the flood map, simulated with the Roe solver, and the DEM-base auto-generated roughness coefficient values on the right and the left one is the reference map. As shown in the pictures, the predicted and reference maximum flooding depths and extents are not similar; the results show an increase in the flood extent and a decrease in the water depths. Since the only difference between this simulation and the one explained above is the solver, it can be concluded that the acceleration solver is more suitable for the study area.

Figure 40: predicted flood extent and depth after the rain event: (a) reference flood map [98], (b) simulation result of using acceleration solver, and the roughness coefficient values used in the SWMM model

Figure 40 displays the flood map, simulated with the acceleration solver, and SWMM roughness coefficient values on the right and the left one is the reference map. As shown in the pictures, the predicted maximum flooding depths and extents are significantly increased in the watershed's non-urbanized area compared to the reference map. It can be concluded that either the roughness coefficient values of the woods used in the SWMM model are not suitable for this model, or the acceleration model is sensitive to the roughness coefficient values, or both. However, inaccuracies caused by using a constant value for one or more parameters, for an entire watershed or parts of the watershed were expected.

Figure 41: predicted flood extent and depth after the rain event: (a) reference flood map [98], (b) simulation result of using Roe solver, and the roughness coefficient values used in the SWMM model

Figure 41 displays the flood map, simulated with the Roe solver, and SWMM roughness

coefficient values on the right and the left one is the reference map. As shown in the pictures, the predicted maximum flooding depths are slightly smaller than the reference values, and extents are increased in the watershed's non-urbanized area. It can be concluded that the Roe solver is less sensitive to the roughness coefficient values than the acceleration solver. However, a slight overestimation of Manning's n values for the woods recommended by the SWMM can be detected from the results. This conclusion does not mean that the recommended values by SWMM are overestimated because SWMM's representation of the surface is different from a 2D model. Here is more rational to stay with the recommended values since they have proven to be more suited for SWMM models; the decision for a change in the SWMM model can only be made by calibration with observed data; moreover, no extensive flood depths were detected in the SWMM results (Section 6.1).

Since the exact values used to generate the reference map are not available, no further numerical calibration was possible. Nevertheless, the first simulation results (Figure 36) show that the acceleration solver combined with the DEM-base Manning's values can deliver similar results to this study area's reference map.

Figure 42 displays the flood map, simulated with the acceleration solver, and the DEM-base auto-generated roughness coefficient values on the right and the left one is the reference map. As shown in the pictures, the predicted maximum flooding depths and extents do not correspond to the reference map. On the one hand, the calculated water depth is less than the water depth shown in the reference map, and on the other hand, the flood extent, especially downstream of this catchment, is predicted more than the reference map.

Figure 42: predicted flood extent and depth after the rain event: (a) reference flood map [98], (b) simulation result of using acceleration solver, and the DEM-base auto-generated roughness coefficient values on the height corrected digital elevation model

A comprehensive field investigation was done to find out which surface model gives the most realistic results. Two significant differences between the reference map and the map generated by the LISFLOOD-FP have been marked on both maps (Figure 42). The spot on the left has a water depth between 1 and 2 meters based on the reference map, which indicates a significant difference compared to the water depths of its surrounding area, which is reasonable considering that the raster cells of the not corrected dem in this spot lay about 1.5 meters below its surrounding cells; this means a sudden change of elevation on the surface, which is easy to see.

Figure 43 (a) is a picture of the same area, showing that the elevation changes smoothly, and there is no hole with around 1.5 meters depth where the water would be stuck and collected; consequently, the water will flow all over the surface and have a smaller depth and a larger extent. In conclusion, the height corrected surface model offers more accurate results than the

raw DEM used to generate the reference map compared with the watershed surface's real conditions.

The second area specified on the right side of the maps (Figure 42) is where the artificial pond lies. Figure 43 (b) shows the area's front view; as demonstrated in the photo, there are only three walls in the pond and not a part of the building. The official map is based on aerial maps and assumes that the building's roof outline matches the ground floor's outline, which is reasonable for modeling a big area. Once a complete survey of the watershed was finished, the differences between the two maps could be explained by these two reasons.

Figure 43: significant differences between the reference map and the map generated by the LISFLOOD-FP: (a) the area for which the DEM data was incorrect, (b) the front view of the structure in the pond

Given that the modeling results with the modified surface model produce more logical outputs than the reference map, in section 6, the LISFLOOD-FP map generated by using the acceleration solver, and the DEM-base auto-generated roughness coefficient values is used for evaluation of the other results.

6 Results

In the following sections, the calculation results of the 1D and 2D flood hazard assessments are presented. In detail, calculations for a small area within the watershed, which are particularly significant. The current study focuses on micro-scale modeling and capability of freeware products rather than the effect of a heavy rain event on watersheds; consequently, not all the details of the results are included in this work.

6.1 SWMM

Once all the required parameter was calibrated, and test runs were completed, the concluding simulation was run, for a 100-year rain event. The rain model lasts for one hour, while the simulation-time is two and a half hours in order to follow the sewerage system behavior. For calculating the approximately 4 hectares watershed, the program's status report summarizes overall results as follows: a total elapsed time of 11 seconds, 0 percent flow-routing continuity error, and 0 percent runoff-quantity continuity error. Usually, a continuity error of less than 1 percent counts as an excellent continuity error, and a continuity error of more than 10 percent requires a revision of the model parameter. A small continuity error means the model is stable based on the provided input values, which was expected here because of the surface and sewer system data accuracy. Figure 44 shows the watershed condition after the precipitation ends; as expected, the outlet located in the undeveloped area (subcatchment-62) has had the maximum runoff (62.69 liters per second) within the watershed. None of the junctions are flooding at this stage, but there is still high-velocity flow in the sewerage system.

Figure 44: calculation results of the one-hour precipitation

For the entire watershed, SWMM calculations estimate 11.495 mm infiltration, 34.157 mm surface runoff, 1066 m³ wet weather inflow, and 79 m³ flooding loss. Figure 45 exhibits the watershed at the end of simulation-time, where there has been no precipitation for one and a

half hours. At this point, the junctions are not draining any more surface water, but there are still some flows in the conduits with more than 0.5 m/s velocities (C34: 0.8 m/s, 35: 0.52 m/s, C70: 67 m/s, C107: 0.52 m/s, and C119: 0.62 m/s). One of these conduits is connected to the pond (C34), two to junctions (J1, J23), and the other one to the terminal point of the drainage system (outfall).

Figure 45: calculation results after the simulation ends

From the figure, it can be understood that the runoff in three undeveloped areas (subcatchments: 57, 62, and 63) has been infiltrated, for the most part, but there is still surface water in the outlet point of the undeveloped region (subcatchment 62, Figure 46).

Figure 46: subcatchment-62 hydrograph with respect to the rain intensity

Figure 46 shows the details of runoff on subcatchment-62 in comparison to precipitation; from the start of the rainfall till the precipitation peak, the rainwater is infiltrated into the soil, 98 seconds after the precipitation peak, the runoff development starts and hits its maximum value

five minutes after precipitation ends (68.91 LPS), and from there the second course of infiltration starts. SWMM has reported for precipitation of 55 mm over this 1355 m² subcatchment, a total runoff volume of 29 m³, and a total runoff depth of 216.04 mm. Subcatchment-62 receives the most runoff volume while having the second total runoff depth. In the entire watershed, subcatchment-16, subcatchment-62, and subcatchment-45 obtain the maximum flooding with 746.16, 132.14, and 216.04 millimeters, respectively (Table 16). Both subcatchment-16 and subcatchment-45 are located within the urbanized area and collect the rainwater of the roof through downspouts beside the direct precipitation they receive (Figure 45, Figure 47).

Table 16: subcatchments with the highest predicted runoff value

Subcatchment	Area [ha]	Total runoff [10 ⁶ liters]	Total runoff [mm]
Sub 16	0.0080	0.06	746.16
Sub 45	0.0728	0.10	132.14
Sub 62	0.1355	0.29	216.04

Figure 47 shows the hydrographs of the above-mentioned subcatchments. The diagram shows that both runoff-curves move parallel to rainfall intensity because almost no infiltration happens in these areas. In contrast to subcatchment-62, the runoff does not last long after the precipitation ends; 5 minutes after the end of precipitating, the flow rate value falls below 10 liters per second, and in 10 minutes, the flow rate value becomes less than 5 liters per second. The two subcatchments reach their flow rate peak values exactly 25 minutes after the beginning of precipitation, where subcatchment-45 reaches a flow rate of 88.38 LPS and subcatchment-16 reaches a flow rate of 54.13 LPS.

Figure 47: subcatchment-16 and subcatchment-45 hydrograph with respect to the rain intensity

According to the results, 19 of the 70 junctions overflow within the course of the simulation. Table 17 details these junctions; junction-54 has the most flooding duration with 14.4 minutes, while junction-26 with 0.6 minutes of overflowing has the least flooding period as well as the least flooding rate of 1.71 LSP. The maximum rate of flooding recorded within the simulation is 91.52 LSP at junction-5, a node that collects surface runoff of its allocated subcatchment

(subcatchment-45) plus the rainwater drained towards it by a downspout; as a result, this junction has the maximum total flood volume of around 20 m³ (Figure 48).

Table 17: SWMM report of the flooded nodes (Figure 49)

Node	Hours flooded	Max. rate [LPS]	Max. flooding time [min]	Total flood volume [10 ⁶ llitr]
J 05	0.09	91.52	24	0.02
J 06	0.05	11.14	24	0.00
J 21	0.04	3.10	24	0.00
J 26	0.01	1.71	24	0.00
J 30	0.14	8.42	24	0.00
J 31	0.16	19.60	24	0.01
J 34	0.17	18.49	24	0.01
J 36	0.14	7.25	24	0.00
J 37	0.14	7.52	24	0.00
J 38	0.22	12.51	24	0.01
J 41	0.11	9.29	24	0.00
J 43	0.10	15.53	24	0.00
J 45	0.13	11.89	24	0.00
J 46	0.06	3.40	24	0.00
J 48	0.09	23.28	24	0.01
J 53	0.08	12.58	24	0.00
J 54	0.10	6.21	24	0.00
J 56	0.24	22.88	24	0.01
J 57	0.13	13.91	24	0.01

Figure 48 shows the decrease in level from junction-5 to the outfall. Conduit-10, which leads to outfall, has the maximum discharge of all the links shown in this figure and also in the whole watershed because the flow comes from various links (here: 491.72 LPS, max.: 505.84 LPS).

Figure 48: water elevation profile from junction-5 to the outfall

The maximum rate of flooding happens 24 minutes after the start of precipitation, and it applies to all the 19 flooded junctions (Table 17). Figure 24 exhibits the watershed model, 24 minutes after raining starts; after comparing this map with the other two maps above, it can be

concluded that surface runoff in the impervious surfaces in the urbanized region of the watershed starts almost as soon as the precipitation hits its peak while the undeveloped area is not flooded and the surface runoff starts nearly towards the end of the precipitation due to infiltration in pervious regions (Figure 46). On the other hand, after precipitation ends, there is no significant runoff in the urbanized area because of the constant draining into the sewerage system. In reality, the entire runoff is not routed into the drainage system; in case surcharge occurs, water can be stored in low points of the watershed.

Figure 49: calculation results 24 minutes after the precipitation starts

Since subcatchment-45 has the most runoff in the urbanized area and its outfall, junction-5, experiences the maximum overflow, it was chosen for a detailed analysis (Section 6.3).

6.2 LISFLOOD-FP

The final LISFLOOD-FP simulation was run using the acceleration solver. An initial time step of 0.001 seconds was set as the limit for calculation time steps resulting in 186.80 minutes of computation time; section 5.4 details the LISFLOOD-FP model settings. Figure 50 displays the simulation outcomes for the maximum water velocities in m/s; LISFLOOD-FP generates outputs containing the maximum water velocity in x- and y-direction for each cell calculated at the cell boundaries; both are shown in the picture below.

Figure 50: maximum water velocities for a 100-year rain event

It can be seen that the flow moves with a higher speed on smooth surfaces with uniform slopes, such as streets. The maximum velocities in both x and y directions occur on the edges of the buildings due to the high difference in elevation; these kinds of high-velocity flows appear in single cells, whereas the relatively high-velocity flows on the streets happen in a series of neighboring cells. The maximum velocities along the x-axis and y-axis are 2.42 m/s and 3.29 m/s, respectively.

Figure 51 displays the maximum water depths predicted for each cell on the link side, and on the right side, the time of the maximum depth occurrence. By comparing the two figures together, it can be noticed that the cells having higher elevation values experience their maximum water depth between 20 to 40 minutes after the precipitation starts, and as time goes by, the low points get filled up by the water flowing from upstream (minute 40 to minute 60).

Figure 51: aspects of the predicted maximum water depth: (a) maximum water depth predicted by the model for each pixel throughout the simulation, (b) the time of maximum inundation depth in each pixel

Figure 52 demonstrates the flood depth and extent at the end of the one-hour precipitation. As LISFLOOD-FP has reported, by the end of the rainfall, 24791 m² of the watershed would be inundated. The total rainwater volume in the domain is predicted to be 3170.5 m³ as the precipitation ends. The maximum water depth predicted within the simulation area is 93.9 cm; however, the maximum water depth value within the selected watershed (shown by the blue outline) is 30.1 cm (shown by the yellow outline).

Figure 52: flood hazard map of IKT-watershed for a 100-year rain event with a duration of one hour generated by LISFLOOD-FP

The with the yellow outline specified area was chosen for a detailed analysis (Section 6.3).

6.3 Focused analysis

6.3.1 SWMM

As explained in section 6.1, subcatchment-45 with 728 square meter area and J-5 with 3 meters have been selected for a focused analysis. The first focused simulation was performed with only these two watershed elements, which resulted in a 100 % flow routing continuity error and a 49.96 mm surface runoff. Because of the overestimated surface runoff value, the continuity error, and the fact that a simulation without considering the environment of the understudied area and especially having the watershed outlet in the system is not rational, no further adjustment was made for these two elements; instead, the links connecting this subcatchment to the outfall was added to the model (Figure 53).

Figure 53: the selected part of the watershed for a focused analysis

This time, for precipitation of 55 mm, SWMM predicted a total runoff volume of 40 m³ and a total runoff depth of 49.96 mm, whereas the predicted total runoff volume and total runoff depth for the same subcatchment observed within its surrounding environment were 100 m³ and 132.14 mm, respectively. It can be concluded that in this case observing just one spot has resulted in an underestimation of the flood characteristics. Figure 54 shows the expected hydrograph for subcatchment-45 by both simulations next to each other. The green line is the predicted result while observing the subcatchment within the watershed, and the red line is the predicted result of an isolated observation of the subcatchment. Both curves move parallel to each other and the rain intensity. Figure 54 reveals an underestimation of the results again. The only similarity between both simulations was 0 % reported continuity error.

Figure 54: simulation results for subcatchment-45

While junction-5 has the most predicted Total flood volume (20 m³) in the watershed simulation, no flooding was predicted for the isolated simulation. The inflow toward this junction predicted by the watershed simulation was added to the isolated model as a time series to improve the results. The runoff of results did not change at all, and no flooding was reported again.

6.3.2 LISFLOOD-FP

In section 6.2, the watershed part whose predicted flood depth was the maximum within the watershed was selected for a separate analysis. This area has a length of 24 meters and a width of 11 meters, and according to initial estimates, the depth of flood in it will reach 30.1 cm. The simulation of this area was performed based on the method described in sections 5.4 and section 6.2. Figure 55 displays a close-up of the selected area on the left and the predicted water depths when only modeling the selected area in the middle and the predicted water depths when modeling the selected area as a part of the watershed on the right.

Figure 55: different conditions of the predicted most critical area: (a) close up of the area selected for separate analysis, (b) HN-modeling result while observing the selected area alone, (c) HN-modeling result while observing the selected area as a part of the watershed

LISFLOOD-FP calculations settled in 25 seconds, according to which 13.39 m³ of rainwater is accumulated on the area by the end of precipitation (Figure 55, (b)). An underestimation seems to be happening since observing the same area as a part of the whole watershed resulted in 40.61 m³ of rainwater accumulated in the same area (Figure 55, (c)); also, a comparison between the two figures reveals an underestimation of flood extent prediction when the selected area is modeled independently, as expected.

Simple statistical analysis of both maps makes the difference between them more transparent. Based on these analysis results, water depths predicted by small area simulation vary from 0.1 cm to 11.5 cm, with an average of 5 cm of rainwater on the surface (Figure 56, (a)). The outcomes of modeling the same spot as a part of an entire watershed predicted water depths from a minimum of 0.1 cm to a maximum of 30.1 cm with an average of 15 cm (Figure 56, (b)). Relying on these outcomes, observing an area while neglecting the effect of the surrounding environment has led to a decrease in water depth predictions by three times on average.

Cutting out this area, which is located at a low level comparing to the rest of the watershed, has caused overlooking the runoff flowing toward this area, as expected.

An average flood depth of 5 cm proves that again, this means from 5.5 cm rainfall depth 0.5 has been infiltrated, and the rest has been divided between the surface pixels based on their elevations. This easy calculation shows that the software did what it had to do, and the lack of necessary information causes unrealistic results; also, the predicted flood extent seems reasonable because the lower cells have received more water than their surrounding cells (Figure 55).

Figure 56: (a) raster histogram of water depths predicted by and isolated simulation of the area, (b) raster histogram of water depths predicted by and simulation of the area as part of the watershed

6.3.3 Downsizing

The question is, what has caused this difference between the outcomes? Is it the size of the understudied area? Or is it the ignoring of the effect of the surrounding environment of the study area? Would the results be unreliable if a whole watershed of small size, including upstream, downstream, and outlet, was observed?

In order to answer these questions, the watershed and all details related to it were downsized in a way that the surface dimensions were each ten times smaller than the original watershed.

6.3.3.1 SWMM

Downsizing the in section 5.3 generated SWMM model was complicated since the two dimensions of the model components must be reduced to be able to use the same rain intensity. In order to adjust the subcatchments, it was enough to multiply their area by 0.01 and their width by 0.1 and keep the height dimension (here, the infiltration can be seen as the third dimension of the surface) constant. Difficulties arose when setting up the drainage system. First, the height and cross-sectional area of the nodes, as well as the length and cross-sectional area of the conduits, were multiplied by 0.1. This conversion, however, caused an unreasonable slope in the conduits, resulting in unreasonable simulation results. Despite all these inaccuracies and estimates, the simulation results were closer to the simulation results in section 6.1 than the results in section 6.3.1.

In the next step, only the radius of the conduits and nodes were multiplied by 0.1, although this method does not visually reduce the length and width of the initial model of the drainage system by 0.1, since the model is a conceptual model, its results are comparable to the results from section 6.1; this reduces the drainage system's capacity by 0.01, while the slope and height of the pipes and nodes do not change. The program's status report summarizes overall results as follows: a total elapsed time of 10 seconds, 0 percent flow-routing continuity error, and 0 percent runoff-quantity continuity error. By comparing the results of the downsized model with the original model, it is observed that the predicted infiltration values in the two models are exactly equal, and the peak runoff value is exactly 0.01 in the initial model, meaning that the

same peak runoff depth on a surface which have the 0.01 of the original size. It can be concluded that the watershed size does not affect these two components (Appendix H). Unlike the earlier predictions, the runoff depth was not exactly equal in the two models. The diagram below shows the runoff depth recorded by both models for each subcatchment (Figure 57). As shown in the diagram, subcatchment numbers 23, 57, 62, and 63 have the most significant difference in the amount of runoff depth predicted by the main model and runoff depth predicted by the downsized model. It is noteworthy that all four subcatchments are located in pervious areas, and there is not much difference in the urbanized regions. One of the reasons for this occurrence could be that the software focuses on urban runoff modeling. The relative error⁵⁴ observed in this simulation is 4.58%, which is acceptable for this process⁵⁵.

Figure 57: the total runoff amount predicted by the original model compared to the total runoff amount predicted by the downsized model

According to the SWMM report, 25 of the 70 nodes overflow within the course of the simulation. In the original model, only 19 junctions became flooded (Table 17); for all these 19 nodes, an overflow is predicted in the downsized model. Figure 58 shows the location of the six new flooded nodes. These six nodes have one thing in common; a field investigation was not possible for them, junction numbers 20, 24, 76, and 77 are not located within IKT institute property, and a container blocked junction numbers 39 and 40. Although the exact invert elevation of junction number 40 was available in the drainage system map, there was no data about the conduits connected to it, and it was speculated based on the data of junctions neighboring junction number 40. This implies that the smaller the modeling area, the higher the sensitivity to data accuracy. The downsized model’s peak flooding time was the same as the original model, 24 minutes after the model rainfall starts, for all nodes.

Other predictions for the drainage system show a notable difference compared to the main model, and no particular pattern for these differences was detected. Of course, the drainage system is a closed system, and the above-mentioned dissimilarities to the original model affect other acquired results; plus, it was not possible to minimize all drainage system components

⁵⁴ $|\text{mean value}_{\text{main model}} - \text{mean value}_{\text{downsized model}}| / \text{mean value}_{\text{main model}}$ [121].
⁵⁵ The acceptable error varies according to the type of research, and there is no single value to determine the acceptable error, although in general, a value less than 10% is acceptable. In the SWMM manual, 10% has been used as a criterion for allowable error [88], [122].

by exactly 0.1; as a result, a numerical comparison between the original model's predicted values and the scaled-down model is not logical in this case.

Figure 58: additional flooded nodes

The downsized model accurately identified critical points so that closer and more accurate investigations could be carried out in real-time cases; moreover, flooding peak times were also correctly predicted. Despite all the hypotheses and inaccuracies made in the downsized model, its results and predictions for the drainage system have been far better than the model introduced in section 6.3.1.

6.3.3.2 LISFLOOD-FP

In order to change the size of the watershed, it was necessary to use QGIS. The same raster files of DEM and Manning's n used in section 6.2 were used in this section. The length and width of the named raster files became ten times smaller so that the result of this downsizing had a length of 37.6 meters and a width of 16.7 meters (Figure 59).

Figure 59: the difference between the size of the original watershed and the downsized watershed

Attempts were made not to change the height of the cells, but in the process of downsizing, yet, some inevitable impreciseness occurred during the reduction of the watershed extent. The downsized watershed elevation varies from 51.53 m to 67.31 m, while the original watershed elevation varies from 51.51 m to 67.39 m. The simulation of the downsized watershed was performed with the method and settings described in section 5.4. Also, the parameters used for this simulation are exactly the same as the parameters used for the simulation performed in section 6.2. Figure 60 shows the simulation result of the downsized model next to the simulation result of the original model. As can be seen in this figure, the downsized model has been able to predict the extent of the flood well. There is a slight difference in the flood depth, which may be due to impreciseness in the downsizing process.

Figure 60⁵⁶: comparison of the downsized⁵⁷ model with the original model: (a) flood hazard map of the downsized watershed for a 100-year rain event with a duration of one hour generated by LISFLOOD-FP, (b) flood hazard map of the original watershed for a 100-year rain event with a duration of one hour generated by LISFLOOD-FP

The downsized watershed results predict an average of 5.23 cm water depths for the entire area after the precipitation ends, whereas the original model results suggest an average water depth of 5.05 cm after the precipitation ends.

Figure 61 shows the result of repeating all the steps for a second time. This time the DEM of the downsized watershed has a resolution of one meter.

Figure 61: downsizing the model without increasing the dem resolution: (a) DEM of the downsized watershed with a resolution of one meter, (b) predicted hazard map for the downsized watershed with the DEM resolution of one meter

Although one-meter DEM resolution is for modeling relatively large areas (Section 3.2), for modeling small areas, it results in inaccurate and strongly unrealistic predictions (Figure 61, (a)). The simulation result of the downsized watershed with one-meter DEM predicts a uniform water depth of 5 cm for the entire domain (Figure 61, (b)).

⁵⁶ The legend in these models is different from the model in section 6.2; here, the effort was made to clearly show the differences between the downsized and the original model and not the extent of the flood.

⁵⁷ It was not possible to draw the watershed boundaries for the downsized model, which is why it is not shown in this image.

7 Discussion and conclusion

In this section, an attempt is made to evaluate the software products used in this research according to the obtained results. The purpose of this evaluation is to answer the following questions in order to conclude whether freeware products are a good option for simulating heavy rain events:

1. Are the results created by these products rational?

The comparison between the results of the LISFLOOD-FP and the reference map shows that the results obtained for the two-dimensional LISFLOOD-FP surface model are overall logical. It allows the conclusion that both models behave quite similarly in terms of water level and flood extent, provided the calculation method and input data are appropriately selected.

Evaluation of the runoff predicted by the SWMM5 is not as easy as the LISFLOOD-FP. Because the SWMM5 has been mainly designed to model the drainage system and the calculation of surface runoff in such a small watershed depends highly on the watershed division method. However, the quality of the results of the SWMM5 also rationally correspond to the reference map. As discussed in detail in section 6.1, the highest runoff amount was predicted for subcatchment-62, exactly the same area predicted by the LISFLOOD-FP and the reference map as the most critical location. Besides, in the urbanized area, the predicted runoff depth for subcatchments that do not directly access the drainage system or receive runoff from adjacent subcatchments is higher than other subcatchments. Although these results obtained by the SWMM5 model correspond to the reference map and the site observation results, it is noteworthy that these results depend largely on the watershed division method. In fact, in this project, the watershed is divided according to the frequent observations of the watershed on rainy days and also the use of QGIS to accurately discretize the surface and predict the surface flow paths so that non-numerical results obtained for the watershed were predictable before the running of the model.

For the entire watershed, the SWMM5 has calculated an average maximum water depth of 3.42 cm, while the average maximum water depth calculated by the LISFLOOD-FP is 5.91 cm. Considering that the first model transfers a part of the generated runoff by the drainage system, the difference of two centimeters can be justified for the runoff produced by these two models. The results of the SWMM5 model for the drainage system are conceptually in accordance with the observations made. Nodes that are downstream relative to their adjacent nodes, as well as nodes that have less capacity than the runoff volume they collect, overflow. Nevertheless, due to the lack of observational data, it is impossible to statistically assess the flooding volume. This model was also able to show the effect of soil infiltration reasonably. In impervious urban environments, the highest flow rate occurs after precipitation reaches its maximum, but in non-urban environments, the highest flow rate occurs when the soil's infiltration capacity is depleted.

2. Are the input parameters of these products adjustable to achieve realistic results?

Most of the input data of both models are changeable and allow the user to calibrate. However, some input data that can have a significant effect on the results are not changeable.

In the SWMM5, all the data used in this research are adjustable except for some node specifications. In the SWMM5 model, the program does not provide any capability to consider node covers; this may not have much effect in simulating large areas. However, it should be considered when examining small watersheds in great detail. There is also no option to define pipe fittings, and the junction option must be used to create them in the model. In order to prevent flooding in pipe fitting junctions, a surcharge depth higher than the maximum expected hydraulic depth in the whole system should be set. This type of node modeling causes minor inaccuracies in the depth of the nodes as well as the length of the conduits. Also, the entrance area of the junctions is not adjustable for each junction, but the SWMM5 model considers a single adjustable value as the area for all junctions.

The LISFLOOD-FP model is an uncomplicated model that, in some cases, does not allow the users to make changes. In this model, precipitation, as well as infiltration, are considered uniformly throughout the modeling area. Due to the small size of the area studied in this thesis and the high intensity of the selected rain model, these two inefficiencies did not negatively affect the model results. However, they could cause inaccuracies when modeling large regions and spatially nonuniform precipitations. Another noteworthy point in this model is that the cell dimensions are unchangeable and uniform and depend on the DEM resolution. On the one hand, It causes an increase in the number of cells required to achieve comparable accuracy to models that allow having a nonuniform grid; consequently, it causes an increase in computing time to achieve the desired accuracy, and on the other hand, when only a part of the domain has better resolution and demands more data accuracy, but the high-resolution DEM is not available for the other parts of the domain, the high-resolution DEM must be resampled so that its resolution matches with the resolution of the rest of the domain, which can lead to a decrease in the results accuracy.

3. Are these user-friendly?

In order to build a model of the drainage network, i.e., junctions and conduits, this software is very efficient and easy to work with, but to prepare subcatchments, it is necessary to use other GIS software products, which means that in addition to this model, the user must work with another software. Alternatively, the user may define the subcatchments according to personal knowledge, which, to some extent, increases the probability of inaccuracy. This software manual also does not provide sufficient and applicable information on the practical methods of dividing the domain into subcatchments. In this study, the watershed division, defining them in the model, and determining the parameters of each subcatchment was the most time-consuming piece of the whole work. The most significant advantage is the fact that the software is open-source, yet it can easily compete with other 1D models.

A LISFLOOD-FP model is simple to create and run since it has a quite straightforward design, diverse simulation methods, is computationally efficient, and acceptable to non-professionals. Similar to the SWMM5, the model is open-source and provides the possibility to achieve acceptable results for researchers who cannot access or afford commercial products. LISFLOOD-FP gives the user the option to choose between different SWE simplifications based on their modeling goals. The DEM data need preprocessing, which requires the user to employ GIS products. Some error warnings will not be notified to the user and just ignored by

the LISFLOOD-FP; for instance, if the model does not recognize some parameters, there will be no warnings. As a result, in case of a typo in one of these parameters, it will be ignored instead of being addressed by the program, which can cause severe problems with result interpreting.

4. Are these products time-consuming in terms of pre-processing, computational, and post-processing time?

In general, building one-dimensional models is more time consuming than building two-dimensional models. The lack of access to a GIS module in SWMM5 makes it necessary to use another software, which greatly increased the surface data preparation time. In order to calculate the parameters of each subcatchment, such as width, area, and slope, it was necessary to use QGIS. In addition to the time required to prepare this data, the data transfer from the QGIS to this model was time-consuming, and in order to prevent errors during data transfer, it was necessary to check and control this step several times.

The calculation time for this model is very short, and due to modeling a small area, it is not possible to comment much on it because, in the simulation of small domains, the calculation time is not a serious issue; instead, the accuracy of the input data is much more decisive.

The SWMM5 model results are not understandable and usable to the public by themselves and require further processing (no hazard map would be generated). The software itself does not do this processing, but other methods and software products must be used to draw a general conclusion from the outputs. Although this step is not done in this study because it was not intended to be, it could be time-consuming; besides, transferring data from one software to another can always be time-consuming and a source of error.

The similarity between the LISFLOOD-FP and the SWMM5 is that this model also needs a GIS product to prepare the inputs; working with this model also needs a very basic understanding of programming concepts, which of course, is very simple to learn. Although this model itself provides an executable to see the simulation results, the executable is of very low quality and is practically unusable due to repeated errors. Also, the results provided by this model are in particular text file formats, so that the QGIS was needed to gain a visual understanding of them. However, it can be said that if the user has sufficient knowledge of the selected GIS product, the pre-processing and post-processing is very simple and not time-consuming. If the outcomes do not need further analysis and a simple overview of flooding hotspots is enough for the user, the executable meets the user's need.

5. Are these products suitable for micro-scale modeling?

This question's answer depends more on the input data and their accuracy and level of detail than on the software used. In the first software review, it was observed that when a minimal area without considering the surrounding conditions was examined, or even when the inflows from the rest of the watershed were added to the model, the results obtained were far from reality. Nevertheless, when investigating a region with the same surface area but encompassing an entire watershed and sewershed, meaning that it has a complete drainage system, upstream, downstream, and outlet, the answers are much closer to reality. From these outcomes, it can be concluded that for modeling a small environment, the accuracy of the data,

as well as the surrounding conditions that affect this environment, must be considered.

The results obtained from the LISFLOOD-FP are the same as the SWMM, with the one difference that the results showed that in the two-dimensional model when a complete watershed but with a very small surface area is modeled, the obtained results are very similar to the results shown in the reference map, and there is little difference in the results obtained for these two models in terms of flood depth and extent.

It is noteworthy that when downsizing the original model, the resolution of the model also increased, while when the same step was done without increasing the resolution of the DEM, the results were significantly different from the original model. In general, it can be concluded from the results obtained that for this watershed, as the area becomes smaller, the accuracy of the data, the details of the catchment, and the environmental conditions become more effective.

6. Are the freeware products suitable for the new IKT- project, building an experimental facility to perform heavy rain tests at a scale of 1:1?

Choosing the right model depends first and foremost on the purpose of the research. If the institute necessarily insists on using a 1D/2D model, unfortunately, freeware products are not a good option, although much effort has been made in this area; for example, some researchers have developed their model [4]. However, if the requirements of the institute's requirements are met by using one-dimensional or two-dimensional models, they will definitely meet their needs with a few adjustments applied.

Since freeware products are sometimes time-consuming due to the lack of direct access to some features such as a GIS module or due to having non or very basic customer services, and due to the need for basic knowledge in related fields from time to time, the institute should consider whether it is better to pay for the human resources or spend for a commercial software product. Besides, regardless of which software is chosen, it is better to collect all the data with the necessary accuracy and details, i.e., to provide the same or better accuracy as desired for the outputs for the inputs and to avoid uncertainties caused by making modeling assumptions and using recommended values instead collecting the required data.

8 References

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9 Appendix

9.1 Appendix A: SVEs based models

SVEs can be simplified by neglecting some of the terms (Table 18) on the equations (3.2.1 and Section 3.2.5); conventional models extracted from SVEs often used in flood simulators are [123]:

1. Full Dynamic Model: all terms are included
2. Diffusive Wave Model with Inertia: the local acceleration is not included (DWMwl)
3. Gravity Wave Model: the convection acceleration is not included (GWM)
4. Diffusive Wave Model without Inertia: the local and convection accelerations are not included (DWMwol)
5. Kinematic Wave Model: only slope and friction terms are included (KWM)

Table 18: terms of the SVEs [22], [123]

Term	1D	2D (x-direction)	2D (y-direction)
Local acceleration	$\frac{1}{A} \frac{\partial Q}{\partial t}$	$\frac{\partial hU}{\partial t}$	$\frac{\partial hV}{\partial t}$
Convection acceleration	$\frac{1}{A} \frac{\partial(Q^2/A)}{\partial x}$	$\frac{\partial}{\partial x}(hU^2) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(hUV)$	$\frac{\partial}{\partial y}(hV^2) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(hUV)$
Pressure gradient	$g \frac{\partial h}{\partial x}$	$\frac{\partial}{\partial x}(0.5gh^2)$	$\frac{\partial}{\partial y}(0.5gh^2)$
Slope	S_0	S_{0x}	S_{0y}
Friction	S_f	S_{fx}	S_{fy}

Where:

A	flow cross-section area
Q	flow discharge
x, y	space coordinates
t	time
g	gravitational acceleration
h	hydraulic head of water
S_0	bed slope in the longitudinal direction
S_f	friction slope (Equation 5)
U, V	velocity components respectively on the x and y directions
S_{0x}, S_{0y}	bed slopes respectively on the x and y directions
S_{fx}, S_{fy}	friction slopes respectively on the x and y directions

9.2 Appendix B: floodplain n-values

$n = (n_b + n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + n_5)m$	
<i>Where:</i>	
n	<i>Manning's friction coefficient</i>
n_b	<i>a base value of n for the flood plain's natural bare soil surface</i>
n_1	<i>a correction factor for the effect of surface irregularities on the flood plain</i>
n_2	<i>a value for variations in shape and size of the floodplain cross-section assumed to equal 0.0</i>
n_3	<i>a value for obstructions on the flood plain</i>
n_4	<i>a value for vegetation on the flood plain</i>
m	<i>a correction factor for sinuosity of the flood plain, equal to 1.0</i>

Equation 16: floodplain n-values (modified channel method) [73]

The n-value reflects the resistance of the bedding against the flow [24].

Table 19: typical floodplain n-values[124]

Type and description	Min.	Norm.	Max.
Pasture, no brush			
Short grass	0.025	0.030	0.035
High grass	0.030	0.035	0.050
Cultivated areas			
No crop	0.020	0.030	0.040
Mature row crops	0.025	0.035	0.045
Mature field crops	0.030	0.040	0.050
Brush			
Scattered brush, heavy weeds	0.035	0.050	0.070
Light brush and trees, in winter	0.035	0.050	0.060
Light brush and trees, in summer	0.040	0.060	0.080
Medium to dense brush, in winter	0.045	0.070	0.110
Medium to dense brush, in summer	0.070	0.100	0.160
Trees			
Dense willows, summer, straight	0.110	0.150	0.200
Cleared land with tree stumps, no sprouts	0.030	0.040	0.050
Same as above, but with a heavy growth of sprouts	0.050	0.060	0.080
A heavy stand of timber, a few down trees, little undergrowth, flood stage below branches	0.080	0.10	0.120
Same as above, with flood stage reaching branches	0.100	0.12	0.160

9.3 Appendix C: Thiessen polygon method

The basic idea is to split the watershed into several convex polygons; each polygon surrounds exactly one drainage junction and has the property where the associated junction is the closest point to any random point polygon. In this approach, each polygon is practically the area from the intersection of the perpendicular bisectors obtained from the adjacent junction connection. The intersection of these perpendiculars forms polygons known as Thiessen polygons. It is important to connect each junction only to the nearest adjacent junctions (Figure 62) [125], [126].

Figure 62: Thiessen polygon construction procedures [127]

9.4 Appendix D: units of measurement

Table 20: units used in the current SWMM5 model [83]

Parameter	Unit
Area (Subcatchment)	Hectares
Area (Storage unit)	Square meters
Decay Constant (Infiltration)	Hour ⁻¹
Depression Storage	Millimeters
Depth	Meters
Diameter	Meters
Elevation	Meters
Flow	Liters per second (LPS)
Head	Meters
Hydraulic Conductivity	Millimeters per hour
Infiltration Rate	Millimeters per hour
Length	Meters
Manning's n	Second per meter ^{1/3}
Rainfall Volume	Millimeters
Slope (Subcatchment)	Percent
Volume	Cubic meters
Width	Meters

Table 21: units used in the current LISFLOOD-FP model [97]

Parameter	Unit
Area (Subcatchment)	Square meter
Area (Subcatchment)	Square meters
Depth	Meters
Elevation	Meters
Flow	Cubic meter per second
Head	Meters
Infiltration Rate	Meter per second
Length	Meters
Manning's n	Second per meter ^{1/3}
Rainfall Volume	Millimeters per hour
Volume	Cubic meters

9.5 Appendix E: Parameters values

Table 22: subcatchments parameters and their values

Name	Area	Width	%Slope	%Imperv	n-Imperv	n-Perv	d _s -Imperv	d _s -Perv	Subarea routing	f ₀	f _∞	k _d
Unit	[ha]	[m]	[%]	[%]	[-]	[-]	[mm]	[mm]	[-]	[mm]	[mm]	[-]
Sub 01	0.0248	8.67	0.9	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 02	0.0372	12.54	0.9	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 03	0.0347	10.23	2	50	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	pervious	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 04	0.0359	9.55	0.9	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 05	0.0118	8.82	0.3	95	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	pervious	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 06	0.0398	9.13	0.9	90	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 07	0.0059	4.50	0.3	90	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 08	0.022	11.19	0.1	90	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 09	0.0151	1.78	0.1	90	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 10	0.0477	13.58	2	50	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	pervious	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 11	0.0523	13.01	2	50	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	pervious	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 12	0.0792	13.42	5	90	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 13	0.0278	6.89	0.3	41	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 14	0.0066	4.07	0.3	47	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 15	0.037	13.90	0.3	53	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 16	0.008	4.91	0.3	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 17	0.1044	18.03	0.3	83	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 18	0.0435	13.83	0.3	85	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 19	0.0247	13.60	0.3	85	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 20	0.0223	10.03	0.3	85	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 22	0.0327	9.23	0.3	85	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 23	0.0182	6.58	0.3	23	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 24	0.0125	6.54	0.3	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 25	0.0167	6.68	0.3	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 26	0.1113	17.95	5.0	100	0.013	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 27	0.0169	6.01	0.3	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 28	0.0181	10.68	0.3	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 29	0.0032	4.29	0.3	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 31	0.029	11.10	0.3	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 32	0.0179	10.38	0.3	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 33	0.0166	9.93	0.3	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 34	0.0033	2.27	0.3	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 35	0.015	8.88	0.3	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 36	0.0236	10.54	0.3	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 37	0.0412	16.58	0.3	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 38	0.0117	5.31	0.3	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 39	0.0269	9.19	0.3	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 40	0.0539	15.15	0.3	7	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 41	0.0238	11.68	0.3	73	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 42	0.103	16.09	5	100	0.013	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 43	0.0023	2.83	0.1	13	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 44	0.0049	4.46	0.1	23	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 45	0.0728	18.23	0.9	85	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 46	0.0662	16.19	0.9	85	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 47	0.0329	15.20	0.3	90	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 48	0.039	8.71	0.9	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 49	0.0319	7.70	0.9	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 50	0.0519	17.23	0.3	17	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 51	0.0352	16.14	0.3	90	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 52	0.0553	12.97	0.9	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 53	0.0748	17.65	0.9	70	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 54	0.0375	9.21	0.9	61	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 55	0.0523	12.97	0.9	79	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 56	0.034	7.34	0.9	99	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 57	0.7119	41.69	5	1.9	0.011	0.4	1.3	7.62	pervious	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 60	0.0467	17.00	0.3	2	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 61	0.0424	16.45	0.3	2	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 62	0.1355	29.65	5	1.9	0.011	0.4	1.3	7.62	pervious	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 63	0.852	27.69	5	1.9	0.011	0.4	1.3	7.62	pervious	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 66	0.1222	45.82	2	83	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 67	0.075	25.82	2	83	0.013	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 68	0.05	45.82	2	83	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3
Sub 69	0.075	20.00	2	83	0.011	0.2	1.3	5.08	outlet	203.2	100.9	3

Table 23: junctions parameters and their values

Name	Invert elevation	Maximum depth	Initial depth	Surcharged depth
Unit	[m]	[m]	[m]	[m]
J 01	49.96	3.900	0	0
J 02	49.61	3.900	0	0
J 03	50.55	3.000	0	0
J 04	49.43	3.720	0	0
J 05	49.92	3.000	0	0
J 06	50.24	3.000	0	0
J 07	53.46	0.150	0	0
J 09	53.05	0.710	0	0
J 10	51.81	2.300	0	0
J 12	52.55	1.500	0	0
J 13	53.05	0.710	0	0
J 14	53.05	0.700	0	0
J 15	53.05	0.710	0	0
J 16	51.97	1.900	0	0
J 17	53.18	0.600	0	0
J 19	49.26	3.560	0	0
J 20	49.61	3.000	0	0
J 21	52.76	0.700	0	0
J 22	51.68	2.000	0	0
J 23	49.41	3.230	0	0
J 24	49.35	3.000	0	0
J 25	49.02	3.510	0	0
J 26	51.83	0.700	0	0
J 27	49.22	3.000	0	0
J 28	48.83	3.440	0	0
J 29	48.51	3.800	0	0
J 30	52.80	0.700	0	0
J 31	52.77	0.700	0	0
J 32	52.75	0.700	0	0
J 33	50.61	2.880	0.2	0
J 34	52.38	1.050	0	0
J 35	51.58	1.900	1.1	0
J 36	52.77	0.700	0	0
J 37	52.75	0.700	0	0
J 38	52.77	0.700	0	0
J 39	52.73	0.700	0	0
J 40	52.19	1.380	0	0
J 41	52.75	0.700	0	0
J 42	52.34	1.240	0	0
J 43	52.76	0.700	0	0
J 44	52.25	1.440	0	0
J 45	52.74	0.700	0	0
J 46	53.17	0.700	0	0
J 48	53.02	0.700	0	0
J 49	52.97	0.790	0	0
J 50	52.17	1.530	0	0
J 52	52.90	1.100	0.5	0
J 53	53.30	1.240	0	0
J 54	53.47	0.700	0	0
J 55	53.05	11.950	0	0
J 56	53.68	0.700	0	0
J 57	53.73	0.700	0	0
J 58	52.59	0.125	0	15
J 59	53.43	0.125	0	15
J 60	52.76	0.151	0	15
J 61	52.25	0.151	0	15
J 62	52.07	0.151	0	15
J 63	51.74	0.151	0	15
J 64	51.79	0.151	0	15
J 65	51.93	0.151	0	15
J 66	52.05	0.125	0	15
J 67	52.75	0.126	0	15
J 68	52.65	0.126	0	15
J 71	53.04	0.700	0	15
J 72	53.61	0.150	0	15
J 73	53.60	0.150	0	15
J 74	53.65	0.150	0	15
J 75	50.70	2.000	0	0
J 76	50.00	2.000	0	0
J 77	52.00	0.700	0	0

Table 24: conduits parameters and their values

Name	From Node	To Node	Length	Roughness	Inlet offset	Outlet offset	Shape	Depth	Entry loss co.	Exit loss co.
Unit	[-]	[-]	[m]	[-]	[m]	[m]	[-]	[m]	[-]	[-]
C 01	J 1	J 2	32.25	0.015	-	-	circular	0.4	0.5	1
C 02	J 2	J 4	35.21	0.015	-	-	circular	1.4	0.5	1
C 03	J 4	J 19	35.10	0.015	-	-	circular	0.4	0.5	1
C 04	J 19	J 25	35.13	0.015	-	-	circular	0.4	0.5	1
C 05	J 25	J 28	33.56	0.015	-	-	circular	0.4	0.5	1
C 06	J 3	J 1	9.50	0.015	-	-	circular	0.3	0.5	1
C 07	J 6	J 2	8.70	0.015	-	-	circular	0.3	0.5	1
C 08	J 5	J 4	7.50	0.015	-	-	circular	0.3	0.5	1
C 09	J 20	J 19	6.20	0.015	-	-	circular	0.3	0.5	1
C 10	J 24	J 25	4.60	0.015	-	-	circular	0.3	0.5	1
C 11	J 27	J 28	4.50	0.015	-	-	circular	0.4	0.5	1
C 16	J 50	J 2	45.35	0.015	-	-	circular	0.3	0.5	1
C 21	J 42	J 44	16.46	0.015	-	-	circular	0.2	0.5	1
C 24	J 43	J 42	2.58	0.015	-	52.55	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 25	J 44	J 50	25.70	0.015	-	-	circular	0.2	0.5	1
C 28	J 49	J 2	45.48	0.015	-	-	circular	0.3	0.5	1
C 29	J 17	J 16	4.95	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 31	J 15	J 13	3.50	0.015	53.6	53.59	rect open	0.15	0.5	1
C 34	Storage	J 10	8.50	0.015	53.15	-	circular	0.3	0.5	1
C 35	J 10	J 1	19.00	0.015	-	-	circular	0.3	0.5	1
C 42	J 9	J 10	6.20	0.015	-	-	circular	0.1	0.5	1
C 47	J 23	J 25	9.53	0.015	-	-	circular	0.2	0.5	1
C 54	J 36	J 35	2.25	0.015	-	52.68	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 55	J 35	J 34	2.60	0.015	52.68	52.41	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 70	J 63	J 23	15.00	0.015	-	-	circular	0.15	0.5	1
C 71	J 21	J 63	15.75	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 72	J 64	J 63	10.00	0.015	-	-	circular	0.15	0.5	1
C 73	J 33	J 64	19.30	0.015	51.89	-	circular	0.15	0.5	1
C 74	J 31	J 62	3.75	0.015	-	-	circular	0.15	0.5	1
C 75	J 30	J 62	8.18	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 76	J 62	J 33	7.75	0.015	-	-	circular	0.15	0.5	1
C 77	J 34	J 65	3.01	0.015	-	-	circular	0.15	0.5	1
C 78	J 65	J 33	7.91	0.015	-	-	circular	0.15	0.5	1
C 79	J 37	J 66	1.22	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 80	J 66	J 65	2.60	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 82	J 42	J 61	10.40	0.015	-	-	circular	0.15	0.5	1
C 83	J 61	J 40	7.35	0.015	-	-	circular	0.15	0.5	1
C 84	J 41	J 61	2.45	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 85	J 45	J 58	2.91	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 86	J 58	J 44	7.05	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 87	J 46	J 58	21.71	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 88	J 57	J 59	6.86	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 89	J 56	J 59	22.10	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 90	J 59	J 53	11.50	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 91	J 53	J 60	15.29	0.015	-	-	circular	0.15	0.5	1
C 92	J 60	J 50	16.68	0.015	-	-	circular	0.15	0.5	1
C 93	J 54	J 60	31.86	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 96	J 13	J 14	3.50	0.015	53.6	53.59	rect open	0.15	0.5	1
C 99	J 12	J 10	25.10	0.015	-	-	circular	0.1	0.5	1
C 101	J 67	J 68	4.00	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 103	J 13	J 68	6.65	0.015	-	-	circular	0.1	0.5	1
C 104	Storage	J 52	5.80	0.015	53.15	-	circular	0.3	0.5	1
C 107	J 29	Out 1	33.74	0.015	-	-	circular	0.5	0.5	1
C 108	J 15	J 67	3.05	0.015	-	-	circular	0.1	0.5	1
C 109	J 40	J 33	44.03	0.015	-	-	circular	0.15	0.5	1
C 110	J 22	J 23	18.51	0.015	-	-	circular	0.15	0.5	1
C 111	J 32	J 64	3.55	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 112	J 39	J 22	37.62	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 113	J 48	J 50	14.67	0.015	-	-	circular	0.2	0.5	1
C 114	J 52	J 49	32.67	0.015	53.4	-	circular	0.3	0.5	1
C 115	J 55	J 49	18.50	0.015	-	-	circular	0.2	0.5	1
C 116	J 38	J 66	24.41	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 117	J 16	J 12	28.14	0.015	-	-	circular	0.2	0.5	1
C 118	J 71	J 22	17.00	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 119	J 26	J 23	17.00	0.015	49.84	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 120	J 7	J 9	20.00	0.015	53.6	-	rect open	0.15	0.5	1
C 121	J 72	J 14	3.50	0.015	53.59	-	rect open	0.15	0.5	1
C 122	J 73	J 15	3.50	0.015	53.59	-	rect open	0.15	0.5	1
C 123	J 74	J 73	6.92	0.015	-	-	rect open	0.15	0.5	1
C 124	J 68	J 12	4.00	0.015	-	-	circular	0.125	0.5	1
C 125	J 14	J 12	8.47	0.015	-	-	circular	0.1	0.5	1
C 126	J 28	J 29	31.00	0.015	-	-	circular	0.5	0.5	1
C 127	J 75	J 76	30.00	0.015	-	-	circular	0.3	0.5	1
C 130	J 76	J 29	30.00	0.015	-	-	circular	0.3	0.5	1
C 131	J 77	J 75	20.00	0.015	-	-	circular	0.2	0.5	1

9.6 Appendix F: LISFLOOD-FP model inputs

```

DEMfile      DEM_FP.dem.ascii
resroot      acceleration
dirroot      results
sim_time     3600.0
initial_tstep 0.01
massint      0.5
saveint      100.0
manningfile  manning_auto.n.ascii
rainfall     ikt.rain
infiltration 0.000001
voutput
qoutput
mint_hk
elevoff
#acceleration
acceleration
#adaptoff

```

Contents of *.par file used for acceleration solver

```

DEMfile      DEM_FP.dem.ascii
resroot      roe
dirroot      results
sim_time     3600.0
initial_tstep 0.01
massint      0.5
saveint      100.0
manningfile  manning_auto.n.ascii
rainfall     ikt.rain
voutput
qoutput
mint_hk
elevoff
#Roe
Roe
#adaptoff

```

Contents of *.par file used for Roe solver

```

100 years
    13 seconds
    0      0
    54     300
    67.2   600
    91.2   900
    177.6  1200
    43.2   1500
    43.2   1800
    33.6   2100
    33.6   2400
    33.6   2700
    27.6   3000
    27.6   3300
    27.6   3600

```

Contents of *.rain.ascii file, one-hour model precipitation for a 100-year event

9.7 Appendix G: SWMM5 results

Table 25: results predicted by the SWMM5 for the subcatchments

Subcatchment	Total runoff	Total infiltration	Total runoff	Total runoff	Peak runoff
Unit	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[10 ⁶ litr]	[litr/s]
Sub 01	0.00	0.21	53.58	0.01	12.16
Sub 02	0.00	0.21	53.57	0.02	18.23
Sub 03	0.00	10.55	40.91	0.01	12.53
Sub 04	0.00	0.21	53.53	0.02	17.49
Sub 05	0.00	1.05	52.59	0.01	5.80
Sub 06	0.00	2.11	51.23	0.02	18.14
Sub 07	0.00	2.11	51.34	0.00	2.78
Sub 08	0.00	2.11	51.16	0.01	9.82
Sub 09	0.00	2.11	50.54	0.01	5.33
Sub 10	0.00	10.55	40.90	0.02	16.95
Sub 11	0.00	10.55	40.84	0.02	17.39
Sub 12	0.00	2.11	51.32	0.04	37.14
Sub 13	0.00	12.45	37.49	0.01	5.98
Sub 14	0.00	11.18	40.05	0.00	1.75
Sub 15	0.00	9.92	41.40	0.02	10.41
Sub 16	692.75	0.21	746.16	0.06	54.13
Sub 17	0.00	3.59	49.17	0.05	41.25
Sub 18	0.00	3.17	49.89	0.02	18.58
Sub 19	0.00	3.17	50.01	0.01	10.93
Sub 20	0.00	3.16	49.97	0.01	9.75
Sub 22	0.00	3.17	49.86	0.02	13.84
Sub 23	61.8	16.25	91.84	0.02	4.61
Sub 24	0.00	0.21	53.55	0.01	6.11
Sub 25	0.00	0.21	53.50	0.01	8.10
Sub 26	0.00	0.00	53.81	0.06	54.48
Sub 27	0.00	0.21	53.48	0.01	8.15
Sub 28	0.00	0.21	53.57	0.01	8.87
Sub 29	0.00	0.21	53.67	0.00	1.58
Sub 31	42.43	0.21	95.03	0.03	14.89
Sub 32	0.00	0.21	53.57	0.01	8.77
Sub 33	0.00	0.21	53.57	0.01	8.14
Sub 34	0.00	0.21	53.59	0.00	1.62
Sub 35	0.00	0.21	53.57	0.01	7.35
Sub 36	0.00	0.21	53.52	0.01	11.49
Sub 37	0.00	0.21	53.50	0.02	19.98
Sub 38	0.00	0.21	53.53	0.01	5.70
Sub 39	0.00	0.21	53.47	0.01	12.95
Sub 40	0.00	19.62	27.12	0.01	3.99
Sub 41	0.00	5.70	46.87	0.01	9.14
Sub 42	0.00	0.00	53.81	0.06	50.39
Sub 43	0.00	18.36	30.85	0.00	0.24
Sub 44	0.00	16.25	33.31	0.00	0.70
Sub 45	82.27	3.17	132.14	0.10	88.38
Sub 46	0.00	3.17	49.96	0.03	28.84
Sub 47	0.00	2.11	51.26	0.02	15.13
Sub 48	0.00	0.21	53.49	0.02	18.89
Sub 49	0.00	0.21	53.51	0.02	15.49
Sub 50	0.00	17.51	30.75	0.02	5.34
Sub 51	0.00	2.11	51.25	0.02	16.18
Sub 52	0.00	0.21	53.50	0.03	26.83
Sub 53	0.00	6.33	46.03	0.03	27.30
Sub 54	0.00	8.23	43.65	0.02	12.11
Sub 55	0.00	4.43	48.41	0.03	21.37
Sub 56	0.00	0.21	53.49	0.02	16.44
Sub 57	0.00	20.70	18.59	0.13	34.88
Sub 60	0.00	20.68	26.35	0.01	3.61
Sub 61	0.00	20.68	26.53	0.01	3.35
Sub 62	206.9	20.70	216.04	0.29	68.91
Sub 63	0.00	20.70	14.48	0.12	28.47
Sub 66	0.00	3.59	49.58	0.06	54.81
Sub 67	0.00	3.59	49.23	0.04	33.44
Sub 68	0.00	3.59	49.34	0.02	23.65
Sub 69	0.00	3.59	49.21	0.04	32.96

Table 26: results predicted by the SWMM5 for the junctions

Node	Average depth	Max. depth	Max. HGL	Time of max. depth	Max. inflow	Time of max. inflow	Total inflow volume
Unit	[m]	[m]	[m]	[hh:mm]	[litr/s]	[hh:mm]	[10 ⁶ litr]
J 01	0.29	3.29	53.25	00:24	79.04	00:28	0.1590
J 02	0.38	3.63	53.24	00:24	180	00:28	0.4530
J 03	0.18	2.71	53.26	00:24	26.82	00:16	0.0200
J 04	0.38	3.49	52.92	00:24	223.57	00:28	0.5500
J 05	0.23	3.00	52.92	00:21	91.52	00:24	0.0963
J 06	0.21	3.00	53.24	00:22	18.14	00:24	0.0205
J 07	0.08	0.15	53.61	01:03	2.5	01:03	0.0003
J 09	0.02	0.58	53.63	00:25	12.6	00:24	0.0143
J 10	0.09	1.44	53.25	00:25	66.69	00:28	0.1290
J 12	0.05	0.94	53.49	00:26	12.21	00:21	0.0105
J 13	0.03	0.54	53.59	00:25	5.33	00:24	0.0076
J 14	0.01	0.44	53.49	00:26	1.63	00:22	0.0001
J 15	0.01	0.46	53.51	00:26	1.35	00:22	0.0001
J 16	0.41	1.52	53.49	00:26	4.15	00:21	0.0030
J 17	0.01	0.31	53.49	00:26	1.34	00:22	0.0007
J 19	0.34	3.27	52.53	00:24	243.11	00:26	0.6000
J 20	0.22	2.94	52.55	00:24	28.84	00:24	0.0331
J 21	0.03	0.70	53.46	00:22	15.13	00:24	0.0169
J 22	0.03	1.12	52.80	00:25	17.67	00:24	0.0207
J 23	0.26	3.09	52.50	00:25	65.18	00:24	0.1550
J 24	0.19	2.57	51.92	00:24	21.37	00:24	0.0253
J 25	0.31	2.89	51.91	00:24	332.34	00:23	0.8090
J 26	0.03	0.70	52.53	00:24	7.6	00:21	0.0160
J 27	0.05	1.22	50.44	00:25	12.11	00:24	0.0164
J 28	0.16	1.61	50.44	00:25	369.16	00:24	0.8600
J 29	0.15	1.29	49.80	00:25	505.78	00:24	1.0100
J 30	0.06	0.70	53.50	00:19	12.95	00:24	0.0144
J 31	0.06	0.70	53.47	00:19	19.98	00:24	0.0220
J 32	0.02	0.53	53.28	00:25	3.99	02:04	0.0146
J 33	1.17	2.85	53.46	00:24	35.15	00:18	0.0814
J 34	0.13	1.05	53.43	00:18	18.49	00:24	0.0204
J 35	0.86	1.88	53.46	00:24	6.29	00:18	0.0123
J 36	0.06	0.70	53.47	00:18	11.49	00:24	0.0126
J 37	0.06	0.70	53.45	00:19	7.52	00:24	0.0080
J 38	0.08	0.70	53.47	00:17	14.89	00:24	0.0276
J 39	0.02	0.47	53.20	00:25	8.77	00:24	0.0096
J 40	0.15	1.31	53.50	00:24	13.43	00:18	0.0223
J 41	0.04	0.70	53.45	00:20	9.29	00:24	0.0039
J 42	0.09	1.16	53.50	00:24	21.03	00:18	0.0353
J 43	0.04	0.70	53.46	00:20	15.53	00:24	0.0109
J 44	0.13	1.26	53.51	00:24	30.83	00:18	0.0670
J 45	0.05	0.70	53.44	00:20	11.89	00:24	0.0198
J 46	0.04	0.70	53.87	00:21	13.84	00:24	0.0163
J 48	0.04	0.70	53.72	00:21	54.13	00:24	0.0597
J 49	0.02	0.42	53.39	00:25	47.42	00:24	0.0559
J 50	0.09	1.33	53.50	00:24	89.3	00:18	0.2010
J 52	0.20	0.34	53.24	00:27	5.98	00:24	0.0109
J 53	0.11	1.24	54.54	00:21	41.25	00:24	0.0730
J 54	0.04	0.70	54.17	00:20	9.75	00:24	0.0111
J 55	0.05	0.74	53.79	00:24	37.14	00:24	0.0406
J 56	0.08	0.70	54.38	00:16	22.88	00:24	0.0237
J 57	0.06	0.70	54.43	00:20	13.91	00:24	0.0134
J 58	0.07	0.92	53.51	00:25	10.66	00:21	0.0316
J 59	0.10	1.01	54.44	00:21	10.72	00:16	0.0247
J 60	0.12	1.35	54.11	00:25	31.42	00:18	0.0779
J 61	0.13	1.24	53.49	00:25	13.65	00:18	0.0220
J 62	0.21	1.40	53.47	00:24	15.87	00:19	0.0281
J 63	0.07	1.37	53.11	00:25	34.24	00:18	0.0998
J 64	0.19	1.48	53.27	00:25	26.91	00:18	0.0833
J 65	0.26	1.52	53.45	00:25	16.01	00:17	0.0432
J 66	0.24	1.40	53.45	00:24	9.19	00:17	0.0285
J 67	0.03	0.76	53.51	00:26	5.67	00:21	0.0004
J 68	0.05	0.86	53.51	00:26	8.56	00:21	0.0080
J 71	0.00	0.00	53.04	00:00	0	00:00	0.0000
J 72	0.00	0.00	53.61	00:00	0	00:00	0.0000
J 73	0.00	0.00	53.60	00:00	0	00:00	0.0000
J 74	0.00	0.00	53.65	00:00	0	00:00	0.0000
J 75	0.02	0.15	50.85	00:25	66.32	00:24	0.0738
J 76	0.03	0.60	50.60	00:25	120.83	00:24	0.1340
J 77	0.02	0.09	52.09	00:24	32.96	00:24	0.0369
Outfall	0.11	0.50	48.50	00:20	505.84	00:25	1.0100
Storage	0.09	0.18	53.23	00:27	80.22	00:24	0.1370

9.8 Appendix H: comparing the downsized model with the original model

Table 27: comparing the SWMM5 results for original and downsized models

Subcatchment	Total infiltration [mm]		Total runoff [mm]		Peak runoff [liter/s]	
	Main model	Downsized model	Main model	Downsized model	Main model	Downsized model
Sub 01	0.21	0.21	53.58	53.77	12.16	0.12
Sub 02	0.21	0.21	53.57	53.77	18.23	0.18
Sub 03	10.55	10.55	40.91	41.32	12.53	0.17
Sub 04	0.21	0.21	53.53	53.76	17.49	0.18
Sub 05	1.05	1.05	52.59	52.77	5.8	0.06
Sub 06	2.11	2.11	51.23	51.48	18.14	0.2
Sub 07	2.11	2.11	51.34	51.51	2.78	0.03
Sub 08	2.11	2.11	51.16	51.46	9.82	0.11
Sub 09	2.11	2.11	50.54	51.32	5.33	0.07
Sub 10	10.55	10.55	40.9	41.32	16.95	0.24
Sub 11	10.55	10.55	40.84	41.31	17.39	0.26
Sub 12	2.11	2.11	51.32	51.5	37.14	0.39
Sub 13	12.45	12.45	37.49	38.87	5.98	0.09
Sub 14	11.18	11.18	40.05	40.54	1.75	0.03
Sub 15	9.92	9.92	41.4	42.03	10.41	0.15
Sub 16	0.21	0.21	746.16	749.22	54.13	0.55
Sub 17	3.59	3.59	49.17	49.64	41.25	0.49
Sub 18	3.17	3.16	49.89	50.2	18.58	0.21
Sub 19	3.17	3.17	50.01	50.23	10.93	0.12
Sub 20	3.16	3.16	49.97	50.22	9.75	0.11
Sub 22	3.17	3.17	49.86	50.19	13.84	0.16
Sub 23	16.25	16.25	91.84	101.25	4.61	0.09
Sub 24	0.21	0.21	53.55	53.77	6.11	0.06
Sub 25	0.21	0.21	53.5	53.75	8.1	0.08
Sub 26	0	0	53.81	54.02	54.48	0.55
Sub 27	0.21	0.21	53.48	53.75	8.15	0.08
Sub 28	0.21	0.21	53.57	53.77	8.87	0.09
Sub 29	0.21	0.21	53.67	53.8	1.58	0.02
Sub 31	0.21	0.21	95.03	99.86	14.89	0.21
Sub 32	0.21	0.21	53.57	53.77	8.77	0.09
Sub 33	0.21	0.21	53.57	53.77	8.14	0.08
Sub 34	0.21	0.21	53.59	53.78	1.62	0.02
Sub 35	0.21	0.21	53.57	53.77	7.35	0.07
Sub 36	0.21	0.21	53.52	53.76	11.49	0.12
Sub 37	0.21	0.21	53.5	53.75	19.98	0.2
Sub 38	0.21	0.21	53.53	53.76	5.7	0.06
Sub 39	0.21	0.21	53.47	53.74	12.95	0.13
Sub 40	19.62	19.62	27.12	30.05	3.99	0.09
Sub 41	5.7	5.7	46.87	47.17	9.14	0.11
Sub 42	0	0	53.81	54.02	50.39	0.51
Sub 43	18.36	18.36	30.85	31.83	0.24	0.01
Sub 44	16.25	16.25	33.31	34.35	0.7	0.02
Sub 45	3.17	3.17	132.14	132.78	88.38	0.91
Sub 46	3.17	3.17	49.96	50.21	28.84	0.32
Sub 47	2.11	2.11	51.26	51.49	15.13	0.16
Sub 48	0.21	0.21	53.49	53.75	18.89	0.19
Sub 49	0.21	0.21	53.51	53.76	15.49	0.16
Sub 50	17.51	17.51	30.75	32.71	5.34	0.12
Sub 51	2.11	2.11	51.25	51.49	16.18	0.17
Sub 52	0.21	0.21	53.5	53.75	26.83	0.27
Sub 53	6.33	6.33	46.03	46.39	27.3	0.34
Sub 54	8.23	8.23	43.65	44.09	12.11	0.16
Sub 55	4.43	4.43	48.41	48.69	21.37	0.25
Sub 56	0.21	0.21	53.49	53.75	16.44	0.17
Sub 57	20.7	20.7	18.59	25.79	34.88	0.66
Sub 60	20.68	20.68	26.35	28.83	3.61	0.08
Sub 61	20.68	20.68	26.53	28.85	3.35	0.08
Sub 62	20.7	20.7	216.04	336.76	68.91	1.57
Sub 63	20.7	20.7	14.48	25.14	28.47	0.74
Sub 66	3.59	3.59	49.58	49.74	54.81	0.6
Sub 67	3.59	3.59	49.23	49.41	33.44	0.37
Sub 68	3.59	3.59	49.34	49.44	23.65	0.25
Sub 69	3.59	3.59	49.21	49.4	32.96	0.37

Eidesstattliche Erklärung

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich die vorliegende wissenschaftliche Arbeit selbständig ohne fremde Hilfe verfasst habe. Es wurden keine anderen als die in der Arbeit angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel benutzt. Die den benutzten Quellen wörtlich oder inhaltlich entnommenen Stellen habe ich als solche kenntlich gemacht.

Bochum, den 10.02.2021

Farzaneh Sadeghi

Unterschrift

Declaration

I hereby declare that I have written this scientific work on my own without any external help. No sources and aids other than those indicated in the thesis have been used. I have acknowledged those passages taken from the sources used, either verbatim or in terms of content.

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